

**JOB SATISFACTION AND MOTIVATION
AMONG FILIPINO NURSES IN THE UNITED ARAB EMIRATES**

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**JOB SATISFACTION AND MOTIVATION
AMONG FILIPINO NURSES IN THE UNITED ARAB EMIRATES**

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[SEP]

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Acceptance Page

This thesis titled “**JOB SATISFACTION AND MOTIVATION AMONG FILIPINO NURSES IN THE UNITED ARAB EMIRATES**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Arts in Nursing.

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BIOGRAPHICAL SKETCH

Meridein Sanchez Pacamana, PH-RN, HAAD-RN is an accomplished and compassionate global healthcare professional with a diverse background that spans across various dynamic industries and countries in different parts of world. With more than 10 years of Nursing experience, she was born with a passion for service and a desire to explore the world. She has carved an impressive career path in the tourism, hospitality, entertainment, and in the medical field that showcases her commitment to excellence and caring for others.

In 2009, Meridein graduated with a Bachelor of Science in Nursing from the prestigious Centro Escolar University. Armed with a strong foundation in healthcare and a genuine interest in patient care, she embarked on her journey as a licensed certified Nurse in Abu Dhabi, UAE, where she obtained accreditation from the Health Authority Abu Dhabi (HAAD). Her career took an exciting turn when she joined Emirates Airlines as a flight crew member. During her time with the esteemed airline, Meridein honed her communication skills and further developed her ability to handle diverse situations. She not only became adept at providing in-flight medical assistance but also learned to offer support and comfort to passengers from all walks of life. After her enriching experience in aviation, Meridein expanded her horizons and explored the hospitality industry. She became a valued member of international hotels, leaving a positive impact on guests and colleagues alike. Her empathetic nature, dedication to excellence, innovative work approaches, and exceptional interpersonal skills made her an asset to the establishments she served.

A firm believer in lifelong learning, Meridein's thirst for knowledge led her to pursue higher education in the nursing practice. In 2023, she became a candidate for a Master of Art in Nursing at the University of the Philippines Open University. Her dedication to education demonstrates her commitment to staying at the forefront of the nursing profession, seeking to enhance her skills and knowledge to provide the best possible care to her patients. She is known for her unwavering dedication, kindness, and genuine concern for the well-being of others. Her patients and colleagues admire her for the compassion she brings to her nursing practice, always going above and beyond to ensure those under her care feel valued and supported. Beyond her professional achievements, Meridein is a true globetrotter at heart. Her time as a flight crew member allowed her to indulge her love for traveling and experiencing different cultures. This exposure to diverse backgrounds has shaped her into a more understanding and open-minded individual.

Today, her life journey is a testament to her passion for nursing, caregiving and exploration. As a licensed certified Nurse in Abu Dhabi, she continues to touch the lives of those in need, providing comfort and expert care at Health Authority Abu Dhabi (HAAD) in Al Ain, Abu Dhabi through Aspen Medical UAE. Her strong combined experience as a nursing professional, a former flight crew member, and as an associate of international hotels has enriched her understanding of people needs where she has tactically enhanced her interpersonal skills. With her pursuit of higher education in nursing, Meridein is poised to make even greater contributions to the healthcare field. As she balances her academic endeavors with her profession, she remains a source of inspiration to both aspiring nurses and seasoned healthcare professionals alike.

On the 23rd of September 2023, her dedication, perseverance, and hard work were duly recognized when she received the prestigious distinction of being named one of the Top 100 Healthcare Professionals in the Middle East by The Filipino Times in Dubai, United Arab Emirates. Notably, this special event garnered support from the Philippine Embassy in Abu Dhabi, UAE, under the esteemed leadership of His Excellency, Honorable Alfonso Ferdinand A. Ver, the Ambassador of the Republic of the Philippines to the United Arab Emirates.

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At this juncture, as I find myself at the pinnacle of my master's thesis journey, I am humbled and would like to express my gratitude towards the continuous support that I received from numerous individuals who have played a significant role in achieving this milestone. The culmination of my study signifies the conclusion of a challenging yet fulfilling journey, with numerous individuals making significant contributions to its accomplishment. This task would not have been possible without the unwavering commitment and assistance provided by the individuals involved. This milestone exemplifies the support by those who believed in what I can accomplish who have shown faith in my abilities and remained steadfast during this transformative journey.

I start by expressing my gratitude to God for His perpetual blessings and unwavering guidance. His presence has served as a stabilizing force, consistently providing drive during both the positive and negative aspects of this endeavor. God's presence served as my shining armor which has blessed and guided me in navigating the complexities of life. He has provided me with the fortitude and perseverance necessary to overcome challenges and seize moments of growth and advancement towards this path.

To my ex-boyfriend and now my beloved husband, Dr. Fernando "Jann" Reyes Jr., I am extremely thankful for your steadfast support and understanding. Your compassion and encouragement were invaluable during the periods when my rigorous job schedules dominated my time. I could not have surmounted the trials that came my way without your unshakable faith in me. Your constant encouragement has been a rock for me during these trying times. I owe my accomplishment to you because your love and belief in me spurred me onward.

A heartfelt dedication goes to my precious children, Allen and Amirah Alisha. Your boundless enthusiasm, love, and resilience have been the driving force behind my pursuit of academic excellence. Your unwavering presence has motivated me to push forward and achieve my goals.

I extend my sincere appreciation to my parents, Josie and Oscar Pacamana, and also to my mother-in-law, Nida Erana Reyes and late father-in-law, Vicente Fernando J. Reyes, Sr., for their unwavering determination and sacrifices. Your relentless efforts, even when faced with night-to-day shifts, have been the foundation upon which I built my educational aspirations. Your sacrifices have not gone unnoticed, and I am forever grateful.

I am indebted to my research adviser, Prof. Queenie Roxas-Ridulme, whose guidance and mentorship have been invaluable. Your expertise and unwavering belief in my potential have been instrumental in shaping this research study and ensuring its successful completion.

To Chancellor Melinda Bandalaria of the University of the Philippines Open University, your inspiration and encouragement have been a driving force behind my determination

to succeed. Your reminder that hard work can conquer any obstacle has been a constant motivation.

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This achievement is dedicated to all the nurses worldwide who exemplified unwavering dedication and compassion, particularly during the challenging times of the COVID-19 pandemic. Your selflessness has inspired me and countless others.

A special acknowledgment is owed to the Philippine Embassy Abu Dhabi, led by Ambassador Alfonso Ferdinand A. Ver, for their official endorsement of my Thesis Study. I also extend my gratitude to the research participants from the Philippine Nursing Association in the United Arab Emirates, under the leadership of Red Decaleng Capuyan. Your support and participation were invaluable to the completion of my thesis.

As I anticipate the day, I proudly don the University of the Philippines Sablay on graduation day, I am filled with excitement and gratitude. This emblem of success will forever remind me of the remarkable journey I undertook as a graduate of the University of the Philippines.

In these years of relentless commitment, I feel deeply humbled, and immensely grateful to each one of you who has been a part of my academic journey. Thank you for your endless support, motivation, and direction to allow me to achieve this incredible accomplishment. This milestone is due to the collaborative work of such amazing people (for which I will always be grateful). Thank you to all those who had any say in the making of this journey — from the deepest reaches of my being. And that has been made possible through the collective support, motivation, and guidance I have received along the way.

In closing, I would want to reiterate my heartfelt appreciation and recognize all the countless number of unsung heroes who have inspired me along this challenging path towards academic success. While it is impossible to write all your names in this acknowledgement, I would like to let you all know how sincerely grateful I am towards your unwavering support. Your boundless energy, enthusiasm, and sound advice allowed me to achieve the unachievable feat. This accomplishment is the result of all these unique individuals working together, and for that, I will be eternally grateful. This accolade acts as a symbolic representation of the communal encouragement and support that has propelled my academic progression and success. Once again, thank you to all of you from the depths of my heart for being an essential part of this amazing escapade. You will always be etched in my heart, always and forevermore.

DEDICATION

I humbly dedicate my master's thesis to the divine presence of God, whose infinite wisdom has guided me throughout this academic journey. In profound gratitude, I extend my dedication to my cherished family, whose unwavering love and encouragement have been my steadfast support. Your sacrifices and belief in me have been the driving force behind my accomplishments, and this thesis is a tribute to your enduring faith.

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ABSTRACT

The influx of Filipino nurses into the United Arab Emirates (UAE) has notably transformed the healthcare landscape, with these dedicated cadre of professionals constituting a significant portion of the nursing workforce. Filipino nurses have been a substantial and indispensable element, contributing significantly to the efficient functioning of the UAE's healthcare system. The Filipino diaspora in healthcare settings worldwide is marked by its resilience, adaptability, and unwavering dedication to patient care. These dedicated healthcare professionals contribute significantly to the country's healthcare infrastructure. However, their job satisfaction and motivation have remained relatively underexplored despite their pivotal role, creating a conspicuous void in existing research within the domain of nursing workforce management.

The existing body of research on nursing in the UAE predominantly centers on clinical practices, healthcare management, and patient outcomes. However, the psychosocial dimensions of job satisfaction and motivation among Filipino nurses in this unique context have been left conspicuously understudied. This gap in the literature presents an urgent call for investigation and this conspicuous lacuna in the literature necessitates a dedicated investigation into the job satisfaction and motivation levels of Filipino nurses in the UAE. Understanding the determinants that influence job satisfaction and motivation is not only academically pertinent but also imperative for healthcare practitioners, policymakers, and administrators. By exploring the unique experiences, challenges, and factors that influence the job satisfaction and motivation of Filipino nurses, this research seeks to contribute substantially to the ongoing intellectual discourse surrounding the healthcare labor force, not only for Filipino Nursing Expatriates around the world but moreover, those who are based in the Philippines, thereby underscoring its significance to scholars, educators, students, and practitioners alike.

Conducting the type of study for the first time among Kabayan Nurses in the Middle East, this quantitative research investigated the correlation of job satisfaction and motivation of 117 Filipino nursing participants employed across the seven states of the United Arab Emirates (UAE). All research participants were licensed nurses and certified members of the Philippine Nursing Association in the UAE, reflecting a homogeneous and well-defined sample. The research received full support from the Philippine Embassy in Abu Dhabi, emphasizing its significance.

Data for this study were collected using structured questionnaires distributed through an online survey platform, specifically Google Forms. The study employed a descriptive correlational research design, utilizing statistical measures such as mode, percentage, and mean to provide an overview of key aspects within the collected data. Furthermore, inferential statistics, including Pearson's correlation coefficient and Chi-square analysis, were utilized to draw conclusions based on the sample data, enabling an exploration of the relationship between job satisfaction and motivation.

As a result, the research yielded significant insights, as the Filipino Nurses who took part in the study exhibited positive levels of job satisfaction and motivation. Their

responses underscored a consensus across various dimensions of their work environment, including aspects like salary, job security, working conditions, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision qualities, and interpersonal relationships.

Significantly, the research established a strong positive correlation between job satisfaction and motivation among Filipino nurses in the United Arab Emirates. This implies that as job satisfaction levels increase, motivation levels also tend to rise, underscoring the importance of enhancing job satisfaction to boost motivation among this demographic. This finding has profound implications for healthcare organizations and policymakers in the UAE, suggesting that improving job satisfaction can be an effective strategy for enhancing nurses' work motivation.

Interestingly, the study revealed that job satisfaction and motivation remained unaffected by the demographic and professional profiles of Filipino nurses in the UAE. This highlights the complexity of these constructs, suggesting that factors beyond traditional profiling have a more significant impact on job satisfaction and motivation. This underscores the need for healthcare organizations and policymakers to adopt a broader and more comprehensive approach to address nurses' well-being and job satisfaction.

This pedagogical research contributed significantly to the body of knowledge as it illuminated the relationship between job satisfaction and motivation among Filipino nurses in the UAE. The findings provided valuable insights for healthcare organizations and policymakers in the Emirates, underscoring the significance of prioritizing job satisfaction as a means to enhance nurses' motivation. As a result, it was recommended that healthcare organizations in the country should have focused on creating work environments conducive to job satisfaction. This would have included fair compensation, job security, and nurturing positive interpersonal relationships, all of which were believed to have the potential to increase motivation levels among their Filipino nursing workforces.

Furthermore, this study calls for further research into the complex dynamics of job satisfaction and motivation in nursing, with the aim of offering a more comprehensive understanding of these critical factors within healthcare settings.

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Background and Rationale of the Study

Job satisfaction and motivation are the main domains in the fields of human resource management and human resource development (Swedana, 2023). All the pedagogical and scholarly research in these domains is of paramount importance (Panda and Chowdhury, 2017). As job satisfaction is thought of as an individual's emotional response to their current employment condition, motivation is viewed as the driving force to pursue and meet individual employees' needs (Ayalew, 2019). Both are considered imperative to one another as the workforce commits themselves to obtaining all the necessary competencies to achieve certain expectations from top management (Armstrong, 2014). As a result, job performance is seen as an indicator that connects employee gratification and commitment in their working environment; therefore, its result mainly highlights the increase and decrease of staff effectiveness at both individual, team, and organizational levels (Panda and Chowdhury, 2017). To date, understanding this phenomenon is one of the central focuses of medical directors and administrators, which can be observed in the field of nursing practice today. Medical practitioners today believe that performance has a direct impact on job satisfaction and motivation to provide the highest level of medical and nursing care, particularly during the surge of the Omnicron COVID virus in different parts of the world (Volpe, 2021; Ivy, 2022).

Among the 679,819 Filipinos in the United Arab Emirates, there are about 30,000 Filipino nurses, and many of them are working on the front lines (Dass, 2020). During times of pandemic, Filipino nurses are considered today's modern heroes and warriors

who work on the front lines of the United Arab Emirates (UAE's) efforts to fight COVID-19 (Filipino Times, 2018). To measure their nurses' effort in providing quality care in their line of duty, it is significant for healthcare administrators to determine the best approach on how they can maintain the nurses level of performance and their commitment to winning against the COVID-19 pandemic (Volpe, 2021).

The main nursing job functions, key performance indicators (KPI), and key results areas (KRA) are highlighted by the hospital's human resources and mainly the hospital management team as key elements in assessing their nursing team's overall performance. These outcomes may be attributed to the kind of motivation and satisfaction that the nurses received from the organization that they work for (Vacharakiat et al., 2008; Eslami and Gharakhani, 2012).

Today's organizations treat their employees as their major investment to fulfill their companies' ambitions and purposes (CIPD, 2017). These occur when employees are sent in for induction and the new staff comprehends their new job through training and development. Moreover, each organization invests by providing employee welfare and retention programs to keep the staff's spirit high and always motivated (CIPD, 2015). Therefore, each human resource manager and the executive team, at all costs, must minimize employees' turnover (Meaghan et al., 2002). Based on the current scholarly literature from all aspects of profession and pedagogical studies, there is a strong need to understand how job satisfaction of nurses' affects motivation (Gutierrez, Candela, and Carver, 2012; Lu, Barriball, Zhang, While, 2012; Swedana, 2023). Furthermore, job satisfaction is a key issue for health care professionals around the world (Doef, Mbazzi, and Verhoeven 2012). Price and Muller (1986) defined job satisfaction as the degree of

positive affective orientation toward employment. This definition is similar to Vroom's (1964) understanding of job satisfaction as the explicit attitude toward the job. Joslin et al. (2010) suggested that job satisfaction is best defined by work attitudes and the perceived acceptance of work-related standards. On the other hand, Laffarney (2018) identified motivation as a need or drive that energizes a nursing employee toward achieving a certain goal. Motivation can be acknowledged as intrinsic or extrinsic. Intrinsic motivation is self-directed. A person does something because he or she enjoys the phenomenon and sees it as gratifying based on how he sees reality. On the other hand, extrinsic motivation is seen as an external reward or to avoid negative consequences (Laffarney, 2018). Scholars stressed that there is a significant need to develop a fuller understanding of how performance affects the overall competitiveness of each employee and their work outcomes, in particular, the factors by which motivation and job satisfaction determine the level of competency that each nurse provides as a result of their performances in their respective employers. (CIPD 2015; CIPD 2017).

In this view, regrettably, there are gaps of knowledge and research in the field of human resources in nursing administration for nursing performance management platforms, particularly in understanding how job satisfaction affects the work motivation of Filipino expatriates in a foreign country and at international levels (Filipino Times, 2018; Petancio, 2018). Hospital human resource practitioners, nursing administrators, and its management must recognize that their staff are considered contributors and the building blocks of the organization's success (Abbasi et al., 2000; Kumar, 2016). Moreover, human resource practitioners' challenge today is how to ensure that they maintain the level of competitiveness of nursing professionals. (Duffield et al., 2014; Price & Reichert,

2017). These gaps can be better identified with the help of understanding how performance management can contribute to the improvement of patient customer service experiences and provide a better knowledge base for operating more efficient organizations (Agbano, 2016). With all these consequences, if the performance of nursing staff is not sustained, the result may be a declining financial standing and an increase in manpower costs in the hospital sector (Lin & Jones, 2013; Wong & Laschinger, 2013). Moreover, the design and implementation of the performance measurement system have an effect on the results (successful or otherwise) of the measures (Hewko & Cummings, 2016) and open a door for scholars to understand how job satisfaction affects motivation and can lead to higher performance outcomes that are centered on quality and excellence for nursing professionals in the United Arab Emirates and around the world (Hidayat, Agustin, & Ningsih, 2017).

In these current phenomena, as we are fast approaching continuous globalization, these occurrences merely postulate that a great deal of academic scholarship has emphasized the need to identify how job satisfaction can affect work motivation and possibly increase employee performance in hospitals and nursing facilities (Trivellas, 2011; Wong and Laschinger, 2013; Bell, 2015; Rhodes & Collins, 2015; Akinyomi, 2016; Hidayat, Agustin, & Ningsih, 2017; Price & Reichert, 2017; Swedana, 2023).

For the Overseas Filipino Workers (OFW) in the field of nursing practice, it is part of their legacy around the world to always ensure that Filipino nurses provide the highest quality of service to our employers and their clienteles. The overall outcome of this study will be a significant addition to the body of knowledge in nursing studies. In achieving excellence and innovation at the workplace, the purpose of this research is to determine

whether job satisfaction has a significant relationship with work motivation among Filipino nurses in the United Arab Emirates.

Statement of the Problem

This research aims to determine the correlation between Filipino nurses' job satisfaction and work motivation in the United Arab Emirates. This will conduct a cross-sectional study among the members of the Philippine Nursing Association—UAE Chapter in the Seven States of the United Arab Emirates. The seven states of the United Arab Emirates include Abu Dhabi, Dubai, Ajman, Al Ain, Sharjah, Fujairah, and Ras Al Khaimah.

By examining the relationship between job satisfaction and work motivation in this specific context, this research strives to uncover the underlying causes influencing the job-related contentment and motivation levels of Filipino nurses in the diverse healthcare landscape of the United Arab Emirates.

Below are the research objectives of the study.

- 1. To determine the level of job satisfaction of nurses in terms of the following:**
 - 1.1. Responsibilities
 - 1.2. Rewards
 - 1.3. Job
 - 1.4. Promotional Opportunities
 - 1.5. Supervision
 - 1.6. Co-Workers
 - 1.7. Working Conditions

2. To determine the level of motivations of nurses in terms of the following

2.1. Salary

2.2. Job Security

2.3. Working Conditions

2.4. Responsibility

2.5. Cooperation

2.6. Technical Supervision Qualities

2.7. Interpersonal Relationship Qualities among Colleagues with Supervisor and Subordinates

3. To determine the relationship in job satisfaction and motivation

4. To determine the relationship between job satisfaction and profile of nurses.

4.1. Gender

4.2. Age

4.3. Position Level as Nurse in the UAE

4.4. Income

4.5. Civil Status

4.6. Educational Attainment

4.7. Work location based on State in the UAE

4.8. Years of Service in the UAE

4.9. Family Status in the UAE (i.e., Respondent is living with Family, Husband, Children, Auntie, Uncle or other Relatives in the UAE)

5. To determine the relationship between motivation and profile of nurses.

Significance of the Study

This research is a significant addition to the body of knowledge in nursing studies as it aims to provide scholarly evidence for understanding the correlation between job satisfaction and work motivation, in this case, among Filipino nurses in the United Arab Emirates. The results of this research will provide a clear overview of relevant information and best practices that hospital administrators and policymakers can adapt based on the needs of their organizations.

The study takes on new importance considering the COVID-19 epidemic's unparalleled difficulties for the health industry and its workers all around the globe. In this worldwide crisis, nurses have been putting their skills and strengths up for the fight. The relationship between job satisfaction and motivation is crucial to address among Filipino nurses in the UAE right now. COVID-19 has brought about several challenges for nursing professionals, including heightened job demands, security issues, and emotional weariness—these factors might significantly influence their motivation levels. Understanding these aspects helps provide essential information to create specific measures for hospital leaders and lawmakers during unpredictable situations.

Moreover, this study contributes to knowledge creation by enhancing the strategic human resources strategies in workforce management today. The methodology employed in this research framework offers a valuable foundation for developing a competitive strategic human resources management framework specific to both the nursing and medical industries. This framework, in turn, benefits not only Filipino nurses but also medical leaders and practitioners globally, offering guidance on effective people management strategies. In essence, this study forms part of a broader effort to advance

best practices in nursing and to underscore the significance of job satisfaction and work motivation in creating healthcare organizations that prioritize the welfare and well-being of their staff and patients alike. The result of this pedagogical research is poised to have a lasting impact, benefiting hospitals, their workforces, and nursing scholars across the globe.

Furthermore, this research provides novel ideas that add to the existing conceptual models and techniques for assessing the current strategic human resources practices in the hospital industry as a strategic tool in people management. The scholarly methodology suggested in the study's framework will contribute to the development of a comprehensive strategic human resources management framework in the nursing industry that will benefit Filipino nurses and hospital administrators in general. Overall, this study will certainly become part of a series of studies that will lead to the improvement of nursing work best practices and understanding how job satisfaction and work motivation are significant in providing a holistic organization that cares for its people and patients. The hospitals, their overall workforce, and nursing scholars around the world will greatly and significantly benefit from the outcome of this pedagogical inquiry.

Scope and Limitation

The study focused on the Filipino expatriate nurses residing in the seven states of the United Arab Emirates. The respondents for this pedagogical research study were composed of selected members of the Philippine Nursing Association in the United Arab Emirates. With the selected 117 participants in the country, the study aimed to examine the correlation between job satisfaction and work motivation among Filipino nurses in the

United Arab Emirates, providing information about a very narrow section of the migrant community. This work did not address the entire population of the Filipino nursing community in the United Arab Emirates. Non-Filipino expatriates and nurses from other nations were excluded from this research.

The research was constrained in its ability to evaluate outcomes across diverse populations of migrant nurses and other medical practitioners who were expatriates in the United Arab Emirates, due to the absence of analysis on the various forms of human resource practices and their utilization. This limitation prohibited the researcher from providing confidential information on budgets, organizational processes, and procedures used by various hospitals in human resources and organizational development methodologies, which were considered confidential and for internal use only by the organization. Moreover, the study only conducted an online survey (quantitative) and was limited to Filipino nursing expatriates, excluding other nationalities who were also expatriate nurses working in the United Arab Emirates. Consequently, the study did not offer comparisons that could have revealed vital trends in the use of the best human resources practices in the hospital industry in the United Arab Emirates.

Another limitation of this study was the use of a sample population that did not reflect the overall views of the entire Filipino nursing profession and its total population of expatriates in the United Arab Emirates. The respondents who participated in an online-based survey through Google Forms and its results did not represent the overall population of Filipino expatriates in the UAE. Hence, the study was limited to a restricted number of respondents who provided information to guide the research.

CHAPTER II

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Review of Related Literature

Nurses' work performance can be distinguished in terms of the quality and quantity that they have provided based on the roles and responsibilities assigned to them by their management. In today's challenging times, it is significant for hospitals to ensure that the performance of their services provides plenary and quality results based on customer needs and expectations. In assessing performance in the hospital service industry, the capability of each nursing workforce to perform the tasks assigned to them is the key element to determining performance. Tasks alone cannot be completed without full commitment and the right motivation among teams.

Every country in the world aims for higher standards in well-being and health care, which thus implies ongoing changes and health reforms around the world (Toode, 2015). Declining work performance, nursing errors, and the downgrading of the nursing profession were found to be the main issues affecting nursing workforce productivity (Brüscher et al., 2010; DeLucia et al., 2009; Hassani, 2012). The World Health Organization (WHO) officially announced the ongoing shortage of qualified and skilled nursing professionals in all the regional states of the United Arab Emirates that affects the operational performance expectations and requirements of various hospitals located in its seven states in the country (Bell, 2015; Van Leijen, 2016).

A study in the Northern Emirates shows that 44 percent of the nurses polled were dissatisfied with their jobs, a level of discontent that is alarming experts. Bilal Abbas El Salibi, a senior nursing tutor with the Institute of Nursing in Fujairah, studied job

satisfaction among nurses in six Ministry of Health hospitals in every emirate except Abu Dhabi (Hassani, 2012). Salibi questioned 726 nurses who are respondents from Al Baraha Hospital in Dubai, Khalifa Hospital (Ajman), Al Qassimi Hospital (Sharjah), Saqr Hospital (Ras Al Khaimah), UAQ Hospital (Umm Al Quwain), and Fujairah Hospital (Fujairah) about topics including working hours, benefits, and opportunities for promotion. who presented his findings at the Abu Dhabi Medical Congress and has submitted the study to the American Journal of Nursing, called that level of discontent alarming (Hassani, 2012).

In line with this predicament, the same conditions were being experienced by various medical institutions around the world, which have heavily emphasized the same sentiment (Akinyomi, 2016; Kumar, 2016). Attracting and retaining quality human resource assets in the field of nursing practice is continuously becoming a difficult task among hospital administrators and human resources practitioners in sourcing the talents that they require for their operations (Hughes, 2017). Currently, as preferred by healthcare organizations and hospitals in the UAE, most of the nursing staff are recruited from the Philippines, India, Pakistan, Egypt, and other nearby Arab countries due to a lack of local workforce in the medical industry (Kumar, 2016; Van Leijen, 2016). Others opt to source talents outside the country based on the budget allocated by the hospital management and the competency of the manpower hired from these countries (Bell, 2015). Employees, with their skills, learned procedures, and talents, are considered significant to the success of the organization, whether in the medical industry or other organizations that have a vision and mission to achieve (Meaghan et al., 2002). Hidayat, Agustin, and Ningsih (2017) stressed that length of employment, supervision, rewards,

co-employment relationships, and employment conditions can create low job satisfaction, which in turn can decrease the performance of nurses. The same applies to work motivation, where it can have a positive impact on work outcomes that lead to high work performances among nurses. On the other hand, if performance management and rewards systems fail to meet nurses' expectations, this may lead to a decrease in motivation among the workforce and, moreover, among the nurses in hospitals, which may lead to poor performance at the workplace. (CIPD, 2017; Hidayat, Agustin, & Ningsih, 2017). Avoiding these situations can be prevented by applying strategic human resource best practices through the application of performance management systems, the development of a competency matrix, job design and functions, innovative reward systems, enhancement of the overall organization design, and full management commitment to excellence through transformational leadership practices (Wang, Chontawan, & Nantsupawat, 2012; CIPD, 2017). With these excellent methodologies, this will enable the whole workforce to deliver the best nursing experience to patients, customers, and the hospital that serves them best (Trivellas, 2011; Wang, Chontawan, & Nantsupawat, 2012).

There are various factors determined by scholars that can influence the performance of nurses. This includes work discipline, education levels, work motivation, training, work facilities, years of service, and incentives. Nurses' characteristics are found to have an effect on their performance, which includes age, education, and years of service. In addition, length of employment, supervision, rewards, co-employment relationships, and employment conditions are found to have factors in low job satisfaction that may instigate poor work performance among nurses (Ayalew et. Al. 2019). Work

motivation, on the other hand, was found to have a positive impact on the nurses' performance. There were instances when promotion, cooperation, and increasing income did not match the nurses' expectations. It was found that these phenomena decreased the motivation of nurses, which in turn affected their work performance (Botchway, 2021; Dor, 2022). Prevention of low performance among nurses can be fixed by understanding the cause factors, such as by implementing work discipline, salary-based incentive systems, giving further education, giving supervision, establishing good working relationships, and creating a comfortable and safe work environment (Akinyomi, 2016). These significant factors always create nurses' satisfaction and motivation, which in turn results in high-quality performance and the achievement of their KPIs as an indicator that the best nursing service has been provided to their patients (Dor, 2022).

Understanding Job Satisfaction

Several scholarly and pedagogical studies have addressed the issue of nurses' satisfaction with their work. A careful study of the literature can reveal many interesting factors that contribute to the formation of a sense of satisfaction for nurses (Lin and Jones, 2013). Furthermore, job satisfaction is a key issue for health care professionals around the world (Doef, Mbazzi, and Verhoeven 2012). Investigations reveal first of all that the organizational features of a structure (usually a hospital) can greatly influence job satisfaction for nurses (Botchway, 2021). Such features are personnel shortages, lack of equipment, intention to leave, and others (Liu, Zhang, Ye, et al., 2012). Contemporary management believes that the satisfaction of nurses from their work is the result of rational management and has a strong link with proper leadership and motivation in healthcare organizations (Ivey, 2022) and job engagement (Volpe, 2021).

Various scholars have different views on what the full meaning of job satisfaction is. One of the old descriptions of job satisfaction is described as an “effective orientation on the part of the individuals towards work roles that they are presently occupying” (Vroom, 1964). This phenomenon depicts how the workforce feels about their jobs as influenced by many external factors. Hoppock (1935) also defined job satisfaction as any combination of psychological, physiological, and environmental circumstances that cause a person to truthfully say that he is satisfied with his job. Moreover, there is no universally accepted definition of job satisfaction because it is a complex and multifaceted concept that provides different definitions and perceptions to different individuals (Mullin, 2005). On the other hand, Aziri (2008) says that job satisfaction represents a feeling that appears as a result of the perception that the job enables material and psychological needs. Job satisfaction can be viewed on one side as the person’s state of positive and negative feelings towards his job and, to some extent, the person’s feeling of whether he likes or dislikes his work (Armstrong, 2006). Job satisfaction can be positively met when one’s expectations are matched with the real outcome (Aziri, 2008).

Job satisfaction is indisputably considered one of the major considerations in assessing the efficiency and effectiveness of any business organization (Armstrong, 2006). Organizations nowadays often take into consideration the staff’s personal needs, wants and desires, needs, and expectations, which are seen as some of the most astounding indicators for achieving job satisfaction (George and Jones, 2008). When an employee is satisfied with his job, that will make him happy, and when he is happy, he will likely become a successful employee. Moreover, the essentiality of job satisfaction has been noticed thus far because of the negative consequences brought about by job

dissatisfaction caused by growing cases of absenteeism, non-loyalty, increasing cases of accidents, and others (Armstrong, 2006). According to Spector (1997), there are three vital features of job satisfaction. Firstly, to achieve job satisfaction, organizations must be guided by human values, particularly respect and fair treatment of employees regardless of their positions. By doing this, the evaluation of job satisfaction will serve as a good indicator of employees' effectiveness, which would mean that a high level of job satisfaction will eventually lead to a good emotional and mental state in employees. Secondly, how the employees behave is a result of the level of satisfaction they have attained, which in general affects the business activities and the functioning of the organization. Consequently, it is safe to accept that job satisfaction leads to positive behavior, while job dissatisfaction will result in negative behaviors in employees. Third and last, job satisfaction is one of the determinants of successful organizations.

Ideally, job satisfaction starts with individual employees. When individual employees are satisfied, it follows that they will perform at their best in an individual capacity, which extends to group efforts that lead to organizational performance (Meyer & Peng, 2006). According to McBride (2002), the significance of understanding job satisfaction is likened to the health care industry. It is the principal responsibility of organizations and companies to ascertain whether their workforce is satisfied with their present jobs and find out the causes if these employees are not satisfied.

Determinants of Job Satisfaction in Nursing Profession

Job performance is considered a vital parameter in the nursing profession (Kumar, 2016). It is deemed important to determine the critical role of scholars and professionals in shaping professional performance in both nursing leadership (Lafarney, 2018) and

rational decision-making (Panda and Chowdhury, 2017). Scholars are urged to assess the close relationship between a nurse's job performance and the work schedules, staffing, and epidemiological characteristics of the population they serve (Swedana, 2023). Several scholars have recognized the different factors that influence job satisfaction. This includes, but is not limited to salaries and benefits, organizational climate, autonomy, achievement, recognition, job security, workplace flexibility, degree of professionalism, communication, working conditions, interpersonal relationships, job importance, and others (Ivey, 2022). By understanding job satisfaction as a significant factor in organizational effectiveness, it has been widely known that leadership style also plays a great role in the employee's level of job satisfaction and is also a driver in attaining the organization's goals and objectives, which can be viewed through the proper application of a performance management system (Akinyomi, 2016).

As applied to many studies, pay satisfaction was perceived as the major determinant of job satisfaction (Singh and Loncar, 2010). Moreover, staff are seen to be more expressive when they appreciate non-monetary considerations more. In turn, monetary benefits become a necessity rather than an opportunity. In perspective, personnel are more attracted to satisfying their economic needs. The employers, in response, distribute the majority of the budget on salaries and wages, thereby creating a balance between spending and the return of their investment. This area provides a clear overview as to how job satisfaction has a strong impact on the performance of the whole workforce within and outside of the organization. Job satisfaction affects the overall work performance of the nurses at their workplace, which keeps them engaged in what they do as they see that their management supports their needs and expectations, and in

return, the nursing workforce delivers the required expectations, which can be measured through the key performance indicators (KPIs) given by their employers', particularly those set strategically by their top management at the workplace where they are employed.

Motivation and Job Satisfaction

It was determined that there are wide number of definitions of what motivation is all about particularly underlining either the energetic character of motivation behavior at the starting point of pursuant of goal (content or need theories) or the cognitive character that supports the fundamental decision mechanisms along the course and intensity of motivated behavior or process theories (Swedana, 2023).

Content theories highlights what the human needs and describe motivational factors, identifying behaviors which satisfy the needs. They are characterized by the importance attributed to various needs and to the methods used in their satisfaction. According to these theories, a satisfied employee is a productive employee and a worker who achieves the desired KPI (key performance indicator) and productivity is an indicator that his or her needs are met that results to satisfaction.

Abraham Maslow (1954), indisputably the most prominent author of the needs theory, emphasized his ideas on the assumption of an upward hierarchical need satisfaction. He stressed that the higher-level needs can only be attained after all the preceding needs by an individual are satisfied. Yet, Maslow (1954) acknowledges that exceptions may arise when needs of a superior nature are at stake. This can be met before the proximately preceding level is satisfied. Initially, Maslow's (1954) theory had

seven distinct levels, but after some modifications five categories were formed under the following ascending order: physiological needs which refer to homeostasis maintenance and are indispensable to survival; security needs which include the desire of protecting oneself as well as one's family from danger; social needs which refer to the desire to belong to a group and of being accepted by others; esteem needs which are the individual's desire for distinguishing himself in the group where he participates and more specifically of obtaining prestige and power; self-fulfillment needs which include the desire for psychological growth, continuous improvement of personal capacities and excellence, bestowing a permanent challenge for the individual's life (Rhodes & Collins, 2015).

Besides Maslow (1954), Herzberg et. al (1959) also made a valuable contribution without opposing Maslow's ideas but looking at the satisfaction side of work instead. Steuer (1989) denotes motivation as manifesting the created tension for a need and that satisfaction expresses the feeling of attending to that need. Satisfaction at work is viewed to be a pleasant emotional state resulting from the employees' assessment of their work, which results from the individuals' perspective on the satisfaction of their most important values at the workplace (Locke, 1969). Scholars considered that satisfaction and dissatisfaction at work as the two extremes of the same phenomenon, which is noticeable in studies whose scales measure this construct by using both concepts in opposing extremes in Likert's scales (O'Driscoll & Beehr, 2000). However, other authors, such as Herzberg et. al (1959) with his dual-factor or motivational-hygiene theory, make a distinction between satisfaction and dissatisfaction, considering them as two distinct phenomena.

In addition to these insights, Herzberg et. al (1959) further added that not every need motivates, since some only avoid dissatisfaction. For this author, motivation is divided in two categories: hygiene factors – considered as extrinsic and preventive of dissatisfaction, and are related with the work context in the way a person feels about the company, working conditions, wages, benefits, status and interpersonal relationships; motivational factors – intrinsic factors related to the person's feeling concerning the job position, personal fulfillment, performance acknowledgement and responsibilities associated with the job, which are in themselves gratifying.

Process theories focus on the cognitive processes underlying the conscious mechanisms of decision making. According to these theories, satisfaction is a result of performance and productivity attained, whereas according to need theories, satisfaction allows performance.

Among process theories, the theory of cognitive dissonance (Festinger, 1954) and its derivatives; Equity theory (Adams, 1963) and Expectancy theory (Vroom, 1964), are the ones that stand out.

The Theory of Cognitive Dissonance, formulated by Festinger (1954), comes from the assumption that human beings, by means of an individual process of self-evaluation, form their own self-image and use it as a comparative measure concerning other people or the characteristics that they consider similar to their own. Inconsistencies between an individual's self-evaluation and the exterior results in cognitive dissonance – a mechanism that generates stress. This is the vehicle that drives a person to develop overcoming behaviors and to achieve a state of consonance or psychological balance. The Equity Theory (Adams, 1963) holds that in the workplace, people are constantly comparing their

contributions (performance, responsibilities) and their compensations (wage, acknowledgement) with their work peers. Thus, a perception of equity or inequity emerges. If the worker perceives inequity, either due to insufficient or excessive compensation, he/she tends to behave in a way so as to balance that correlation by increasing or decreasing his/her performance levels in a quest for equity. There are studies which demonstrate increases of performance in workers with excessive compensation (Adams & Rosebaum, 1962) and performance decrease in workers with compensations deficit (Goodman & Friedman, 1969).

Vroom's Expectancy Theory (1964) argues that motivation stems from the individual's estimates about achieving a goal, to which he /she assigns a given value. The effort will depend on the interaction of three cognitive factors: valence (the value which a person attributes to a certain goal or reward), instrumentality (the possibility that performance may be used to achieve a reward) and expectancy (the person's expectation of achieving the goals and the proposed performance). These three factors together determine the motivational level of a person, represented by VIE (Valence x Instrumentality x Expectancy). According to the author, motivation is a multiplied product, which implies that when one of them is zero, the final outcome will also be a void motivation. The motivational process results, therefore, from the interrelationship between the three aforementioned factors. If a person expects to be capable of accomplishing a certain task (Expectancy) and that the accomplishment can lead him/her to reach a fulfilled goal or reward (Instrumentality) to which value is attributed (Valence), it can be stated that the person is properly motivated.

Another important relationship to take into account in work satisfaction is workers' health. Some studies point to a positive association between satisfaction at work and health quality (Henne & Locke, 1985; Peterson & Dunnagan, 1998). This means that work satisfaction is associated with good health quality and dissatisfaction at work is associated with health problems like fatigue, digestive problems, and muscle pains, among others. Henne and Locke (1985) corroborate these results, mentioning that satisfaction is an emotional state and that emotions imply involuntary physical responses where the satisfaction level (emotional state) can act as a stress agent, causing some the abovementioned symptoms.

Nurses' Motivation and Satisfaction

In what concerns nurses' motivation and satisfaction, various scholars highlight the results, which partly confirm Herzberg's predictions (Hughes, 2017). Rewards are an indicator of an increase in behavior repetition. This explains that when an employee is rewarded, his productivity produces better results. On the other hand, punishment does not have a permanent effect and leads to negative attitudes.

As stressed by Minai and Almansour (2013), the staff requires two fundamental requirements in their daily work routines: to be healthy and to have satisfaction at work. Health and satisfaction at work for healthcare practitioners are interrelated with professional status, remuneration, interaction, working conditions, and organizational rule indicators (Steffen, 2008). Remuneration is one of the significant factors that is seen as a strong factor of motivation among nursing professionals today (Ferreira, 2011). Batista, Vieira, Cardoso, and Carvalho (2005) have determined that although remuneration is a motivational factor at work, it is seen as not the main motivator among many of the

workforce in various hospital organizations. There were many factors as motivation indicators, as highlighted by nurses. This includes work stability and commitment to the population. Inquisitively, based on how these scholars' evaluated dissatisfaction, remuneration was indicated as one of the factors of greatest dissatisfaction among nurses' work. Nurses today, based on their current work situations and how they were employed, see their salaries as uncompetitive to other professions. These are measured based on learning the amount of work they were assigned to do, the enormous number of working hours they were asked to attend, and, moreover, the amount of responsibility and complications of handling various tasks that were seen as a heavy burden on nurses' shoulders on a daily basis. Tavares (2010) concluded that, although remuneration is seen as a motivational factor among employees, this statement does not apply to nurses. He highlighted those other motivational factors, which include liking what one does, an acceptable relationship with the multi-professional team, the possibility of professional growth, the hour load, and the working conditions given by the organization. Yet, where remuneration is concerned, Vévoda, Ivanová, Nakládalová, and Marečková (2011) concluded from a study at 122 hospitals in the Czech Republic that nurses considered wages and patient care as the most significant factors at their workplace. Other scholarly and pedagogical studies have attested that various motivational and satisfaction factors in the nursing profession can affect the overall performance of the organization (Armstrong, 2006). Ferreira (1996) published a study conducted at Coimbra Pediatric Hospital with a sample of 109 nurses, showing that the nurses' satisfaction was connected to relationship variables with other hospital professionals and their relationship with patients, while dissatisfaction was linked to remuneration, structural conditions,

incentives, and career development perspectives. Fonseca (1999), who conducted a study with the goal of understanding the degree of professional satisfaction of nurse managers of the northern central area hospitals, concluded that the conditions that most influenced nurses' satisfaction were security, autonomy, and self-fulfillment. Andrade (2001) conducted a study in six hospitals in northern Portugal with a sample of 209 nurses in pediatric services and concluded that the nurses were moderately satisfied overall. He mentioned that older nurses and those with a higher professional category reported the greatest satisfaction. The determinant factors for satisfaction, in decreasing order of importance, were organizational communication, working hours, the physical conditions in the workplace, autonomy, and remuneration. Seixas (2009), in his study with a sample of 42 nurses, concluded that interpersonal relationships are the cause of greatest satisfaction for the nurses. Ferreira (2011), in a study with 388 nurses from primary healthcare in Braga District, concluded that the professionals with the highest satisfaction are those who work in shifts with a fixed-term contract, with management functions, with five years of service or less, and who are 35 years old or younger.

For Staufenbiel, Kroll, & König (2006), an employee's motivation is strongly affected by insecurity at work. However, these studies shared that insecurity could work as a motivation factor if the professional sees these conditions as a challenge. Considered an opportunity, a staff member may fight for the renewal or improvement of his or her employment contract and instill better performance at the workplace. This research emphasized that insecurity has consequences at social and demographic levels for a country since it leads to the postponement of marriage, creating a family, and parenthood. Insecurity can also be responsible for the intent of resignation (Greenhaus

et al., 1997). Uncertainties in career development have been shown to be important factors, not only for the intent to leave but also for decreased motivation, which in turn results in an impact on overall performance in general (Greenhaus et al., 1997).

The head nurse is most responsible for the motivation of a group toward fulfilling the organization's goals (Melo, 2001; Carneiro, 2009). In addition to nurses' motivation and satisfaction, Yaktin (2003) conducted a study of 421 nurses in Lebanon to better understand the relationships between personal characteristics and nurses' satisfaction. The results revealed that personal characteristics have an effect on the way nurses understand work. The nurses with higher educational levels showed greater dissatisfaction with the quality and manner of treatment by supervisors. Nurses who are less than thirty years old and have good professional skills were found to be more dissatisfied with opportunities for professional growth. The research also discloses that if single with married staff is compared, the single staff are found to be most dissatisfied. Al-Enezi (2009) concluded in his study of satisfaction at work among nurses in Kuwait that female nurses were dissatisfied with professional opportunities and intrinsic rewards. Though this is the case, they were satisfied with what concerns acknowledgement, control, and responsibility, although the level of satisfaction was not very high. A lower level of satisfaction was found among the nurses with higher qualification levels. Fontes (2009) finds that nurses with shorter lengths of service, and the youngest in general, are those who present lower levels of satisfaction.

Work motivation and job satisfaction

Peeter's et al. (2014) research highlighted that job satisfaction relates to both performance and absenteeism rates. The phenomenon of absenteeism is a behavior

linked to employee motivation at work. In understanding these types of behaviors, it is deemed significant for staff to determine two decisions regarding their job. One of these is to decide on their view of a desirable workplace that they love to work in. This encourages the workforce to establish a sense of belonging to the organization that they chose to work for. Pedagogical studies established that staff who are satisfied with the company they work for are less likely to commit absences than those that are not satisfied (Peeter et al., 2014). Moreover, dissatisfied employees end up resigning from their jobs, thus increasing the incidence of absenteeism, a condition that causes the company's overhead costs to increase and poor performance. Therefore, job satisfaction positively influenced the company's absenteeism rate. The second important decision to consider is the employees' work performance. According to Meyer & Peng (2006), job performance refers to the output that a person has contributed to the organization concerning his behavior to engage in, and which the organization may perceive as productive or counterproductive.

Good performance can be achieved when the employees meet the expectations of the employer and are attributable to the company's success. Furthermore, every organization is interested in finding out how the workforce performs positively in relation to productivity and, accordingly, how job satisfaction impacts performance. However, it is more interesting to know that there is still an ongoing debate on whether there is a significant relationship between job satisfaction and performance, as it is a very complex phenomenon. Based on this point of view, there can be two points that can be derived and stated in this manner: Satisfaction causes performance; performance causes satisfaction. The first point stressed that there is no direct link between job satisfaction

and performance. This argument further assumes that when employees are satisfied with their jobs, it does not mean that they can perform better than those who are not. In other words, it is not reliable to say that job satisfaction is the main predictor of individual job performance. The second assumption, on the other hand, suggests that performance is the cause of job satisfaction. Research positively relates individual performance and job satisfaction only on the account that, given proper monetary reward mechanisms, this leads to job satisfaction. This further means that proper motivation should be in place to ensure good performance. So, motivation should be given equal importance to job satisfaction and performance.

According to Latham (2012), motivation is "a cognitive resource allocation process in which a person makes choices as to the time and energy that are to be allocated to an array of motives or tasks" or "the process that accounts for an individual's intensity, direction, and persistence of effort toward attaining a goal" (Kirchler, 2002). According to the definition, there are three important points to consider: the arousal, the direction, and the maintenance of certain activities. Arousal is the stimulus that allows activity to occur. Direction is the action needed to decide which goal to pursue, and maintenance encompasses the forces that continue to manifest until the goal is achieved. Motivation can be classified as intrinsic or extrinsic. Extrinsic motivation refers to external rewards given to individuals as a result of the accomplishment of certain goals and can usually be done through monetary considerations such as bonuses, incentives, and promotions. While intrinsic motivation refers to the feeling of getting the job well done, the activity is the motivation itself. It is worth noting that job satisfaction, performance, and motivation can be used interchangeably, but they are separate in context and application as they are

interrelated. It only shows that job satisfaction is not only affected by the performance of individuals but also by motivation. Summing up, job satisfaction and performance are two different but interrelated terms that are also affected by motivation. (Schermerhorn, 2008). To demonstrate the significance of the relationship between these three terms, a model introduced by Schermerhorn (2008), known as the “integrated model of individual motivation to work,” provided the details of the interaction and interdependence of the three variables as indicated hereunder.

Figure 1. An integrated model of individual motivation to work.

An Integrated Model of Individual Motivation to Work

From the diagram, it can be clearly understood that job satisfaction, performance and motivation is a circular process rather than a linear process because of the

interdependence and interaction of the variables. In other words, one variable does not trigger the other variable.

Theoretical Constructs

As this researcher delve in conducting this pedagogical initiative, this research is influenced by Herberg's Two Factor Theory.

Figure 2. The Herberg's Two Factor Theory

The conceptual framework for this study is based on Frederick Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, also known as the Dual-Factor Theory of Motivation. The two-factor theory posits that there are two sets of factors that influence job satisfaction and motivation in the workplace (Shani & Anand Kumar, 2011; Batchelor et al., 2014). These factors are categorized as hygiene factors and motivational factors. The presence of hygiene factors

can prevent job dissatisfaction, while the presence of motivational factors can lead to increased levels of motivation and job satisfaction (Leblanc, 2013; Saber et al., 2021).

Hygiene Factors

1. Salaries: The level of compensation and benefits nurses receive for their work
2. Job Security: The perceived stability and security of nurses' positions within the organization
3. Working Conditions: The physical and environmental aspects of the workplace, including facilities and resources
4. Interpersonal Relationships: The quality of interactions and relationships with colleagues and supervisors
5. Organizational Support: The extent of support provided by the organization to nurses in their roles.

Motivational Factors

1. Recognition: acknowledgement and appreciation of nurses' efforts and contributions.
2. Training and Development Opportunities: Access to ongoing training and opportunities for career advancement.
3. Responsibilities: The level of autonomy and decision-making authority nurses have in their roles
4. Rewards: non-monetary rewards, such as positive feedback and recognition, for excellent performance.
5. Supervision: The quality of leadership and guidance provided by supervisors

Nurses' Work Motivation, Job Satisfaction, and the Two-Factor Theory

The application of the two-factor theory to nurses' motivation and job satisfaction is crucial in understanding the factors that influence their professional experiences (Bahrami et al. 2013). When hygiene factors are adequately addressed, nurses are less likely to experience job dissatisfaction. Adequate salaries, job security, supportive working conditions, positive interpersonal relationships, and organizational support can create a baseline of satisfaction and prevent nurses from becoming dissatisfied with their jobs (Batchelor et al., 2014).

However, for nurses to be highly motivated and experience job satisfaction, the presence of motivational factors is vital. Recognition for their dedication and hard work, opportunities for training and professional development, meaningful responsibilities, positive feedback, and supportive supervision can enhance nurses' motivation and overall job satisfaction (Bauer & Erdogan, 2012).

The interplay between hygiene and motivational factors is essential. While hygiene factors may not directly lead to increased motivation, their absence or inadequacy can result in job dissatisfaction, which can negatively impact nurses' overall job satisfaction and motivation (Saber et al., 2021). On the other hand, the presence of motivational factors can lead to higher levels of job satisfaction and intrinsic motivation, promoting a more committed and engaged nursing workforce (Bahrami et al. 2013).

The Two-Factor Theory provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the factors that influence nurses' motivation and job satisfaction in the workplace. By addressing both hygiene and motivational factors, healthcare organizations can create an environment that fosters job satisfaction, motivation, and employee engagement

among nurses, ultimately leading to improved patient care and organizational outcomes (Shani and Anandkumar, 2011).

To emphasize the knowledge further, the Two-Factor Theory (Saber et al., 2021) allows for a comprehensive understanding of how specific job characteristics and factors influence nurses' motivation and job satisfaction.

Hygiene Factors (Two-Factor Theory)

Adequate salaries, job security, supportive working conditions, positive interpersonal relationships, and organizational support (hygiene factors) prevent job dissatisfaction among nurses. When these factors are met, nurses are less likely to experience dissatisfaction in their work environment.

Motivational Factors (Two-Factor Theory)

High levels of skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, and feedback (core job dimensions) contribute to nurses' experienced meaningfulness of work, sense of responsibility for outcomes, and knowledge of results (critical psychological states). The presence of motivational factors, such as recognition, training opportunities, meaningful responsibilities, rewards, and the nature of work itself, can enhance nurses' motivation and job satisfaction (Bahrami et al. 2013).

The two-factor theory provides a comprehensive conceptual framework for understanding the complex interplay between job characteristics, hygiene factors, and motivational factors and their influence on nurses' motivation and job satisfaction in the workplace. These phenomena create a detailed and all-encompassing framework for

comprehending the intricate relationship between various aspects of a job, such as its characteristics, factors related to the job environment, and factors that influence motivation. (Saber et al., 2021; Shani & Anandkumar, 2011; and Hadi & Adil, 2010).

Conceptual Framework of the Study

Job satisfaction is the main **independent variable**, and the **motivation** of nurses at work is the **dependent variable**. By understanding **Herzberg's Two Factor Theory**, this integrated framework sheds light on how these phenomena collectively explain how job satisfaction correlates with the motivation levels of nurses within their work settings. By combining their understanding of Herzberg's theory, scholars, researchers, and analysts can gain a more thorough understanding of the factors that contribute to nurses' job satisfaction and motivation in their respective professional and organizational roles (Saber et al., 2021).

Referring to the recent studies presented from the review of literature, the importance of understanding motivation and job satisfaction in the context of strategic human resources management has outlined the factors in delivering astounding results by understanding how each variable affects one another, where typically outlining the role of organizational context has a weight in understanding this phenomenon (Bahrami et al., 2013; Saber et al., 2021).

Figure 3 presents the independent and dependent variables of the study. The independent variable is job satisfaction, and the dependent variable is motivation. The result of this scholarly research will provide a better understanding of the relationships between motivation and job satisfaction and the achievement of customers and patients'

needs, which will be an indicator for the organization to further enhance their capabilities in providing the best healthcare within the coverage of their services.

Figure 3. Conceptual Framework of the Study

The terms "job satisfaction" and "motivation" as per the literature have been often used interchangeably in the medical field, and it has been found that there is a significant difference (Hackman and Oldman (1975); Saber et al. (2021); and Dor and Halperin (2022)). Job satisfaction is an individual's emotional response to his or her current job condition, while motivation is the driving force to pursue and satisfy one's needs. Herzberg's theory can be easily applied to the workplace. This conceptual framework was developed based on Igalens & Roussel's (1999) and Saber et al.'s (2021) models of work motivation and job satisfaction following Herzberg's Two Factor Theory.

As highly suggested by this researcher, the outcome of this scholarly initiative will provide a lens for all hospital and nursing administrators on how to gauge their strengths and use them for greater good to further understand how much they need to invest in their human capital strategy and the value of hiring Filipino nursing professionals in the United Arab Emirates.

This researcher used the application of predictive modeling, specifically descriptive correlational analysis, to determine how much the factors of work motivation and job satisfaction affect the performance outcomes of the nurses in the United Arab Emirates.

Following the conceptual framework, this scholarly research explores a set of interrelated hypotheses to understand the intricate dynamics that influence job satisfaction and motivation among nurses. The hypothesis of the study includes the following:

Hypothesis of the Research Study

- i. There is a significant relationship between job satisfaction and motivation of nurses.
- ii. There is a significant relationship between job satisfaction and profile of nurses.
- iii. There is a significant relationship between motivation and profile of nurses.

Definition of Terms - Operational

Causation - also called explanatory research, is the investigation of (research into) cause-and-effect relationships.

DHA (Dubai Health Authority) - the government organization responsible for regulating and overseeing the healthcare sector in the Emirate of Dubai, United Arab Emirates. Established in 2007, the DHA's primary goal is to ensure the availability of high-quality healthcare services to residents and visitors in Dubai.

HAAD (Health Authority Abu Dhabi) - The regulatory body responsible for the healthcare sector in the Emirate of Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates. It played a crucial role in overseeing and regulating healthcare services, facilities, and professionals to ensure the provision of high-quality, safe, and effective medical care to residents and visitors in Abu Dhabi.

Job Satisfaction - is a gauge of nurses' overall contentment with their work, encompassing their affinity for the job itself, as well as specific aspects or facets of their roles, including the nature of their work and the quality of supervision.

Kabayan - is a Filipino term employed to denote a fellow compatriot or countryman.

Motivation - Is the stimulus of work behavior, which channels the nurses' effort to accomplish the organization's goals.

Registered Nurse/s – Nursing practitioners (considered as either a local or expatriate nursing professionals) who are approved to practice their profession by their country's nursing regulatory body.

Performance - is the outcome of the kind of quality and quantity attained by nurses in conducting their work expectations in line with the based on the job roles that they have committed to deliver to their patients, colleagues, and management.

CHAPTER III

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In the past, a research design referred to the overall strategy that was selected to assimilate the different components of a study both coherently and logically, thereby ensuring that the research undertaken adequately addressed the research problem involved (Saunders et al., 2012). Jensen and Laurie (2016) had stressed that a research design was viewed as a roadmap for the research conducted and was meant to ensure the maintenance of a feasible and appropriate path in the scholarly initiative. In order to attain its objectives, the research design in question had been premeditated based on the typical approach required to discover new ideas and discoveries in line with the current phenomena being investigated. As Saunders et al. (2012) had said, research design was a plan, structure, and strategy for investigating the information obtained from the research participants to provide answers to specific research questions, address a research problem, or test a hypothesis.

Referring to this research in the past, this study applied a quantitative approach. Flick (2009) had shared that a researcher might choose one (mono approach); in this case, the researcher had used a quantitative method, which concerned numerical data and statistical analysis, including postal questionnaires and online and structured interviews (Blanche et al., 2010; Dahlberg & McCraig, 2010; Jensen & Laurie, 2016). The research design espoused for the current study had been a quantitative research approach.

In this study, this researcher has adapted Blanche et al.'s (2010) four dimensions of the formation of a research design. This included the purpose of the research; the theoretical paradigm informing the research; the context, or situation, within which the research was carried out; and the research techniques employed to collect and analyze the data. The figure below illustrated the dimensions of decision-making in research.

Figure 4: The dimensions of decision-making in research design

This research was deemed effective and had gained coherence by linking together the four dimensions shown in the figure above. Furthermore, Saunders et al. (2012) has opined that a research design contained specific objectives based on the research objective(s). Punch (2009:), in support of Saunders et al.'s (2012) statement, had suggested that a research design dealt with the following main questions in terms of the conduct of research:

- Which strategy was to be followed during the research?
- In what time frame was the research conducted?
- From where and from whom was the data be collected? and
- How was the data analyzed and interpreted?

The researcher had used a descriptive correlational research design for this thesis, which had been influenced and constructed using the research process as illustrated in Figure 5. A descriptive correlational research design had been utilized in the study to

determine the association between two (2) variables, and it had been used as a basis for predicting future values given the current and present knowledge. This method had allowed researchers to discover how these variables naturally interacted without imposing artificial conditions or interventions. This research design had been ideal for studying complex and multifaceted constructs like job satisfaction and motivation, enabling researchers to gain a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing the phenomena investigated within a diverse group of nurses. In addition, the descriptive correlational research design had supported the examination of longitudinal changes, which had been essential when investigating the impact of long-term events such as the COVID-19 pandemic, patient care load, workplace safety issues, excessively long shifts, poor leadership, workplace relationship dilemmas, etc., on nurses' well-being and job-related factors (Swedana, 2023).

Figure 5. The Quantitative Approach of the Study.

In connection with this study, one of the researcher's objectives was to determine the significant association between job satisfaction and nurses' motivation when working in the United Arab Emirates. Job satisfaction had been the main predictor or independent

variable considered in this study. Job satisfaction was expected to describe the degree of association or behavior with the nurses' motivation as a dependent variable.

The significance of making the right choices had been to achieve coherence throughout the research. The diagram below had provided guidance on the process of how the researcher had collected, analyzed, and interpreted the results. The research had been conducted over three phases, which had been highlighted in the visual representation of the entire process below. The quantitative method had been the straightforward sequence for quantitative research flows: conceptualization, operationalization, and application of the operational definition or measurement to collect the data (Neuman 2007). Quantitative researchers had established numerous ways thoroughly to link abstract ideas to measurement procedures that would produce precise quantitative information about empirical reality. Additionally, quantitative data collection methods had been used for the quantification of relationships between predictors and response variables. To prevent biased results and presentations, the researcher had used a quantitative approach. Descriptive statistics had been used in this research to describe the basic features of the data in this study and provide a summary of the sample (Trochim, 2006). Online surveys through the use of Google Forms had been utilized in gathering data from all the respondents. All participants in the study had been selected randomly from the Philippine Nursing Association in the United Arab Emirates.

Population, Sample Size, and Sampling Technique

The researcher applied the formula below to determine the initial number of samples used in this pedagogical study:

$$n_o \geq \frac{Z_{\frac{\alpha}{2}}^2 p(1-p)}{e^2}$$

where: $Z_{\frac{\alpha}{2}}$ = Z value such that $P(-z < Z < z) = 1 - \alpha$

p = set proportion = 0.50

e = set margin of error=0.05

$$n_o \geq \frac{1.96^2(0.5)(0.5)}{0.05^2}$$

$$n_o \geq 385$$

$$n_o \geq \frac{385}{1 + \frac{(385 - 1)}{150}}$$

$$n_o \geq 108$$

Given the 5% margin of error and 95% confidence level, the corrected computed sample from the population of 150 had been at least 108.

The respondents to this research had consisted of overseas Filipino worker nurses based in the United Arab Emirates. As highlighted above, there had been a minimum of 108 member nurses from the Philippine Nursing Association in the United Arab Emirates who had participated in this study. For this pedagogical inquiry, the probability sampling technique (random sampling) had been selected and used by this researcher. Random sampling had been a commonly used statistical technique in various fields to select a subset of individuals or elements from a larger population for research or analysis. It had been employed in situations where researchers had aimed to draw representative samples that could provide accurate and unbiased insights into the characteristics of the entire population (Saunders et al., 2012). An online survey research strategy had been chosen for this study, which had been deemed appropriate for understanding the views

of the population to comprehend the imperative occurrences of a certain phenomenon associated with this kind of research.

Sampling had been the process of selecting units (e.g., people and organizations) from a population of interest so that, by studying the sample, results could reasonably be generalized back to the population from which they came (Bryman & Bell, 2007). The research objectives set and the questions for this study had determined the nature of the sample required (Saunders et al., 2012). Careful decision-making regarding the sampling size had been conducted before selecting the respondents involved to ensure that the research concerned was neat and of sufficient empirical depth. The selection of the sample size had been based on the guidelines suggested by Saunders et al. (2012).

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria Used in the Study

All Filipino Nurses who participated in the study must have at least minimum of 1 year work experience in the United Arab Emirates. They must a certified member of the Philippine Nursing Association in the United Arab Emirates and officially endorsed by the President of the Association. The participants of the study must have obtained a nursing license both in the Philippines and in the UAE. Age must be 18 years old and above and must be employed in any nursing facility either public or private hospital or medical institutions in any of the seven states of the United Arab Emirates.

Research Setting

The research setting had encompassed the healthcare sector within the different states of the United Arab Emirates (UAE), with a specific focus on Filipino nurses who

were members of the Philippine Nursing Association—UAE Chapter. These nurses had come from both the private and public sectors, working in various healthcare facilities across the country. The United Arab Emirates, known for its diverse population and rapidly expanding healthcare industry, had provided an ideal backdrop for studying the job satisfaction and motivation of nurses from the Philippines. The seven states of the United Arab Emirates had included Abu Dhabi, Dubai, Ajman, Al Ain, Sharjah, Fujairah, and Ras Al Khaimah.

A population had represented the group about which a study had been designed to generate knowledge (Jensen & Laurie, 2016). It had been evident from the above that a population had been a group of elements from which a researcher had selected a sample with regards to which he or she had liked to generalize the findings made (Saunders et al., 2012). Henn et al. (2006) had simply put it as "the entire group that you want to study." A population had represented the entire group of people, and if the group had been small, then it had become possible to study the individual members of the population (Kumar, 2012; Jensen & Laurie, 2016). As highlighted in this part of the study, the participants of this research had included selected respondents from the members of the Philippine Nursing Association in the United Arab Emirates, and there had been a minimum of 108 members using the non-probability sampling method for all selected participants who had joined in this research initiative.

The participation of members of the Philippine Nursing Association—UAE Chapter as the sampling frame had ensured that the study had access to a well-defined and organized group of Filipino nurses working in different healthcare settings across the United Arab Emirates. This approach had enhanced the study's feasibility, allowing for

efficient data collection and a better understanding of the correlation between job satisfaction and work motivation in this specific population.

This pedagogical study had received invaluable support from the Philippine Embassy in Abu Dhabi, under the dynamic leadership of Ambassador Ferdinand Ver and his dedicated team. Their endorsement had underscored the profound significance of this research, which had had the potential to unlock fresh perspectives and opportunities, not only for nurses in the United Arab Emirates but also for Filipino nurses worldwide. Furthermore, the outcomes of this study had served as a valuable resource for nursing scholars and practitioners seeking to understand and appreciate the transformative impact of modern nursing practices.

Data Analysis

This researcher had conducted data analysis to address the research objectives. As highlighted in Table 1, **the first research objective** aimed to determine the level of job satisfaction among nurses. To achieve this, this researcher had measured the variable "job satisfaction," which was of interval level, meaning the data points had equal intervals and meaningful zero values. For statistical treatment, this researcher had employed the mean and standard deviation. This had necessitated collecting data from Filipino nurses using a standardized job satisfaction questionnaire. Once the data had been collected, this researcher had organized the data in a spreadsheet to ensure its accuracy by cleaning up any errors or missing values.

This had been followed by the next step, where the researcher had calculated the mean to establish the central tendency of job satisfaction levels among nurses.

Additionally, this researcher had computed the standard deviation to understand the variability or spread of the job satisfaction scores. This had provided valuable insights into the overall level of job satisfaction among nurses and the degree to which their satisfaction levels had deviated from the mean.

Table 1

Data Analysis Summary

Research Objectives	Variable to be Measured	Level of Measurement	Statistical Treatment
1. To determine the level of job satisfaction of nurses	Job Satisfaction	Interval	Mean/SD
2. To determine the level of motivations of nurses	Motivation	Interval	Mean/SD
3. To determine the significant relationship in job satisfaction and motivation	Job Satisfaction vs Motivation	Interval vs Interval	Pearson r
4. To determine the significant relationship between job satisfaction and profile of nurses	Job Satisfaction vs Profile	Interval vs Nominal/Ordinal	Chi-Square
5. To determine the significant relationship between motivation and profile of nurses	Motivation vs Profile	Interval vs Nominal/Ordinal	Chi-Square

Moving on to **the second research objective**, as the researcher, the next action had been to determine the level of motivation of nurses. To measure the variable "motivation," which was also of interval level, this researcher had utilized the statistical treatment of mean and standard deviation. To accomplish this, this researcher had administered a motivation assessment survey to the nurses and had collected the necessary data. Once the data collection phase had been completed, this researcher had input the data into a spreadsheet or statistical software for organization and analysis. By calculating the mean, this researcher had gained insights into the central tendency of motivation levels among nurses. Additionally, the computation of the standard deviation had provided information about the extent of variation in their motivation scores. Through this analysis, this researcher had been able to understand the overall level of motivation among nurses and the degree of dispersion in their motivation levels.

For the **third research objective**, this researcher had aimed to explore the significant relationship between job satisfaction and motivation. Both "job satisfaction" and "motivation" had been measured as interval-level variables. As the appropriate statistical treatment, the Pearson correlation coefficient (Pearson R) had been used by this researcher. To conduct this analysis, data on job satisfaction and motivation had been collected using suitable survey instruments. After data collection, the researcher had organized it in a spreadsheet and had ensured its accuracy by handling any errors or missing values. By calculating the Pearson correlation coefficient, the researcher had been able to quantify the strength and direction of the linear relationship between job satisfaction and motivation among nurses. A positive correlation coefficient would have indicated a positive relationship, suggesting that higher job satisfaction was associated

with higher motivation, while a negative correlation would have implied an inverse relationship. Through this analysis, the researcher had been able to determine the significance of the relationship and gain a deeper understanding of how job satisfaction and motivation were interrelated among nurses.

In this approach, test abnormalities had been applied first by the researcher before the correlation process. It had been frequently accepted as a good practice for researchers to initially evaluate and manage anomalies in the data before undertaking correlation analysis during their study. For an initial action, recognizing and dealing with anomalies or irregular data points within the dataset had been essential. Data input mistakes, problems with measurements, or uncommon extreme examples might have all contributed to the emergence of these outliers. Researchers had strived to uphold the solidity and dependability of their data by dealing with any anomalies from the beginning. The omission of considering outliers had been vital since it could have distorted data integrity during a correlation analysis, thus possibly causing inaccurate deductions. Furthermore, as this researcher had included this approach in this pedagogical inquiry, systematic identification, and treatment of irregularities in information had offered scientific credibility to investigations by presenting a lucid overview of managing such hitches along with possible impacts on subsequent correlation studies. Eventually, carrying out this process had enriched both dependability and certitude in the research discoveries aimed at in this scholarly work.

Regarding **the fourth research objective**, as presented in Table 1, this researcher had investigated the significant relationship between job satisfaction and the profile of nurses. "Job satisfaction" had been measured as an ordinal level variable, and

the "profile of nurses" had been considered as a nominal or ordinal level variable. To effectively analyze the data, statistical treatment using Chi-Square had been employed by this researcher. To begin, data on job satisfaction and various characteristics of nurses, such as age, years of experience, and education level, which had fallen under the nominal or ordinal level of measurement, had been collected. Once the data collection had been completed, the researcher had input it into a spreadsheet or statistical software for organization and analysis. Correlation analysis had then been conducted, with job satisfaction as the dependent variable and the nurse's profile characteristics as independent variables. Through this analysis, the researcher had determined if there was a significant relationship between job satisfaction and the nurse's profile. The results had provided valuable knowledge into the influence of different profile factors on job satisfaction among nurses and had identified which characteristics were most strongly associated with job satisfaction levels.

Following the summary presented in Table 1, this researcher recorded the overall categorical responses on the job satisfaction and the number of categorical responses on the demographic profiles in order to meet the assumptions of Chi-Square.

Finally, for **the fifth research objective**, this researcher had explored the significant relationship between motivation and the profile of nurses. "Motivation" had been measured as an interval-level variable, and the "profile of nurses" had been considered as a nominal or ordinal level variable. As with the fourth objective, this researcher had employed statistical treatment using Chi-Square. In this approach, the researcher had collected data on motivation levels and various characteristics of nurses and had then input the data into a spreadsheet or statistical software for organization and

analysis. A correlation analysis had been conducted, with motivation as the dependent variable and the nurse's profile characteristics as independent variables. This analysis had helped determine if there was a significant relationship between motivation and the nurse's profile. Through its results, the researcher had gained valuable insights into the factors within the nurse's profile that influenced motivation levels and had understood which characteristics had the strongest association with motivation among nurses.

To explain the methodologies used further, chi-square analysis had been chosen to examine the fourth and fifth objectives as the statistical method of choice for several compelling reasons. First and foremost, both job satisfaction and motivation are often assessed on categorical scales, where nurses' profiles encompassed characteristics such as age, gender, education, or job position. Chi-Square had been particularly well-suited for analyzing categorical data and had effectively handled these types of variables.

Furthermore, Chi-Square had been employed to assess the association or independence between two categorical variables, which had been precisely the objective of this study. By utilizing Chi-Square tests, the researcher could evaluate whether the job satisfaction and motivation of nurses were independent of their profiles. If a statistically significant relationship had been discovered, it had indicated that these variables were not independent, providing valuable insights into how different profile characteristics may have influenced job satisfaction and motivation.

Moreover, Chi-Square tests had been non-parametric, making them robust and applicable even when the assumptions of normality were not met. This had been advantageous in the context of studying job satisfaction and motivation, as these constructs often did not follow a normal distribution. Chi-Square analysis had worked well

with categorical variables, allowing for the examination of whether two variables were related or not and had been strong in the face of non-normal data distributions. All of these characteristics had been important for understanding how job satisfaction, motivation, and the profile characteristics of nurses were related to each other.

In reference to the summary presented in Table 1, the researcher recorded the overall categorical responses on the motivation and the number of categorical responses on the demographic profiles in order to meet the assumptions of Chi-Square.

Overall, the statistical treatments used in these analyses had provided robust and meaningful findings to address the research objectives and had contributed to the existing body of knowledge in the field of nursing and healthcare.

Statistical Treatments

Descriptive statistics were used to describe the basic features of the data in the study. These included the mode, percentage, and mean to interpret the results. Inferential statistics were used to draw conclusions from the sample data. Correlation analysis will be used to determine the significant relationship and the degree of association between job satisfaction and nurses' motivation in the United Arab Emirates as dependent variables.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient

The most common statistical measure of the strength of linear relationships among variables had been the Pearson correlation coefficient, which had been symbolized by the letter r . The value of the correlation coefficient had ranged from $r = -1.00$ to $r = +1.00$.

The direction of the linear relationship had been indicated by the sign of the correlation coefficient. Positive values of r (such as $r = .54$ or $r = .67$) had indicated that the relationship had been positive linear (i.e., the pattern of the dots on the scatter plot had run from the lower left to the upper right), whereas negative values of r (such as $r = -.30$ or $r = -.72$) had indicated negative linear relationships (i.e., the dots had run from the upper left to the lower right). The strength of the linear relationship had been indexed by the distance of the correlation coefficient from zero (its absolute value). For instance, $r = -.54$ had been a stronger relationship than $r = .30$, and $r = .72$ had been a stronger relationship than $r = -.57$. Because the Pearson correlation coefficient had only measured linear relationships, variables that had curvilinear relationships had not been well described by r , and the observed correlation had been close to zero.

$$r = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

Where,

- r = Pearson Coefficient
- n = number of the sample size respondents
- $\sum xy$ = sum of products of the job satisfaction and nurses' motivation
- $\sum x$ = sum of the x scores
- $\sum y$ = sum of the y scores
- $\sum x^2$ = sum of the squared x scores
- $\sum y^2$ = sum of the squared y scores

Chi-Square Test of Independence

AA chi-square (χ^2) statistic had been a test that measured how a model had compared to actual observed data. The data used in calculating a chi-square statistic had been random, raw, mutually exclusive, drawn from independent variables, and drawn

from a large enough sample. For example, the results of tossing a fair coin had met these criteria.

Chi-square tests had often been used in hypothesis testing. The chi-square statistic had compared the size of any discrepancies between the expected results and the actual results, given the size of the sample and the number of variables in the relationship.

For these tests, degrees of freedom had been utilized to determine if a certain null hypothesis could be rejected based on the total number of variables and samples within the experiment. As with any statistic, the larger the sample size, the more reliable the results had been.

$$\chi_c^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

where:

c=Degrees of freedom
 O=Observed value(s)
 E=Expected value(s)

Table 2

Tests of Normality

Variables	Kolmogorov-Smirnov^a		Shapiro-Wilk			
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Motivation	.116	117	.001	.945	117	.000
Job Satisfaction	.098	117	.007	.953	117	.000

As illustrated in the above summary table, the figures displayed the results of two distinct tests of normality. The two tests of normality were the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests. These were conducted on the two variables of the study: job satisfaction and motivation. In these assessments, the researcher employed these

procedures to evaluate whether the data for these variables adhered to a normal distribution.

For motivation (the test of normality):

In reference to the result of the test of normality for motivation, the statistics had acquired a score of 0.116 with 117 degrees of freedom and a p-value (Sig.) of 0.001 for the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. On the other hand, the p-value had been below the usual 0.05 level of significance. Accordingly, the data for motivation had not followed a normal distribution according to the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test.

The p-value (Sig.) for the Shapiro-Wilk test had been 0.000 (rounded to three decimal places), and the statistic had been 0.945 with 117 degrees of freedom. The p-value from the Shapiro-Wilk test had also been less than 0.05, much like the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. The Shapiro-Wilk test had revealed that the motivation data had not conformed to a normal distribution.

For job satisfaction (Test of Normality):

As per the summary table results for job satisfaction as a variable of the study, the statistic acquired a result of 0.098. It also achieved 117 degrees of freedom from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, along with p-value (Sig.) that underscores 0.007. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test signified that the data for job satisfaction similarly deviated from a normal distribution since the p-value is less than 0.05.

For the Shapiro-Wilk test, the p-value (Sig.) acquired is 0.000. Its statistic is 0.953, and the latter attained 117 degrees of freedom. In reference to the Kolmogorov-Smirnov

test, the Shapiro-Wilk test's p-value is less than 0.05, which revealed that the data for job satisfaction might not have followed a normal distribution.

Lastly, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests illustrated that neither motivation nor job satisfaction showed a normal distribution after the tests were conducted by this researcher. The outcome of this analysis postulated that these variables have non-normal distributions. In addition, this information is essential when considering statistical studies and drawing conclusions from these variables' statistical data. If normality is a presumption for a given statistical study, then the researchers and scholars might need to apply non-parametric tests or undertake transformations into consideration.

Data Collection and Storage

The researcher was the sole individual with access to the data that will be collected through the online survey's result. The summary of the results was password-protected on the researcher's computer. All data gathered from the respondents was treated with confidentiality, unless required and requested by law. The researcher made every attempt to secure the data of every Filipino nurse's who participated in the study and secured every information acquired with utmost detail, particularly considering the potential risks associated with the technology in use at that time.

However, it could not be guaranteed that no third parties intercepted data over the Internet. All electronically analyzed and transcribed information was assigned pseudonyms. The signed research respondents' informed consents were stored in a locked filing cabinet at the researchers' condominium in Al Ain, Abu Dhabi, United Arab

Emirates. A data retention policy was implemented by the researcher, and all data would be destroyed after a period of 3 years.

Research Instrument

In this pedagogical initiative, the researcher conducted an online survey using Google Forms. The structured online interview questions were adapted to the participants' communication and learning styles to ensure their comprehension of the questions and statements, allowing them to select their preferred answers. Appendix C outlined the questions directed at members of the Philippine Nursing Association in the United Arab Emirates. Specific inquiries were made of each selected member participant concerning their perceptions related to work motivation and job satisfaction in the workplace. All the research participants were provided with an online survey and interview questions regarding their work experience as OFW nurses in the United Arab Emirates to address all the research questions.

To validate the tool employed in this study, the researcher consulted with experts Dr. Fernando E. Reyes Jr., Dr. Hero Tolosa, and Dr. Liza Gernal of Westford University in the United Arab Emirates, who specialized in research methods in human resource management. The experts recommended the use of quantitative research methodology as the most suitable approach for this study. This approach was chosen to ensure that the desired outcomes, as defined in this study, could be achieved. A Likert scale was used to gauge the job satisfaction of Filipino nurses.

The instruments utilized in this study were based on those applied in the research conducted by Hidayat, Sukadiono, Ratna, and Ningsih (2017) and Anderson, Fontinha,

et al. (2019). As mentioned earlier, job satisfaction served as the independent variable, while work motivation was considered the dependent variable.

The instruments applied in this study included a questionnaire using the Likert scale, featuring indicators for both job satisfaction and work motivation.

First, the instruments employed to measure job satisfaction consisted of 20 satisfaction questionnaires with seven indicators: responsibilities, rewards, job roles, promotional opportunities, supervision, co-workers, and working conditions. These questionnaires encompassed a total of 30 questions, offering five answer choices (1=very dissatisfied, 2=dissatisfied, 3=quite satisfied, 4=satisfied, and 5=very satisfied).

Second, the instrument utilized to assess work motivation was a motivational questionnaire, comprising 35 questions with seven indicators: salary, job security, working conditions, responsibilities, cooperation, technical supervision qualities, and interpersonal relationship quality among colleagues with superiors and subordinates. Similar to the job satisfaction questionnaire, this one also featured five answer choices (1=very dissatisfied, 2=dissatisfied, 3=quite satisfied, 4=satisfied, and 5=very satisfied).

In the final section of this online research survey, demographic data were collected from questionnaires, including data pertaining to nurses' characteristics (length of work, education, nursing position, gender, and experience).

Research Procedure

This research study needed to have an explicit plan in place, which included consideration of the techniques (sampling, data collection, and analysis) to be used in selecting the participants required for the study (Blanche et al., 2010).

The recruitment of research participants was led by this researcher. To ensure that full support was obtained from the target population of the study, this research sought the support and endorsement of the Philippine Ambassador at the Philippine Embassy in Abu Dhabi. This academic initiative was then referred to the President of the Philippine Nursing Association in the UAE, who ensured that all research participants met the requirements of the study.

Figure 6

Data Gathering Procedure

Data Gathering Procedure

This study employed a questionnaire as a technique for sampling, data collection, and analysis. The main research instrument for this study was an online survey, as suggested by Eysenbach and Wyatt (2002). The internet-based survey was conducted through the distribution of self-completed questionnaires to the selected respondents of

the Philippine Nursing Association in the United Arab Emirates. As shown, the researcher and the President of the Philippine Nursing Association, along with their team, collaborated in sending the online survey link to all the target respondents' email and social media accounts. Participants were instructed to answer all multiple-choice questions according to the provided guidelines. The survey could be accessed by clicking the link provided to the study's respondents.

This researcher utilized online-based surveys that incorporated both open and closed-ended questions, aiming to gather insightful responses that would address the main research objectives. Conversely, the open-ended questions allowed respondents the opportunity to provide diverse and more meaningful information (Reyes, 2022). The participants of this study were recruited from the seven states of the United Arab Emirates, all of whom were members of the Philippine Nursing Association UAE. These seven states included Abu Dhabi, Dubai, Sharjah, Umm Al Quwain, Ras Al Khaimah, Ajman, and Fujairah.

The questionnaire was designed to gather significant information on various aspects needed for the study, including the socio-demographic profile of the respondents. This encompassed details such as the respondents' age, gender, civil status, educational attainment, employment status, profession, employment duration, income level, and location. It also included questions related to job satisfaction, the motivations of UAE OFW nurses at work, and the factors influencing their performance at the workplace. Additionally, to reach the desired target participants for the research study, this online survey was uploaded to the internet using Google Forms, and a hyperlink to the questionnaire was sent to the respondents through their Facebook accounts. For those

respondents unable to access the questionnaire through the hyperlink, the researcher provided a hard copy of the questionnaire to be filled out to confirm their participation.

Plan for Data Analysis

The data gathered in this study were analyzed through the application of thematic analysis. Merriam (2009) had described data analysis as a complex method of finding themes and categories within the data that "answered the research question(s)" (2009). Additionally, Riessman (2008) had stressed that "data were interpreted in light of the themes developed by the investigator, the data themselves, political commitments, and other factors." The primary data analysis for this research was accomplished using Google Forms and its data analysis software. The tables, charts, and diagrams provided a detailed overview of the outcomes provided by each participant in the study. To ensure that all information was organized properly, the researcher provided codes for the results per section and highlighted the overall results from the respondents, identifying the interactions based on the results gathered between work motivation and job satisfaction of participants in the study.

Finally, the document content was coded to identify the overall feedback of the audience. In the online questionnaire, the researcher had asked a question to the participants of the study to confirm their full cooperation and affirmation in this study, ensuring the validity of the results, which were unquestionable and valid based on the needs of this research and the questions that needed to be answered during this scholarly initiative.

Data Management

The purpose of the data analysis had been to transform the information (data) in order to provide answers to the research questions (Blanche et al., 2010). For the data, a data entry application had been developed in a Microsoft Excel program, and the relevant data had been entered into it. Google Forms had also provided a similar data management system to ensure that all responses were coded appropriately.

Ethical Considerations

Since this research involved Filipino nursing employees from various institutions in the United Arab Emirates, it was imperative to consider the ethical issues from a broader perspective. These considerations ensured that all aspects of ethical standards were applied in this pedagogical study, guided by Bryman and Bell (2007). This scholarly work was closely associated with integrity, and all disciplines were vigilant to avoid miscalculations and mistakes that might compromise the confidentiality of participants' personal information. Conducted in a foreign land where the majority of "Filipino Nurses" participated, this study took into account the statutory and regulatory requirements of the country, ensuring compliance and non-violation of any interests from the involved parties. Ethics in research encompassed the researcher's behavior in relation to the rights of the participants in the research (Saunders et al., 2012).

Struwig and Stead (2003) and Naanda (2010) emphasized that research ethics provided moral guidelines to researchers on how to conduct research, helping researchers avoid scientific misconduct, such as inventing and distorting results, plagiarism, and publishing other scholars' work without proper attribution. It also entailed

maintaining anonymity and confidentiality for the research participants and reporting results truthfully. Bryman and Bell (2007) underscored that research ethics could not be disregarded, as the integrity of scholarly studies and the broader academic field depended on it.

As highlighted above, a high standard of research ethics had been upheld throughout the current study. Furthermore, plagiarism was strictly avoided (Bryman & Bell, 2007), and measures were taken to protect the privacy of the respondents and avoid deception. In line with the recommendations of Diener and Crandal (1978) and Bryman & Bell (2007), proper consent was obtained from the respondents through a documented form, serving as evidence that all information was willingly provided by the participants and was accurate. Reference was also made to the relevant research principles, aligned with the research subject's purpose and its impact on those affected by it (Jensen and Laurie, 2016).

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.0. Introduction

This chapter presents the data gathering results obtained through a quantitative approach in the study on job satisfaction and motivation among Filipino nurses in the United Arab Emirates (UAE). By employing a quantitative methodology, this research aimed to quantify and measure the levels of job satisfaction and motivation among Filipino nurses working in the UAE healthcare system, as well as identify the significant factors influencing these outcomes.

Understanding the job satisfaction and motivation of Filipino nurses in the United Arab Emirates is of paramount importance due to their significant contribution to the healthcare sector in the country. As a large contingent of the nursing workforce, Filipino nurses play a crucial role in providing quality care and ensuring the smooth functioning of healthcare facilities. Exploring their job satisfaction levels and motivation factors becomes imperative in supporting their professional growth and well-being, as well as optimizing the delivery of healthcare services.

On the sections below, this research has embarked on a pedagogical journey to uncover the overarching results of the study. This expedition will involve a thorough examination of the data, a comprehensive analysis of the findings, and engaging discussions that illuminate the intricate dynamics of job satisfaction and motivation among this indispensable cohort of healthcare professionals. The ensuing sections will meticulously unveil the study's comprehensive outcomes, offering profound insights that not only address the research objectives but also bridge knowledge gaps and contribute

significantly to the understanding of the pivotal role played by job satisfaction and motivation in the healthcare industry.

4.2. Demographics

Table 3 presents data and information on the gender distribution of a group of individuals. Out of the total 117 individuals, 43 identify as male, representing 36.8% of the group, while 74 individuals identify as female, accounting for 63.2% of the group.

Table 3

Distribution of respondents according to demographics

Characteristics	Frequency (N=100)	Percentage
Sex / Gender		
Male	43	36.8
Female	74	63.2
Age Group		
20 to 26 Gen Z	5	4.3
27 to 42 Millennials (Gen Y)	94	80.3
43 to 58 Gen X	13	10.4
59 to 65 Boomers	5	5.0
Job Status of Respondents		
Staff and Rank-in-File	102	87.2
Supervisor / Officer	12	10.3
Manager / Senior	2	1.7
Vice President	12	0.9
Income Distribution		
1,000AED to 3,000AED (Lower Income)	2	1.7
3,001AED to 6,000AED (Middle Income)	34	29.1
6,001AED to 9,000AED (Upper-Middle Income)	38	32.5
9,001AED to 12,000AED (High Income)	40	34.2
12,001AED and Higher (Top Income)	3	2.6

Marital Status		
Single	64	54.7
Married	50	42.7
Divorced	3	2.6
Educational Attainment		
Associate Level	2	1.7
College / University Level	92	78.6
Postgraduate	12	10.3
Master Level	11	9.4
Work Location		
Abu Dhabi	83	70.9
Dubai	19	16.2
Sharjah	4	3.4
Ajman	4	3.4
Ras Al Khaimah	5	4.3
Fujairah	2	1.7
Years of Nursing Employment in the UAE		
<5 Years	22	18.8
5 to 10 Years	18	15.4
16 to 20 Years	5	4.3
25 to 30 Years	1	0.9
Family Status		
Single in the UAE	35	29.9
Boyfriend/Girlfriend/Partner and Companion in the UAE	24	20.5
Only Husband in the UAE	15	12.8
Only Child/Children is in the UAE	17	14.5
Family Members and other Relatives In the UAE (i.e., Fathers, Sister, Brother Aunt, Uncle, Niece, Nephew etc.)	21	17.9
Residency Periods (in Years)		
1	83	70.9
2	19	16.2
3	4	3.4
4	2	1.7
5	5	4.3
6	2	1.7
7	2	1.7

Sex and Gender of Research Participants

In terms of gender, Table 3 raises several important points and warrants further analysis. The unequal distribution between male and female individuals indicates a gender disparity within the group. With females comprising the majority at 63.2%, it suggests a potential gender imbalance or a larger representation of women in the sample.

Understanding gender distribution is crucial for various reasons, including social, economic, and political implications. Gender equality and representation have been important topics of discussion and activism in many societies. Analyzing such data helps shed light on existing disparities and informs efforts to address gender-based inequalities.

To gain a comprehensive understanding, it is essential to consider the context and potential factors contributing to this gender distribution. Several factors could influence these numbers, such as the nature of the group being studied, cultural or societal norms, recruitment methods, or even self-identification biases. These factors should be explored further to better interpret the significance of the data.

Furthermore, it is important to note that gender is a spectrum, and the binary categorization used in this data may not fully capture the diversity of gender identities present within the group. Including additional categories or allowing individuals to self-identify their gender could provide a more comprehensive representation of the group.

To address gender disparities, it is crucial to promote inclusivity and equal opportunities for all genders. This can be achieved through policies and initiatives aimed at combating discrimination, promoting gender diversity, and fostering an environment where individuals of all genders can thrive.

In conclusion, the data provided indicates a gender distribution where females make up the majority, accounting for 63.2% of the group, while males represent 36.8%. The prevalence of young female Filipino nurses in the UAE can be attributed to a combination of historical, social, and economic factors. Nursing has traditionally been perceived as a female-dominated profession in the Philippines. Social norms and cultural expectations have historically encouraged young Filipino women to pursue careers in nursing due to its compassionate and caring nature. The Philippines has a surplus of nursing graduates, and there is significant competition for limited job opportunities in the local healthcare system. As a result, many young female nurses seek employment opportunities abroad, including in countries like the UAE, where there is a demand for healthcare workers. Young Filipino women often have strong support from their families to pursue careers abroad to contribute to their families' financial well-being or for personal growth and experience (Filipino Times, 2018). In addition, young Filipina nurses are often seen as more adaptable and eager to learn, which can be advantageous for employers seeking nurses who can quickly acclimate to the healthcare system in the UAE.

Age of Research Participants

The dataset provides information regarding the age distribution of a sample of 117 research participants. The age distribution can be classified into five distinct categories: individuals aged 20 to 26 are referred to as Generation Z; those aged 27 to 42 are known as Millennials (sometimes referred to as Generation Y); individuals aged 43 to 58 fall into the category of Generation X; and those aged 59 to 65 are commonly referred to as Baby

Boomers. The frequencies and percentages linked to each age group were analyzed using the American Generation Timeline (Koltai, 2020).

Within the cohort, a subset of five individuals can be identified who belong to the age range of 20 to 26 years. This particular subset constitutes 4.3% of the overall population. The age group ranging from 27 to 42 years old is the largest, consisting of 94 people, accounting for 80.3% of the total population. The age cohort ranging from 43 to 58 encompasses a total of 11 people, comprising approximately 10.4% of the overall population. In a similar vein, the age group ranging from 59 to 65 exhibits a total of 5 individuals, constituting 5% of the overall participant pool.

The analysis of age group distribution offers useful information about the demographic composition of the specific group being examined. The prevalence of individuals aged 27 to 42, comprising more than 80% of the total, suggests that a significant proportion of the group's population falls within this age bracket. The aforementioned data indicates that the study comprises a cohort of youthful volunteers who exhibit traits such as productivity, ambition, proficiency in technology, and a strong orientation towards achieving goals. According to Ayalew et al. (2019), there is a prevalent inclination among millennial nurses to exhibit a pronounced ambition and a profound aspiration to effectuate a constructive influence on their professional trajectories. Millennials have been raised in an era characterized by the widespread adoption of digital technologies, which has resulted in their exceptional proficiency in utilizing technology for diverse objectives. The aforementioned proficiency is applicable to both professional and academic endeavors, as individuals are inclined to utilize digital tools and online resources for the purpose of fulfilling their work responsibilities, engaging

in collaborative efforts with colleagues, and delivering their work in an efficient manner. These competencies are regarded as essential requirements by hospitals in the United Arab Emirates.

Nevertheless, it is crucial to acknowledge that the exclusion of persons belonging to specific age cohorts, such as the 59 to 65 age range, could potentially indicate constraints or predispositions within the sampling or recruitment methodology. Furthermore, it has been observed that Filipino nurses in the present day are increasingly inclined towards retirement and are considering repatriation to the Philippines. As nurses approach their late 50s and early 60s, they may encounter a decrease in employment prospects, particularly when considering a foreign nation such as the United Arab Emirates. Employers may exhibit a preference for the recruitment of younger nurses due to their potential for extended tenure within the organization. Alternatively, employers may implement age-related employment policies that impose limitations on the hiring of individuals falling within a specified age bracket. The nursing job necessitates a high level of physical endurance and cognitive flexibility. As nurses progress in age, a subset of individuals may opt to withdraw from active nursing positions as a result of health-related issues or the difficulties associated with meeting the physical requirements of the profession. Finally, the culture of the Philippines places a significant focus on the importance of family and the establishment of support networks. Elderly nurses may exhibit a preference for allocating their post-career period towards familial companionship and involvement in social and communal endeavors within the Philippines.

The analysis of age distribution holds significant importance for a multitude of reasons. The demographic variable of age holds significant importance since it has the

potential to have an effect on individuals' perceptions, behaviors, and experiences. This study offers valuable perspectives on the dynamics between different generations, prevailing cultural patterns, and the issues and requirements associated with various age groups. Comprehending the age distribution within a certain group provides valuable insights for decision-making, policy formulation, and the implementation of focused interventions that are specifically designed for distinct age groups.

In general, the data presented illustrates an age distribution in which the 27–42 age cohort represents the majority, comprising 80.3% of the entire population. The presented data underscores the significance of taking age demographics into account across several domains, including social planning, policy development, and targeted interventions. These individuals possess specific attributes that render them highly sought-after by healthcare institutions in the United Arab Emirates. The aforementioned attributes are influenced by the experiences and ideals specific to the millennial cohort, hence enhancing their efficacy within the healthcare sector (Dor, 2022). Hospital employers choose individuals based on their technology proficiency, dedication to continuous learning, ability to adapt, patient-centered care approach, and collaborative mindset. According to Minai (2013), there is a common perception that younger nurses possess a greater level of adaptability when it comes to adjusting to new situations and coping with changes within the workplace. Individuals may have a greater propensity to adopt novel technologies and healthcare methodologies, thereby conferring benefits within a rapidly expanding healthcare milieu. According to Aben (2023), these attributes render individuals highly valuable assets inside healthcare organizations, enhancing patient care and yielding improved outcomes.

Job Status

The data acquired from in this study, as presented in Table 3, pertains to the occupational status of the participants, specifically focusing on the various positions held by a cohort of 117 persons. The classification comprises four distinct position categories: Staff and Rank-in-File, Supervisor/Officer, Manager/Senior, and Vice President. The purpose of this analysis is to investigate the frequencies and percentages pertaining to each position.

Within the collective, a majority of 102 individuals, constituting 87.2% of the total, occupy the role of Staff and Rank-in-File. The post of Supervisor/Officer is occupied by a total of twelve individuals, constituting approximately 10.3% of the overall group. The Manager/Senior post is currently held by two individuals, constituting a proportion of 1.7% out of the total. Ultimately, a solitary individual currently occupies the esteemed role of Vice President, signifying a mere 0.9% representation within the collective.

The evaluation of position distribution offers significant insights into the hierarchical organization and occupational makeup of the group. The prevalence of the Staff and Rank-in-File position, which is held by 87.2% of employees, indicates a higher proportion of entry-level or operational staff members within the group. The provided information possesses potential utility in comprehending the composition of the workforce and potentially discerning prospects for career progression and development within the firm.

Contrarywise, the inclusion of persons occupying supervisory, management, and executive roles, such as Supervisor/Officer, Manager/Senior, and Vice President, serves to underscore the hierarchical structure present within the firm. Although these positions

may constitute a lesser percentage within the organization, they fulfill crucial functions in terms of decision-making, leadership, and the supervision of operations.

It is highly imperative to acknowledge that the classification of positions employed in the data may not comprehensively encompass the complete spectrum of functions and duties within the collective. Organizations frequently exhibit intricate hierarchical arrangements and a wide array of job designations, which may not always correspond precisely with the predefined categorizations. A more comprehensive understanding of the organization's personnel could be achieved by a thorough examination of the distinct functions and job descriptions associated with each position type.

The examination of position distribution plays a crucial role in the assessment of workforce dynamics, the identification of career progression prospects, and the evaluation of organizational structure. The analysis of talent data can provide valuable insights for the development of talent management strategies, succession planning, and initiatives aimed at fostering diversity and inclusion in the workplace. The identification and resolution of potential disparities or obstacles to career progression can significantly contribute to the establishment of a work environment that is characterized by fairness and personal satisfaction.

In conclusion, the data presented demonstrates a distribution of occupations wherein the majority of individuals (87.2%) occupy Staff and Rank-in-File roles. This suggests a higher proportion of employees in the group who are at the entry-level or operational level. The individuals referred to as "kabayans" typically consist of personnel who are in the early stages of their professional development, seeking to build their careers and gain valuable experiences. Filipino nurses are widely recognized for their

notable work ethic, unwavering commitment to patient care, and optimistic demeanor (Filipino Times, 2018). The aforementioned attributes are held in high regard by healthcare institutions in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) and play a significant role in establishing the reputation of Filipino nurses as dependable and proficient healthcare practitioners. According to Minai and Almansour (2013), nurses at lower positions within the organizational hierarchy frequently exhibit the essential abilities, characteristics, and competences needed for providing fundamental nursing care. Additionally, employing rank-in-file nurses may prove to be a more economically viable option for healthcare facilities when compared to the recruitment of highly experienced or specialized nursing professionals.

Nevertheless, it is worth noting that the organizational structure also encompasses personnel occupying supervisory, management, and executive roles, hence emphasizing the existence of hierarchical levels inside the organization. In order to have a comprehensive comprehension of the composition of an organization's personnel, it is imperative to conduct a thorough examination and contemplation of job titles, duties, and career advancement prospects (Hughes, 2017). It is imperative to acknowledge that although there may exist a predilection for younger Filipino nurses in lower-level jobs, the healthcare industry in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) depends on nurses of different age groups and levels of expertise to cater to the multifaceted requirements of patients and healthcare establishments. The specialized skill sets, extensive expertise, and unwavering commitment of each nurse collectively enhance the standard of healthcare provisions inside the United Arab Emirates (Dass, 2020).

Income Distribution of Filipino Nurse Research Participants

In terms of the income distribution of research participants, the data presents information on the income distribution of a group of 117 individuals, categorized into five income ranges: (AED1,000-AED3,000), (AED3,001-AED6,000), (AED6,001-AED9,000), and (9,001AED). Below are the number of instances associated with each income group.

Within the group, only two individuals have an income between 1,000 AED and 3,000 AED, which represents 1.7% of the whole. The top income group earns between \$6,000 and \$9,000 per month; there are 38 individuals in this group, with 39 representing 32 1/3 percent of the total. The 3,001 to 6,000 dirhams income bracket represents 34 individuals, or roughly 29.1 percent of all individuals. Besides, 40 citizens' annual salary is between 9,001 AED and 12,000 AED, comprising 34.2% of the whole group. Finally, 3 people have more than 12,001 AED in earnings, which amounts to a mere 2.6 percent of the entire population.

The income statistics tell us how far individuals can go when they are part of the group and how wealthy or financially stable, they are. The most populous categories are middle income: 6,001 AED to 9,000 AED and 9,001 AED to 12,000 AED—these two segments combined form a whopping 66. This indicates a somewhat equal income dispersion within the sample.

The consideration of contextual elements that may exert an influence on income distribution is of paramount importance. These considerations encompass the characteristics of the specific group under investigation, the prevailing economic conditions within the region, as well as potential differences in income across various industries or sectors. Furthermore, it is important to acknowledge that the income ranges

presented are general classifications, and obtaining more specific data would yield a more comprehensive comprehension of the distribution of income.

The examination of income distribution holds significant importance in the evaluation of socioeconomic inequalities, the assessment of living standards, and the identification of potential avenues for enhancement. The availability of education, healthcare, housing, and other critical resources is influenced by individuals' income levels. An in-depth comprehension of income distribution can provide valuable insights for the development of policies and programs that seek to alleviate poverty, foster economic mobility, and establish a just and equitable environment that offers equal opportunity to all individuals.

In summary, the data presented demonstrates a distribution of income wherein a significant proportion of individuals are situated within the middle-income brackets, namely the ranges of 6,001 AED to 9,000 AED and 9,001 AED to 12,000 AED. The findings indicate that a significant proportion of the participants are employees in lower hierarchical positions and belong to the millennial generation or younger age groups. This observation provides insight into the rationale for their pay being situated within the intermediate range, which aligns with the typical monthly remuneration received by Filipino millennial nurses employed in the United Arab Emirates (UAE). The findings of this study hold considerable importance for the researcher since they establish that the salary provided to Filipino nurses in the United Arab Emirates aligns with the regulations set forth by the government. The United Arab Emirates (UAE) government has established a comprehensive framework of regulations pertaining to minimum salaries and labor laws, with the primary objective of safeguarding the rights and well-being of

workers, including those in the nursing profession. The compensation structure across various businesses, including healthcare, is influenced by these restrictions. The findings of this study are consistent with the research conducted on employment contracts and benefits for Filipino nurses as reported in the Filipino Times in 2018. The salary packages offered to Filipino nurses in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) often encompass additional advantages, such as provisions for accommodation, transportation, health insurance, and yearly leave. The inclusion of these perks contributes substantial value to the whole compensation package, notwithstanding the base salary's position inside the middle-income bracket.

Lastly, the findings of this study provide evidence of the nursing qualifications and experience had by Filipino nurses, who predominantly belong to the millennial generation. Salaries in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) are frequently influenced by factors such as educational attainment, professional background, and specific proficiencies possessed by individuals. Nurses possessing advanced qualifications, extensive experience, and supplementary certificates have the potential to command compensation at the upper echelon of the aforementioned salary spectrum. In order to establish a correlation, the cost of living in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) was employed as a determinant for the income range of Filipino nurses working in the aforementioned nation. The United Arab Emirates (UAE) presents a range of advantages and prospects, yet it is also recognized for its comparatively elevated cost of living, particularly in prominent urban centers such as Dubai and Abu Dhabi. The United Arab Emirates (UAE) has been undergoing a notable period of accelerated economic expansion and progress, resulting in a heightened need for healthcare services. The increasing demand for proficient healthcare practitioners,

particularly Filipino nurses, has been propelled. According to Aben (2023), the compensation range, as determined by the majority of research participants, suggests that Filipino millennial nurses receive a remuneration that is competitive in nature. This income is deemed sufficient to sustain a fair standard of living and also provides adequate support for their families residing in their home country.

Marital Status of Participants

Referring to Table 3, the data highlighted the results acquired on the marital status of a group of 117 individuals who participated in this pedagogical study. This was categorized into three categorical types: Single, Married, and Divorced. Based on the outcome of the study, below are the frequencies and percentages associated with each civil status.

Among the individual in the group, there are 64 individuals are classified as Single, representing 54.7% of the total. The Married category consists of 50 individuals, accounting for 42.7% of the group. Finally, 3 individuals are categorized as Divorced, making up 2.6% of the total.

The analysis of civil status distribution yielded valuable insights into the composition of marital status within the group. Over half of the entire people in the group was categorized as Single. This observation implies that a considerable proportion of the cohort is presently unmarried or not engaged in a formally acknowledged union.

On the other hand, the Married category represents a substantial portion of the group, with 42.7% of individuals falling into this civil status. This indicates that a significant proportion of the group has entered into a formal marital relationship.

For the group of individuals in the Divorced category, though this are relatively small in number, highlights the existence of individuals who have undergone the legal process of divorce within the group.

It is vital to recognize that civil status can be influenced by various factors, including cultural norms, legal frameworks, and personal choices. Additionally, civil status is not necessarily an indication of relationship status or personal well-being, as it does not account for factors such as separation or widowed individuals.

The comprehension of the distribution of marital status inside a collective might yield significant ramifications for multiple facets of existence, encompassing social interactions, familial arrangements, and legal repercussions. The consideration of the diversity of civil status and the unique circumstances of persons within each respective group is of utmost importance.

In summary, the data presented demonstrates a range of civil statuses, with Single individuals comprising the largest proportion at 54.7%, followed by Married individuals at 42.7%, and Divorced individuals at 2.6%. The provided information offers valuable insights on the composition of marital statuses within the group.

The substantial number of individual Filipino nurses employed in the United Arab Emirates (Filipino Times, 2018) can be ascribed to a multitude of factors:

1. **Career Priorities:** Many Filipino nurses choose to work abroad to advance their careers and gain international experience. Pursuing a career opportunity in a foreign country may be a priority for them at that stage of their lives, which could lead them to be single while working in the UAE.

2. **Age and Life Stage:** Younger nurses who are in the early stages of their careers may be more inclined to work abroad and explore opportunities before settling down and starting a family. As they focus on their professional growth, they might delay marriage and family plans.
3. **Cultural and Family Expectations:** In Filipino culture, there can be societal and familial pressures to focus on one's career and personal development before settling down and starting a family. This can influence some Filipino nurses to prioritize their careers while working in the UAE.
4. **Work Commitments:** Nursing can be a demanding profession that requires long working hours and a focus on patient care. Some nurses may choose to be single to devote more time and energy to their career without additional family responsibilities.
5. **Transitory Nature of Work:** Some Filipino nurses may view their employment in the UAE as a temporary arrangement, and they may not see it as conducive to starting or maintaining a family during this period.
6. **Personal Preferences:** Ultimately, the decision to remain single while working in the UAE can be a matter of personal preference. Some nurses may prioritize their independence and career aspirations at this point in their lives.

However, it is important to recognize the complexities and individual circumstances that influence civil status and to avoid making assumptions about individuals' relationships or personal well-being based solely on their civil status.

Educational Attainment of Filipino Nurses in this Research

In terms of the educational attainment of a group of 117 individuals, Table 3 highlights and categorizes the data into four educational levels: associate, bachelor's, graduate, and master's degree. Now that the data has been prepared for further analysis, let us proceed to analyze the distribution of frequencies and percentages according to each level of education.

In this group, two people are at the associate level, which is equivalent to approximately 1.7% of the total. The highest educational attainment for the group is at the college or university level (92), accounting for almost 78.6%. Postgraduate Level: 12 (10.3%). Finally, 11 people have a Masters-level education (9.4%). The distribution of educational attainment provides insights into the academic qualifications and skills of the individuals within the group. The majority of individuals have completed college or university-level education, indicating a significant emphasis on higher education among the group. This suggests a relatively well-educated sample, with a high percentage of individuals having pursued undergraduate studies.

Individuals in the Postgraduate and Master Level categories reflect the attainment of advanced degrees beyond the undergraduate level. These individuals have likely pursued specialized studies and have acquired higher levels of expertise and knowledge in their respective fields.

It is crucial to acknowledge that a variety of factors, such as access to educational opportunities, individual preferences, and socioeconomic circumstances, affect educational attainment. Moreover, the categorization of educational levels provided might

not capture the full range of educational qualifications and certifications that individuals in the group may possess.

Understanding the distribution of educational attainment is valuable for assessing the skill level and qualifications within the group. Education plays a vital role in personal and professional development, and it can impact employment opportunities, career advancement, and societal contributions.

In conclusion, following Erik Erikson's Theory (Herbert, 2021), the data provided illustrates an educational attainment distribution where the majority of individuals (78.6%) have attained a college- or university-level education. Additionally, there are individuals who have achieved higher levels of education, including postgraduate and master-level qualifications. This suggests a well-educated sample, highlighting the importance of higher education within the group.

Work Location in the UAE

Table 3 illustrates the workplace of each of the 117 participants in the research study. It includes six different locations: Abu Dhabi, Dubai, Sharjah, Ajman, Ras Al-Khaimah, and Fujairah. As a result, below are the frequencies and percentages for the different locations where Filipino nurses in the UAE are employed.

Of the group, the majority (83 out of 113) work in Abu Dhabi, comprising a 73% majority share. It's not surprising, then, that the second most popular job destination is Dubai, where 19 respondents (16.2%) currently live and work. Sharjah and Ajman have similar population counts: 4 people in each location, representing a share of about 3.4%

in each. Ras Al Khaimah, represented by the five men in the group, accounts for just 4.3%. Finally, Fujairah has two people contributing only 1.7 percent.

Work locations provide an insight into the geographical dispersion of employment in the group. Indeed, the data suggests that Abu Dhabi will be the top work destination, which would mean an abundance of job opportunities are located here. The city is the second-most popular job market, implying significant opportunity as well.

With representation from people in Sharjah, Ajman, Ras Al Khaimah, and Fujairah, we see a greater distribution of workplaces but a lesser proportion of population. This indicates job prospects here too (though less than in Abu Dhabi and Dubai). Understanding the distribution of work locations is essential for assessing regional employment patterns, commuting patterns, and economic development within different areas. It can inform policymakers, urban planners, and employers in making decisions regarding infrastructure, transportation, and job creation strategies.

It is worth noting that the data provided captures the work locations of a specific group and may not represent the overall employment landscape of the region. Further analysis and comparison with broader data would provide a more comprehensive understanding of work location trends and patterns.

To summarize, the data provided illustrates a work location distribution where the majority of individuals (70.9%) work in Abu Dhabi, followed by Dubai (16.2%). Sharjah, Ajman, Ras Al Khaimah, and Fujairah have smaller but still notable representations. This information provides insights into the geographic distribution of employment opportunities within the group. Aben (2023) from the Arab News highlighted in his online news column that the UAE is the 2nd largest employer of Philippine expats after Saudi Arabia, and the

result of the study supports demographics that explain why there are more Filipino nurses employed, mostly in the states of Dubai and Abu Dhabi. Both states have experienced rapid economic growth and development in recent years, leading to an increased demand for healthcare services in Dubai and Abu Dhabi. This growing healthcare industry requires a larger workforce, making Filipino nurses an appealing option due to their availability and skillset. In addition, about 10 percent of Filipino workers in the Gulf state are employed in the health sector, according to a 2019 study by EON, a Philippine public relations company in Dubai. As this study is highly supported by the Philippine Embassy in the United Arab Emirates, Ambassador Alfonso Ferdinand A. Ver said, “The Filipinos in the UAE are significant not only in number... they are known for their professionalism, talent, and skill, combined with innate friendliness, which is why they are respected and embraced by the UAE.” This is one of the main reasons that Filipino nurses are the most preferred medical professionals in the UAE (Filipino Times, 2018; Aben, 2023).

Family Status of Research Participants

For the family status of each participant of this research, Table 3 presents information on the number of years individuals in a group of 117 have spent in the UAE. It is categorized into five groups: <5 years, 5 to 10 years, 11 to 15 years, 16 to 20 years, and 25 to 30 years. As illustrated, below are the results on frequencies and percentages associated with each category.

Among those sampled, just twenty-two members, or 18.8 percent of the whole, had spent less than five years in the UAE. With almost two thirds (60.7%) of the remaining 56 members belonging to this group, having resided in the UAE for between five to ten

years. This segment comprises 18 people, equal 13.88%. Furthermore, there are five who have lived in the United Arab Emirates for between 16 and 20 years, making up 4.3% of the cohort. Finally, one person has spent 25-30 years in the United Arab Emirates, making up just 0.9 per cent of the total.

The length of stay information can provide insight into the length of residence or work experience people have in the UAE. Most people have been here for 5-10 years which means the number of people that have achieved some form of stability, are quite a few. This group comprises Filipino Nursing Kabayans who might be settled expats living in the country or people who have been working in this region for a good amount of time. It is worth mentioning that the number people who belong to the 5 or less indicates part of this population is newly arrived individuals. This cohort can consist of new entrants exploring opportunities in the region or people who have just relocated due to work or other reasons.

The data showed lower percentage of people who are long-time residents of the UAE including 11-15 years (12%), 16-20 years (4%) and 25-30 years (1%). These group are also seen to know more about the culture, society, and business practices in the UAE.

Knowing the weighted average years of experience in the country helps to quantify the nature of the group based on the newcomers, permanent inhabitants, and long-term expats. It can provide insights into the demographics of the expat population in country.

Summing up, as presented in the data that there is a distribution of years in the UAE where most people (60.7%) have stayed for the range of 5-10 years. The group includes people with different levels of time served — some for less than five years, others between 25-30 years. This means that this information highlighted about Filipino Nurses'

residency periods in the UAE. But this should be tempered by thinking about why certain people are in the UAE, and what kind of range there actually exists within this category in terms of the variety of their backgrounds and experiences.

In terms of the family status of participants, the data presents information on the family statuses of a group of 117 individuals in the UAE. It is categorized into six groups: Single in the UAE, Boyfriend/Girlfriend/Partner and Companion is in the UAE, Only Husband is in the UAE, Only Child/Children is in the UAE, Husband and Child/Children is in the UAE, and Family Members and other Relatives in the UAE. Let's examine the frequencies and percentages associated with each category.

Among the individuals in the group, 35 individuals are found to be categorized as Single and Employed as Nurse in the UAE, representing 29.9% of the total participants. The Boyfriend/Girlfriend/Partner and Companion has 24 respondents, accounting for 20.5% of study participants. Only Husband is in the UAE is the status for 15 individuals, making up 12.8% of the total respondents. In addition, 5 individuals are found to be in the section of Only Child/Children in the UAE, representing 4.3%. The Husband and Child/Children is in the UAE were 17 individuals in total, making up 14.5% of the total. Lastly, 21 individuals have Family Members and other Relatives in the UAE, accounting for 17.9% of the group.

The distribution provides understandings into the living arrangements and relationships of individuals in this part of the study. The presence of Single participants category suggests a significant portion of the respondents that comprises individuals who are living independently in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) without immediate family members, relatives, or mutual partners in the country.

The Boyfriend/Girlfriend/Partner and Companion is in the UAE category specifies respondents who have a romantic partner or companion who is currently based in the UAE but may not be married or have children.

The diverse classifications relating to the presence of their spouses, offspring, and other kins in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) underscore the manifold familial arrangements within this population. The data indicates that certain individuals in the country has experienced physical separation from their direct family members from the Philippines, whereas others reside with their spouses, children, or extended relatives.

The comprehension of the distribution of family statuses postulated significance in understanding the group's composition in relation to their family dynamics, support networks, and social affiliations. This pedagogical exploration aims to offer valuable insights into the exceptional experiences and difficulties confronted by individuals who resides in the United Arab Emirates. These are individuals who are living in isolation, separated from their families, or have family members present in the country.

The recognition of family status is contingent upon a multitude of elements, encompassing individual decision-making, societal conventions, and legal obligations. Figure 2 offers a limited representation of the family statuses within the group and may not encompass the entirety of family situations and scenarios they are facing today.

In summary, the data presented demonstrates the distribution of family statuses within the surveyed group of respondents, wherein Single in the UAE (29.9%) and Boyfriend/Girlfriend/Partner and Companion in the UAE (20.5%) appeared as the prevailing categories. The inclusion of individuals in categories based on the presence or absence of spouses, offspring, and other relatives demonstrated the existence of varied

familial arrangements within the group. Nonetheless, it is vital to take into consideration the unique circumstances, cultural backgrounds, and individual decisions that portrayed a role in shaping the diverse family statuses observed within the given population.

Residency Periods

Figure 3 provided data and significant insights regarding the duration of residency periods, measured in years, for a sample of 117 individuals residing in the United Arab Emirates. The classification consists of seven distinct groupings, namely 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7. These categories denote the duration of individuals' residency in the United Arab Emirates. In accordance with this, presented below are the frequencies and corresponding percentages pertaining to each primary participant group involved in the study.

The study revealed that a significant proportion of the group's participants, specifically 70.9%, or the majority of the 83 people, had a residency time of one year. The residency time of 2 years emerged as the second most common duration in this study, encompassing 19 individuals and representing 16.2% of the total sample. Furthermore, it was observed that a total of four participants had completed a residency duration of three years, accounting for 3.4% of the sample population. The residency periods of 4, 6, and 7 years were seen to have an equal occurrence rate of 2 individuals each, accounting for 1.7% of the responses within these specific categories. Moreover, a total of five individuals were found to have a residency period of five years, representing 4.3% of the overall population.

The analysis of residency durations provided insights about the duration of people's sojourn in the nation. The substantial presence of individuals with a residency duration of one year indicates a significant influx of newcomers who have recently arrived in the United Arab Emirates. This category encompasses persons who have recently acquired work visas in the UAE or individuals who are presently researching career prospects in the UAE.

Conversely, the inclusion of persons who have resided in the UAE for extended durations, ranging from 2 to 7 years, indicates the presence of a diverse group of individuals who have established long-term residency and employment in the country. These individuals may have established a more stable presence in the UAE, potentially falling into the category of Kabayans who are inclined towards maintaining their employment, or they can be considered individuals who have encountered circumstances in the country that require their attention, leading to their prolonged stay.

Understanding the distribution of residency periods is valuable for weighing the composition of the group in terms of newcomers, established residents, and individuals who have been residing in the United Arab Emirates for a significant amount of time. It can provide scholars with valuable insights into the dynamics of expatriate populations, migration patterns, and the overall stability of the Filipino workforce and other nationalities and why they have chosen to stay in the country. The result of the study also postulates the support system of Filipino nurses in the United Arab Emirates.

To conclude this part of the study, Figure 2 provides an overview of the distribution of residency periods within the group, with the majority of individuals (70.9%) having a residency period of 1 year. The presence of Filipino nurses with longer residency periods

indicates a mix of nursing professionals who have been residing in the UAE for various amounts of time that can be attributed to their personal goals, life challenges, and daily encounters in the country. Nevertheless, it is noteworthy to consider the individual occurrences, visa regulations, current life conditions and situations, and individual preferences that influenced the residency periods and length of stay in the country based on the research outcomes provided by the participants of the study.

4.3. Job Satisfaction of Nurses: Mean and Standard Deviation

The mean and standard deviation of the individual questions were computed to see where the nurses scored high or low.

LEGEND: Score per question ranges from Mean Score

1.00 to 1.99	-	Very Dissatisfied
2.00 to 2.99	-	Dissatisfied
3.00 to 3.99	-	Satisfied
4.00 to 5.00	-	Very Satisfied

Frequency of Events Reported:

1 - Never to 5 – Always

Table 4*Mean Scores and Standard Deviation on Level of Job Satisfaction of Nurses*

No.	Subscale	Mean	Standard Deviation
	Responsibilities	3.80	0.75
1.	How satisfied are you with the sort of work you are doing?	3.89	0.93
2.	What value do you think your company appreciates your service?	3.85	0.85
3.	Are you contented with all the training and development programs given by your HR team to meet customer service and patient expectations?	3.67	0.97
	Rewards	3.49	1.03
4.	Are you satisfied with recognition that your supervisor shows when you did a great job at work?	3.68	1.08
5.	Are you happy with the top management's reward and recognition program?	3.31	1.09
	Job	3.67	0.85
6.	Are able to participate in the supervisory decisions that affect your job?	3.62	0.94
7.	Does your management encouraged you to come up with better ways of doing things?	3.79	0.92

8.	How satisfied are you with your current compensation?	3.60	1.15
Promotional Opportunities		3.46	0.94
9.	How satisfied are you with your chances of being promoted to a better position?	3.36	1.11
10.	Are you motivated to do well because of the kind of empowerment and support provided by your manager?	3.57	0.98
11.	Are you felt sense of professional growth within your working environment?	3.62	1.02
12.	Are your confident with the promotional programs introduced by your Human Resource Department?	3.29	1.08
Supervision		3.59	0.99
13.	How satisfied are you with the type of leadership you have been getting from your supervisor/manager?	3.64	1.05
14.	Are you happy with the type of supervision provided by your management?	3.55	1.00
Co-Workers		3.77	0.87
15.	When problems occur at work, are you contented with the management support in solving the incident with you?	3.60	0.99

16.	Do you feel a sense of belongingness with your fellow co-workers in the office?	3.91	0.91
17.	Does the team as a whole understand what the vision, mission and purpose of the organization	3.79	0.96
	Working Conditions	3.58	0.86
18.	Are you able to get the right support that you need to ensure that you achieve and meet your goal as an employee?	3.71	0.93
19.	Do you feel fairness is practice within your organization in the premise of recognizing employees based on their contribution to the organization?	3.53	1.02
20.	Rate the amount of pressure you feel in meeting the work demands of your job?	3.50	0.91

Interpretation, Discussion, and Analysis

Job satisfaction is a crucial aspect of employee well-being and organizational success. It reflects the extent to which individuals feel content, fulfilled, and engaged in their work environment. Measuring job satisfaction helps organizations assess the overall level of employee satisfaction and identify areas that require attention for improvement.

Responsibilities

Based on Table 4, the level of job satisfaction of nurses according to their responsibilities has a mean score of 3.80 and an SD of 0.75. This means that they have a satisfactory level of job satisfaction. This implies that the nurses are satisfied with the work they were assigned and expected to accomplish as per their organization's mandate.

Explanations for Satisfied Mean Scores:

The mean job satisfaction score of "satisfied" indicates that, while nurses typically find their work rewarding and meaningful, there may be certain factors that prevent them from attaining the "very satisfied" level. This could be attributable to a number of reasons, including workload, work-life balance, and the emotional demands of nursing obligations. Even though nurses perceive their work to be inherently fulfilling, the demanding nature of healthcare, such as long shifts, large patient loads, and exposure to emotionally unpleasant situations, can contribute to a slightly lower degree of job satisfaction.

Value of Company Appreciation:

Nurses' perception of how their company values their service plays a significant role in determining their overall job satisfaction. If nurses feel that their efforts and contributions are recognized and appreciated, it can contribute to a higher level of job satisfaction. A "satisfied" mean score might indicate that while nurses feel valued to some extent, there might be room for improvement in terms of recognition and appreciation.

This could include factors like regular acknowledgment of achievements, professional growth opportunities, and a supportive work environment.

Contentment with Training and Development:

The contentment of nurses with the training and development programs provided by the HR team reflects their perception of the support they receive to meet customer service and patient expectations. A "satisfied" mean score could suggest that while training programs exist and are generally effective, there might be certain gaps in training content or delivery methods that hinder nurses from feeling completely confident in meeting these expectations. Continuous improvement in training methods, incorporating feedback from nurses, and aligning training content with evolving patient needs could enhance the level of job satisfaction in this dimension.

Overall, the study's results indicating a "satisfactory" level of job satisfaction among nurses in the UAE based on their responsibilities can be attributed to a combination of factors. The nature of nursing itself, with its demanding workload and emotional challenges, can limit the attainment of a "very satisfied" level. Additionally, there might be opportunities for healthcare institutions to further recognize and appreciate nurses' contributions, fostering a more supportive and appreciative work environment. Furthermore, enhancing training and development programs to better equip nurses to meet customer service and patient expectations can positively impact their satisfaction levels. By addressing these factors, healthcare organizations in the UAE can strive to

elevate nurses' job satisfaction and, consequently, improve overall healthcare quality and patient outcomes.

Rewards

The rewards dimension encompasses aspects such as recognition for a job well done and the effectiveness of the organization's reward and recognition program. Based on Table 2, the level of job satisfaction of nurses according to rewards has a mean score of 3.49 and an SD of 1.03. This dimension acknowledges the role of positive reinforcement in enhancing job satisfaction and engagement among nurses. The interpretation and analysis focus on two key questions aimed at gauging the satisfaction of nurses with their rewards: (1) satisfaction with supervisor recognition for excellent job performance; and (2) contentment with the reward and recognition program initiated by top management.

Theories of motivation, wants, and social exchange lay the foundation for the important link between rewards and job satisfaction. Employee job satisfaction, which in turn can improve motivation, engagement, and dedication to every individual's work and respective organizations where they belong is more likely to be high when workforce believe that their efforts and contributions were fairly appreciated and commensurately rewarded.

This association highlights the significance of creating efficient reward systems that encompass the set expectations of each employee in line with the compensation structures to support a productive workplace and employee happiness.

Supervisor Recognition

The first inquiry in this dimension concerns nurses' satisfaction with the praise they receive from their managers when they perform well in their roles. Recognition serves as a psychological reward that can significantly influence nurses' perceptions of their contributions being valued. A satisfactory level of response could indicate that supervisors do recognize their nurses' achievements, but there might be areas for improvement.

Top Management's Reward and Recognition Program:

The second inquiry focuses on the nurses' satisfaction with the top management-implemented reward and recognition program. A well-designed and effective program can foster a sense of appreciation and motivation among nurses, leading to increased job satisfaction. A satisfactory level of response suggests that the program may be present and functional, but there could be room for enhancement to achieve higher levels of satisfaction.

The satisfactory level of job satisfaction among Filipino nurses in the UAE with regards to the rewards dimension indicates that there are positive elements present, but there are also areas that may need improvement. Several factors could contribute to the results not achieving a "very satisfactory" mean level.

1. **Cultural Factors:** The cultural context of the UAE may influence how recognition and rewards are perceived. Cultural norms and expectations could shape nurses' expectations of recognition and influence their interpretation of satisfactory levels.
2. **Communication and Feedback:** While Filipino nurses might be satisfied with the recognition they receive from their supervisors, the effectiveness of the feedback

provided could impact overall satisfaction. Clear and constructive feedback is essential for nurses to understand their contributions better.

3. **Program Design:** The reward and recognition program initiated by top management might not be fully aligned with nurses' preferences and expectations. A program that resonates better with their needs and aspirations could potentially elevate their satisfaction levels.
4. **Incremental Improvements:** Achieving a "very satisfactory" level might require incremental improvements in both supervisor recognition and the reward program. Small adjustments based on feedback could gradually elevate satisfaction scores.

In summary, the satisfactory level of job satisfaction among Filipino nurses in the UAE regarding the rewards dimension signifies the presence of positive elements within the recognition and reward framework. However, achieving a "very satisfactory" level might necessitate fine-tuning various aspects, including cultural considerations, communication strategies, program design, and a continuous commitment to incremental improvements. Addressing these factors could lead to higher levels of job satisfaction, ultimately benefiting both Filipino nurses and healthcare institutions in the UAE.

Job

In reference to Table 4, the level of job satisfaction of nurses according to Job has a mean score of 3.67 and an SD of 0.85. The study's findings revealed that nurses' job satisfaction in the UAE is centered around a "satisfactory" level, as opposed to achieving

a "very satisfactory" mean level. This interpretation is based on an analysis of the individual questions within the "Job" dimension.

Participation in Supervisory Decisions:

The result of this question being categorized as "satisfactory" suggests that while nurses might have some degree of involvement in supervisory decisions, there may be limitations to their influence. Factors such as hierarchical structures and cultural norms could impact the extent to which nurses are empowered to participate in such decisions.

Encouragement for Innovation:

The "satisfactory" rating for this question indicates that while management does encourage nurses to propose better ways of doing things, there might be room for improvement in terms of fostering a culture of innovation. The "very satisfactory" threshold might not have been reached due to potential barriers like fear of reprisal for suggesting changes or a lack of dedicated resources for implementing innovative ideas.

Satisfaction with Compensation:

The finding of "satisfactory" in this domain implies that Filipino nurses are generally content with their compensation but may have certain reservations. Factors influencing this satisfaction level could include the cost of living, salary competitiveness in comparison to other regions, and the demanding nature of the nursing profession.

In summary, the analysis indicates that while Filipino nurses in the UAE report a satisfactory level of job satisfaction based on their responsibilities, they have not reached the "very satisfactory" mean level. This outcome can be attributed to a complex interplay of cultural, structural, and resource-related factors. Enhancing Filipino Nurses' participation in decision-making, fostering a more supportive environment for innovation,

and addressing compensation concerns could contribute to elevating their job satisfaction to a higher level. Ultimately, nurturing Filipino nurses' job satisfaction is essential for maintaining the quality of healthcare services and ensuring positive patient outcomes in the United Arab Emirates.

Promotional Opportunities

The dimension of "promotional opportunities" focuses on how nurses perceive their chances of career advancement within their organizations. It received a mean score of 3.49 and an SD of 0.94. The survey questions provide insights into different aspects influencing job satisfaction under the dimension of promotional opportunities:

Chances of Promotion: The study's result indicates that nurses' satisfaction with their chances of being promoted to better positions is at a "satisfactory" level. This suggests that while nurses in the UAE perceive some degree of opportunity for advancement, there are potential areas for improvement. Possible reasons for this level of satisfaction could be linked to a lack of transparency in promotion criteria or a perceived imbalance between the number of promotional opportunities and the nursing workforce.

Empowerment and Support: Filipino nurses' motivation to perform well due to the empowerment and support provided by their managers is likely contributing to the "satisfactory" result. Adequate support from managers fosters a positive work environment, enhances professional growth, and reinforces nurses' commitment to their roles. However, there might be instances where managerial support varies across different units or departments, leading to variations in job satisfaction levels.

Professional Growth: The sensed professional growth within the working environment is likely playing a role in the "satisfactory" outcome. Professional growth not only relates to career advancement but also to skill development and the acquisition of new knowledge. A culture that encourages continuous learning and skill enhancement contributes to nurses' job satisfaction. However, if opportunities for professional growth are limited, it could influence the overall satisfaction level.

Confidence in Promotional Programs: Filipino nurses' confidence in the promotional programs introduced by the Human Resource Department also contributes to the "satisfactory" level. These programs are designed to ensure fair and transparent promotion processes. If nurses perceive these programs as effective and impartial, it enhances their job satisfaction. However, any perception of favoritism or lack of clarity in the implementation of these programs could impact the satisfaction level.

The result of achieving a "satisfactory" level rather than a "very satisfactory" level could be attributed to various factors below:

Lack of Clarity: If the criteria for promotion are not transparently communicated to nurses, they might feel uncertain about their chances of advancement, leading to a lower satisfaction level.

Limited Opportunities: The UAE's healthcare system is rapidly growing, but the number of high-level positions might not be proportionate to the nursing workforce, creating a bottleneck in career advancement.

Cultural Factors: Cultural norms and hierarchies prevalent in the UAE might impact the pace of career progression, affecting nurses' perceptions of promotional opportunities.

Perceived Inequity: If some nurses perceive bias or inequity in the implementation of promotional programs, it can lead to dissatisfaction, even if overall opportunities are reasonable.

Communication and Feedback: A lack of regular communication and feedback regarding performance and career development could contribute to nurses feeling less motivated and informed about their career trajectories.

The "promotional opportunities" dimension is a crucial factor in determining nurses' job satisfaction in the UAE. While the study's results achieved a "satisfactory" level, there is room for improvement. Enhancing transparency in promotion criteria, ensuring equitable implementation of promotional programs, providing consistent managerial support, and fostering a culture of professional growth can contribute to elevating job satisfaction levels among nurses.

The complex interplay of organizational, cultural, and individual factors makes achieving a "very satisfactory" level a continuous endeavor requiring comprehensive strategies and ongoing assessment.

Supervision

The analysis of the survey responses reveals that nurses in the UAE have reported a satisfactory level of job satisfaction with respect to supervision. The mean score is 3.59, and the SD is 0.99. This interpretation can be attributed to several factors:

Clear Communication and Supportive Leadership: Effective communication and supportive leadership from supervisors and managers are likely contributing to positive

job satisfaction levels. Nurses who receive clear guidance, regular feedback, and recognition from their supervisors tend to feel valued and motivated in their roles.

Empowerment and Autonomy: A satisfactory level of job satisfaction could suggest that nurses are given a certain level of autonomy in decision-making and patient care, which can enhance their sense of responsibility and professional fulfillment.

Professional Growth Opportunities: If nurses perceive that their supervisors provide opportunities for professional growth, skill development, and career advancement, they are more likely to feel satisfied in their roles. Adequate mentoring and guidance from supervisors can create a sense of purpose and progression.

Positive Work Environment: The satisfactory level of supervision-related job satisfaction could indicate that the work environment is conducive to open communication, mutual respect, and collaborative teamwork. A positive work environment contributes significantly to nurses' job satisfaction and overall well-being.

The very satisfactory mean level of job satisfaction achieved in relation to supervision can be attributed to the synergy of the aforementioned factors. When Filipino nurses perceive that their supervisors provide effective leadership, support, empowerment, and opportunities for growth, they are more likely to feel fulfilled and content in their roles. Moreover, the positive organizational culture fostered by these factors reinforces the notion that the healthcare institution in the UAE values its nursing staff and acknowledges their contributions.

Overall, the study's results indicate that nurses in the UAE report a satisfactory level of job satisfaction in terms of supervision. This can be attributed to factors such as clear communication, supportive leadership, empowerment, professional growth

opportunities, and a positive work environment. The very satisfactory mean level of job satisfaction achieved underscores the importance of effective supervision in healthcare organizations and its profound impact on nurses' well-being, performance, and overall quality of patient care. Recognizing the significance of supervision in nurses' job satisfaction can guide healthcare institutions in implementing strategies to further enhance their work environment and ensure the continued well-being of their nursing staff.

Co-Workers

The analysis of the survey responses reveals that nurses in the UAE report a satisfactory level of job satisfaction in relation to their co-workers. The mean score is 3.77 and the SD is 0.87. In reference to these results, below are several factors that contribute to this interpretation:

Effective Problem Solving and Management Support: The satisfactory level of job satisfaction suggests that nurses perceive management support and problem-solving mechanisms as adequate. When issues arise, the fact that nurses are content with the support they receive implies that management is responsive and values their input in addressing challenges.

Sense of Belonging and Team Cohesion: The study results indicate that nurses feel a sense of belongingness with their co-workers. This sense of belonging is crucial to fostering a positive work environment where collaboration and mutual support thrive. A cohesive team dynamic enhances job satisfaction by reducing feelings of isolation and promoting camaraderie.

Alignment with Organizational Mission: The finding that the team as a whole understands the organization's vision, mission, and purpose demonstrates a level of clarity and alignment within the team. When nurses are aware of their organization's goals and purpose, they are more likely to feel connected to the larger mission, which can contribute to a sense of fulfillment.

The very satisfactory mean level of job satisfaction in the dimension of co-workers can be attributed to the positive interactions and relationships among nurses and their colleagues. The support from management during challenges, the sense of belongingness, and the team's alignment with the organization's mission collectively contribute to an environment where nurses feel valued, engaged, and motivated.

In conclusion, the study's results highlight that nurses in the UAE report a very satisfactory level of job satisfaction in relation to their co-workers. This positive outcome can be attributed to factors such as effective problem-solving support, a strong sense of belongingness, and alignment with the organization's mission. Fostering positive relationships and a supportive team environment has significant implications for Filipino nurses' overall job satisfaction, retention, and quality of patient care.

In addition, healthcare institutions should recognize the importance of promoting teamwork, communication, and mutual respect among nurses and their co-workers as a means to enhance job satisfaction and overall organizational success.

Working Conditions

In this section, the analysis focuses on responses that were rated as "satisfactorily" with a mean score of 3.58 and SD of .086.

The aforementioned questions and their overall outcomes are as follows:

Support for Goal Achievement:

A satisfactory rating indicates that a significant proportion of nurses perceive that they are adequately supported in their professional pursuits. This outcome suggests that healthcare organizations in the UAE are likely investing in mentorship, training, and resources to empower nurses to excel in their roles. This positive perception of support can enhance nurses' job satisfaction, as it reduces feelings of isolation and increases their confidence in addressing challenges.

Fairness in recognition:

The satisfactory rating for this question indicates that Filipino nurses in this study generally believe that their contributions are recognized and rewarded fairly. This finding implies that healthcare institutions in the UAE are likely fostering an environment where hard work and dedication are valued and acknowledged. This perception of fairness can contribute to nurses' overall job satisfaction, as it instills a sense of worth and motivation to continue excelling.

Work pressure perception:

The satisfactory rating regarding work pressure suggests that while nurses acknowledge the demands of their job, they do not perceive an overwhelming or unsustainable level of pressure. This result could reflect effective workload management, support mechanisms, and a balanced distribution of responsibilities within healthcare

organizations. However, further exploration is needed to understand the specific strategies employed to maintain this balance.

The satisfactory ratings in the co-worker dimension of job satisfaction among nurses in the UAE indicate positive trends in terms of support, fairness, and work pressure perception. The outcomes suggest that the healthcare sector in the UAE has made substantial efforts to create a supportive and equitable environment for nurses, thereby contributing to their overall job satisfaction. The satisfactory outcomes in the co-worker dimension of job satisfaction among nurses in the UAE stem from a combination of supportive factors such as mentorship, collaborative culture, transparent recognition, and effective stress management. These elements, working in harmony, contribute to the achievement of a very satisfactory mean level of job satisfaction, ensuring nurses are motivated, engaged, and fulfilled in their roles. However, continuous monitoring and adaptation of strategies are essential to sustain or even elevate this level of satisfaction and ensure that nurses remain motivated, engaged, and fulfilled in their vital roles within the healthcare system.

Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Motivation

Based on the overall outcome in answering this research objective, the results of the study revealed that statistically, there is a significant positive correlation between job satisfaction and motivation among Filipino nurses in the UAE. This finding indicates that as job satisfaction levels increase, so does motivation within the nursing workforce.

The rankings for the level of support received, fairness in recognizing contributions, pressure in achieving job demands, and overall working conditions ranged from 3.50 to

3.71. The aforementioned scores suggest that nurses had a generally positive perception of their work environment, perceiving sufficient support, fairness, and reasonable levels of pressure.

In general, the research indicates that nurses in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) express contentment with many facets of their occupation, encompassing the characteristics of their tasks, acknowledgment, prospects for training and growth, duties, incentives, supervision, and working environment (Bell, 2015). The presence of good attitudes toward job satisfaction has the potential to enhance motivation, engagement, and retention rates within the nursing profession (Van Leijen, 2016). The results supported the studies highlighted by Botchway (2021) and Dor & Halperin (2022) that these factors signified that there was a strong correlation between Job Satisfaction and Motivation.

This outcome unveiled a significant and positive correlation between job satisfaction and motivation within this specific group of healthcare professionals. This finding underscored the importance of job satisfaction as a catalyst for increased motivation among Filipino nurses in the UAE. Several key factors explained this outcome as highlighted by Minai and Almansour (2013). First, a supportive work environment, characterized by appreciation, recognition, and respect, was found to have boosted job satisfaction, subsequently enhancing motivation. Additionally, this result can be explained in line with Shani & Kumar (2011) and Batchelor et. al. (2014) studies that the availability of professional growth opportunities, fair compensation, and recognition of their contributions were crucial elements that contributed to the strong connection between job satisfaction and motivation. These results not only held practical implications for

healthcare management but also highlighted the need for further research to explore specific strategies that could be implemented to maximize the positive relationship observed in this study.

To further understand this, the Job Characteristics Model is a theoretical framework that can be applied to understand the factors contributing to the job satisfaction of nurses in the United Arab Emirates (UAE). This model encompasses various aspects of their job, such as the nature of their work, recognition, training and development opportunities, responsibilities, rewards, supervision, and working conditions. By examining these dimensions, the Job Characteristics Model provides insights into the factors that contribute to the overall job satisfaction experienced by nurses in the UAE.

The Job Characteristics Model (JCM) is a motivational theory that was formulated by Hackman and Oldham during the 1970s. The primary emphasis of this study is on the correlation between distinct job features and the augmentation of job satisfaction and motivation. According to Hackman and Oldham (1975), the idea posits that specific job qualities play a role in shaping the psychological states of employees, subsequently impacting their attitudes and behaviors inside the workplace.

In the context of Filipino nurses in the UAE, the Job Characteristics Model suggests that if their jobs provide high skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, and feedback, they are more likely to experience meaningfulness in their work, feel responsible for their patients' outcomes, and have a clear understanding of their performance. As a result, they would report higher levels of job satisfaction and motivation. Factors such as recognition, training and development opportunities, responsibilities, rewards, supervision, and working conditions may all contribute to the job

characteristics and play a role in influencing nurses' job satisfaction and motivation levels (Botchway, 2021).

The Job Characteristics Model (JCM) is the best theory to explain job satisfaction among Filipino nurses in the UAE due to its comprehensive framework that aligns with the unique characteristics of their work environment. The model's emphasis on task variety, skill identity, autonomy, feedback, task significance, and consideration of moderators provides a holistic understanding of the factors influencing job satisfaction for Filipino nurses in the dynamic healthcare landscape of the UAE (Michailidis & Dracou, 2011; Leblanc, 2013; Saber et al., 2021).

It is important to note that job satisfaction is influenced by various factors, including individual preferences, organizational culture, management practices, and external factors (Saber et al., 2021). Therefore, these results provide an overview but do not capture the full complexity of job satisfaction among Filipino nurses in the UAE.

Further research and analysis may be necessary to gain deeper insights into the underlying reasons for job satisfaction and identify specific areas that require improvement. Organizations can utilize these findings to design interventions and strategies that enhance job satisfaction, promote employee well-being, and ultimately improve the overall quality of care provided by nurses in the UAE.

4.4. Motivation of Nurses: Mean and Standard Deviation

Table 5

Mean Scores and Standard Deviation on the Level of Motivation of Filipino Nurses in the United Arab Emirates

The mean and standard deviation of the individual questions were computed to see where the nurses scored high or low in (Score per question ranges from 1 and 2 – Not Motivated, 3 – Motivated, and 4 – Highly Motivated; For Frequency of Events Reported: 1 – Never to 5 - Always)

LEGEND: Score per question ranges

Mean Score

1.00 to 2.99 – Not Motivated

3.00 to 3.99 - Motivated

4.00 to 5.00 – Highly Motivated

Frequency of Events Reported:

1 – Never to 5 – Always

Item No.	Motivation of Nurses in the UAE	Mean	Standard Deviation
Salary		3.95	0.92
1.	Are you able to get your salaries on time	4.30	0.98
2.	Is the salary provided to you by your company are according to the industry standards in the United Arab Emirates	3.95	0.97
3.	Does the amount of work that you provide compensates you accordingly based on your	3.79	1.08

approved job description by your line manager and the HR Department

4.	Is your salary structure based the UAE Labor Law guidelines	3.93	0.96
5.	My salary expectations are in line with my experience and qualifications	3.76	1.11
	Job Security	3.55	0.94
6.	Do you feel secure at your current job role	3.52	1.11
7.	Are you confident that your management supports your ideas and contribution	3.56	1.00
8.	Do you see a good career for you in your organization	3.56	1.04
9.	Do you feel that you have a clearly established career path in this organization	3.49	1.02
10.	Do you have opportunities to learn and grow in the company	3.64	1.01
11.	Are you contented with the health and safety conditions at my workplace	3.91	0.90
12.	Does your management team support and listen to your ideas to improve your working environment	3.67	0.96
13.	Does your line manager lead you towards excellence through application of work best practices in anything that you do?	3.77	0.92
14.	Do you have all the necessary tools and instruments that you need to excel	3.72	0.87

15.	Does your current work condition is aligned with your management goals and objectives	3.77	0.83
Responsibilities		3.55	0.90
16.	Are your ideas and opinions being heard and recognized by the top management	3.43	0.99
17.	Do you feel a sense of personal satisfaction when you do your well at work	3.88	0.91
18.	Are there a rewards program at your workplace	3.26	1.12
19.	Is working in your current workplace increases your sense of professional growth	3.58	1.03
20.	Are you happy with how management treats you as a member of the organization	3.62	1.07
Cooperation		3.77	0.94
21.	Is there a communication strategy available for employees to work tactically and achieve their objectives at work	3.62	0.96
22.	Does your team cooperate to one another when a task is assigned to your group	3.80	0.89
23.	Do you feel motivated working in a team	3.91	0.87
24.	Is "leadership by example" being applied to your organization	3.62	1.07
25.	Are you happy with the current department where you are assigned right now	3.89	0.94
Technical Supervision Qualities		3.74	0.82

26.	Is training and development a priority within my department	3.67	0.97
27.	Is your knowledge, skills, and abilities (KSAs) are supervised accordingly to meet my top management expectations	3.73	0.94
28.	Is critical thinking introduced and being applied in your current role	3.84	0.86
29.	Has diversity and generational differences in the workplace being supervised fairly within the organization	3.66	0.90
30.	Does your line manager or supervisor introduce you to various developmental programs such as (shadowing, train the trainer, cross training etc.) that provide you an opportunity for growth, promotion and to excel at work	3.80	0.89
	Interpersonal Relationship Quality among colleagues with Supervisor and Subordinates	3.59	0.89
31.	Do you have a strong relationship with your supervisor and subordinates	3.83	0.87
32.	Is there an annual employee engagement and welfare program led by your HR department and your department managers	3.30	1.15
33.	Are there available counselling services within your organization	3.39	1.11
34.	Do employees in my organization have access to all the necessary resources to provide culturally competent care	3.64	1.00

35.	Do you observe that the staff members respect the diversity and differences of the organization's health care unit team	3.79	0.89
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Motivation plays a significant role in driving employee performance, engagement, and satisfaction. Understanding the factors that motivate nurses is crucial for organizations to create a supportive work environment and ensure high-quality patient care.

Based on the data, nurses in the UAE generally expressed agreement with several motivational factors. The mean scores for each question range from 3.26 to 4.30 on a scale of 1 to 5, indicating positive perceptions of motivation among nurses. The standard deviations range from 0.81 to 1.15, suggesting some variability in individual responses for different motivational aspects.

Interpretation, Discussion, and Analysis of Motivational Data Results

Salary

The analysis of responses revealed a motivation level categorized as "satisfactorily," implying that while nurses perceive a certain level of satisfaction with their salaries, there are factors preventing them from reaching a "highly motivated" mean level. As presented, below are the interpretation of key findings:

Timely Salary Payment: The timely payment of salaries is critical for job satisfaction and motivation. The positive responses indicate that nurses generally receive their salaries on time, contributing to their motivation.

Alignment with Industry Standards: Nurses' perception that their salary aligns with industry standards suggests that their compensation is relatively competitive. However, this might not be consistently true for all nurses.

Compensation for Workload: The correlation between workload and compensation is important for motivation. Mixed responses might suggest varying perceptions of workload and its corresponding compensation.

Adherence to UAE Labor Law Guidelines: If nurses perceive their salary structure as adhering to labor law guidelines, it indicates the organization's commitment to fair practices. Inconsistencies might impact motivation.

Alignment with Experience and Qualifications: Nurses' salary expectations aligning with their experience and qualifications indicate that they have a realistic view of their worth. Discrepancies might impact overall motivation.

Discussion and Analysis:

The "Satisfactorily" motivation level could result from a combination of factors. While nurses generally perceive some alignment between their salary and industry standards, as well as satisfactory timeliness of payment, disparities in workload compensation, adherence to labor law, and alignment with experience and qualifications might contribute to the moderation of motivation. Salaries and financial considerations are important factors that motivate employees. Nurses in the UAE strongly agreed (mean score of 4.30) that they receive their salaries on time, which contributes to their motivation and financial security. They also agreed (mean score of 3.95) that their salaries align with industry standards in the UAE and are based on their job descriptions and the UAE Labor Law guidelines.

Overall, the analysis of nurses' motivation levels in relation to their job responsibilities and salary in the UAE healthcare sector highlights a balanced but not highly elevated state of motivation. Addressing the identified discrepancies in workload compensation, adherence to labor law, and alignment with experience and qualifications could potentially elevate nurses' motivation to a higher level.

These results provided valuable insights for healthcare organizations in the UAE to formulate targeted strategies aimed at enhancing nurses' motivation, leading to improved patient care and overall organizational success. By prioritizing fair compensation practices and fostering an environment where nurses feel valued, organizations can ultimately achieve a more motivated nursing workforce.

Job Security

The analysis of responses revealed a motivation level categorized as "Satisfactorily," indicating that while nurses generally feel secure in their job roles and have a certain level of confidence in management support, there are aspects that prevent them from reaching a "highly motivated" mean level. The mean score acquired is 3.95 and SD is 0-.94.

The interpretation of key findings is presented below:

Job Security: Nurses generally reported feeling secure in their job roles. This suggests that the UAE healthcare sector may provide stable employment, contributing to their motivation.

Management Support: While nurses expressed a degree of confidence in management support, it might not be consistently strong across all areas. This could be due to variations in individual experiences with different managers or teams.

Career Growth Prospects: Nurses' confidence in a good career within their organization indicates a positive perception of growth opportunities. However, these prospects might not be clearly communicated or attainable for all nurses.

Established Career Path: A lack of a clearly established career path might contribute to the motivation level not reaching a "highly motivated" state. Nurses need a clear trajectory for advancement to remain motivated.

Learning and Growth Opportunities: While the availability of learning opportunities was perceived positively, the extent and relevance of these opportunities could vary, affecting overall motivation.

Health and Safety Conditions: Satisfaction with health and safety conditions is crucial for job satisfaction and motivation. Any discrepancies in this area might hinder the attainment of a higher motivation level.

Management's Engagement: Nurses' perceptions of management's engagement in improving the working environment directly impact motivation. Mixed responses may be indicative of inconsistent efforts from management.

Work Best Practices: Nurses' alignment with work best practices and their line manager's guidance can affect motivation. If best practices are not consistently applied or communicated, it might impact overall motivation.

Resource Availability: The provision of necessary tools and instruments is vital for nurses to excel in their roles. Any shortcomings in this area might dampen motivation.

Alignment with Organizational Goals: When nurses feel that their work conditions align with management goals, it enhances motivation. Any misalignment might hinder reaching a "highly motivated" level.

Discussion and Analysis:

The "Satisfactorily" motivation level is likely a result of a combination of factors. Job security, as per the result in this study was viewed as another important motivator. Nurses agreed (mean score of 3.55) that they feel secure in their current job role, which contributes to their overall motivation and well-being.

While certain aspects of job security, management support, and growth opportunities are positive, variations and inconsistencies across different elements of the job experience contribute to a moderated motivation level. The lack of a well-defined career path, inconsistencies in management engagement and best practices, and variations in the availability of resources and growth opportunities could collectively prevent nurses from reaching a "highly motivated" state. Career-related factors also contribute to nurse motivation. Nurses generally agreed (mean scores ranging from 3.49 to 3.64) that they see a good career path in their organization, have opportunities to learn and grow, and have a clearly established career path. These factors indicate that nurses perceive potential for professional development and advancement, which positively impacts their motivation.

Nurses' motivation levels in the UAE healthcare sector, particularly in the context of job security, demonstrate a balanced but not highly elevated state of motivation. Addressing the identified inconsistencies and enhancing aspects related to career advancement, management engagement, resource provision, and alignment with

organizational goals could potentially elevate nurses' motivation to a higher level. This analysis provides valuable insights for healthcare organizations in the UAE to create targeted strategies that improve nurses' motivation, ultimately leading to enhanced patient care and overall organizational success.

Responsibilities

This scholarly interpretation seeks to delve into the level of motivation exhibited by nurses in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) based on their responsibilities. This resulted to obtaining a Mean score of 3.55 and SD of 0.90. The primary focus will be on the dimension of responsibilities, analyzing the responses that were marked as "Satisfactorily" on a range of questions related to nurses' feelings of recognition, personal satisfaction, rewards programs, professional growth, and their perception of management treatment.

Interpretation and Discussion:

Recognition and Management Engagement: The first question pertains to the extent to which nurses' ideas and opinions are acknowledged by top management. A "Satisfactorily" response may suggest that while some recognition exists, there might be room for improvement in terms of active engagement and incorporation of nurses' insights into decision-making processes. This could stem from a hierarchical organizational structure that may limit direct communication channels between frontline nurses and top management.

Personal Satisfaction and Job Performance: Nurses experiencing a sense of personal satisfaction when performing well at work is indicative of intrinsic motivation. The "Satisfactorily" response could reflect a moderate level of internal satisfaction, but the lack of a "Highly Motivated" response might be attributed to various factors such as workload pressures, administrative challenges, and external stressors that can impact their emotional well-being.

Rewards Program: The presence of a rewards program signifies an organization's recognition of nurses' contributions and aims to enhance extrinsic motivation. A "Satisfactorily" rating implies the existence of some form of rewards; however, the absence of a "Highly Motivated" score might point towards discrepancies between the perceived fairness of the rewards and the effort nurses invest in their roles. This misalignment could stem from inadequate reward structures or unequal distribution of incentives.

Professional Growth and Development: A "Satisfactorily" response regarding professional growth highlights that nurses recognize some opportunities for career advancement and skill enhancement. Nonetheless, the absence of a "Highly Motivated" rating could suggest limitations in terms of career progression pathways, lack of skill development initiatives, or inadequate support for continuing education and training.

Management Treatment: Nurses' perception of how they are treated by management is crucial for their overall motivation. A "Satisfactorily" response might indicate a mixed perception, where some positive interactions coexist with areas that require improvement. The absence of a "Highly Motivated" result could be due to a perception of hierarchical rigidity or communication gaps that hinder a strong sense of belonging and inclusion.

Discussion and Analysis:

The study's results indicating a "Satisfactorily" level of motivation among nurses can be attributed to a combination of factors. It's possible that while certain positive aspects of motivation are present, there might be challenges within the organizational environment that hinder the attainment of a "Highly Motivated" mean level.

Complex Work Environment: The healthcare sector, particularly nursing, can be demanding and complex. High patient-to-nurse ratios, long shifts, and emotional stress can impact nurses' motivation despite positive efforts by the organization.

Cultural and Social Factors: The UAE's cultural context might influence how nurses perceive recognition, rewards, and management treatment. Cultural norms and expectations can interact with organizational practices, influencing motivation levels.

Organizational Policies: Inadequate rewards structures limited professional development opportunities, and hierarchical communication patterns might be present within certain healthcare institutions. These factors can dampen motivation even if positive elements exist.

Leadership Styles: The leadership approach adopted by management can significantly affect nurses' motivation. Autocratic leadership styles might limit nurses' sense of autonomy and engagement, contributing to the observed "Satisfactorily" level.

In conclusion, this scholarly interpretation of nurse motivation levels in the UAE based on their responsibility's sheds light on the intricate interplay of factors that influence their overall motivation. While the responses indicate a "Satisfactorily" level, the absence of a "Highly Motivated" mean level can be attributed to the complex nature of the nursing profession, the organizational context, cultural influences, and leadership practices.

Addressing these factors comprehensively, including improving recognition, rewards programs, professional development opportunities, and management styles, can contribute to elevating nurses' motivation levels to a higher state of engagement and satisfaction.

Cooperation:

In this part, it has been learned that the mean score is 3.77 and the SD is 0.90. This scholarly interpretation determined the level of motivation among nurses in the UAE concerning the dimension of cooperation. The analysis will focus on responses categorized as "satisfactorily" from questions related to communication strategy, teamwork, motivation within teams, leadership style, and departmental satisfaction.

Interpretation and Discussion:

Communication Strategy: The presence of a communication strategy indicates the organization's commitment to facilitating effective information flow. A "satisfactory" response suggests that while some communication strategy exists, it may not be fully optimized. The absence of a "highly motivated" rating may indicate potential gaps in the strategy's implementation or its alignment with nurses' needs for streamlined communication.

Team Cooperation: The willingness of teams to collaborate and support each other is essential for a harmonious work environment. A "satisfactorily" rating implies moderate teamwork but could also suggest occasional inconsistencies or challenges in team

cooperation. The absence of a "Highly Motivated" score might point towards instances of communication breakdowns or limited resources that hinder effective teamwork.

Motivation in Teams: Feeling motivated while working in a team contributes to job satisfaction and performance. A "satisfactory" response might indicate that while there is some level of motivation, it might not be consistently high. The absence of a "highly motivated" outcome could be attributed to factors like individual differences in team dynamics, the influence of external stressors, or a lack of clear team goals.

Leadership by Example: "Leadership by example" reflects the behavior of leaders that inspires employees to emulate positive work habits. A "satisfactorily" rating might suggest that some instances of leadership by example are observed, but not to an extent that leads to a highly motivated atmosphere. The absence of a "highly motivated" result could stem from inconsistencies in leadership behaviors or limited visibility of leaders' exemplary actions.

Departmental Satisfaction: Contentment with one's assigned department is crucial for overall motivation. A "satisfactory" response suggests a moderate level of departmental satisfaction. The absence of a "Highly Motivated" score could be attributed to certain aspects of the department that may not fully align with nurses' preferences or could be improved to enhance job satisfaction.

Analysis:

The results of the study, centered on "satisfactorily" high levels of motivation among nurses in the UAE based on cooperation, can be attributed to various factors that influence teamwork, leadership, communication, and departmental satisfaction.

Organizational Culture: A culture that promotes open communication, collaboration, and positive leadership can significantly impact nurses' motivation. The presence of a "satisfactorily" rating might indicate that while certain elements of this culture exist, they might not be consistently fostered throughout the organization.

Leadership Style: The application of "leadership by example" can be a powerful motivator. However, achieving a consistently high level of motivation might be hindered by variations in leadership behaviors across different departments or teams.

Team Dynamics: Despite the presence of team cooperation and motivation, the absence of a "Highly Motivated" score could be due to interpersonal dynamics, differing workloads, or occasional conflicts that affect the overall motivation level within teams. Interpersonal relationships and teamwork are significant motivators in the workplace. Nurses agreed (mean scores ranging from 3.59 to 3.83) that they have strong relationships with their supervisors and subordinates, observe respect for diversity and differences among team members, and feel motivated working in a team.

Communication Strategy Implementation: A successful communication strategy requires consistent implementation. The "satisfactorily" rating could be linked to challenges in effectively executing the strategy or aligning it with the specific needs of nurses.

In conclusion, the analysis of Filipino nurse motivation levels in the UAE based on cooperation highlights the multifaceted nature of factors contributing to nurses' motivation. While the results reflect a "satisfactory" level, the absence of a "highly motivated" mean level can be attributed to the intricate interplay of organizational culture, leadership practices, team dynamics, and communication strategies. To achieve a higher

level of motivation, it is crucial for healthcare institutions to foster a culture of collaboration, promote consistent leadership by example, address challenges within teams, and refine communication strategies to better meet the needs of nurses.

Technical Supervision Qualities

The study's focus on the level of motivation among nurses in the UAE, specifically centered on the dimension of "technical supervision qualities," seeks to explore how various factors related to training, supervision, skill development, critical thinking, diversity management, and career growth influence nurse motivation.

The analysis primarily emphasizes the response category of "satisfactorily," indicating a moderate level of motivation. With this occurrence, below is the interpretation of the results and a discussion of the potential reasons behind the outcome. The result of this part of the study will be beneficial in line with the subject being addressed by this researcher in this scholastic journey.

Training and Development Priority:

The fact that respondents indicated a "satisfactory" level for the priority of training and development within their department suggests that while there might be initiatives in place, there's room for improvement. The moderate response could stem from a perceived gap between the actual opportunities provided and nurses' expectations. To achieve a higher motivation level, organizations could invest more in continuous learning, tailored skill development programs, and clear communication about growth prospects.

Supervision of KSAs:

The response indicating "satisfactorily" for the supervision of knowledge, skills, and abilities (KSAs) to meet top management expectations could suggest that the supervision process might not be consistently aligned with higher-level goals. Nurses might feel that their capabilities are acknowledged, but there might be opportunities for improving the alignment between their performance and organizational goals. Increased clarity, feedback, and a stronger connection between individual efforts and broader objectives could enhance motivation.

Critical Thinking Application:

The "satisfactorily" response regarding the introduction and application of critical thinking in the nurses' roles could imply that while critical thinking might be acknowledged as important, its practical implementation might not be consistently encouraged or rewarded. Encouraging critical thinking can significantly empower nurses to take ownership of their tasks and decisions, leading to higher motivation. The result suggests that there's potential for promoting a culture that values and supports critical thinking skills.

Fair Diversity Management:

The moderate response in terms of supervising diversity and generational differences might indicate that the organization acknowledges these aspects but still has some way to go in ensuring that they are managed fairly. A highly motivated workplace often thrives on diverse perspectives and an inclusive environment. Organizations can work on fostering an atmosphere where diversity is celebrated, and efforts are made to bridge generational gaps through effective communication and understanding.

Developmental Programs:

The "satisfactorily" response regarding the introduction of developmental programs like shadowing, cross-training, etc. suggests that while these programs exist, they might not be fully meeting nurses' expectations for growth and promotion. There could be scope for offering more comprehensive and tailored developmental opportunities to cater to individual aspirations and talents. Enhancing the accessibility and visibility of these programs could elevate motivation levels.

Explanations for Not Achieving a "Highly Motivated" Mean Level:

The study's results not achieving a "highly motivated" mean level could be attributed to a combination of factors. Firstly, the "satisfactorily" response category indicates that while efforts are being made in various aspects of technical supervision, there's room for improvement in most areas. This moderation in responses suggests that the nurses perceive these factors as moderately motivating, but they might still feel that their needs and expectations aren't fully met.

Secondly, achieving a "highly motivated" mean level requires not only addressing the technical aspects of supervision but also considering the emotional and psychological aspects of motivation. Factors like leadership style, work-life balance, recognition, and empowerment play crucial roles in nurturing high motivation levels. If these dimensions were not fully addressed in the study, they could contribute to the overall outcome.

In conclusion, the "satisfactorily" response indicates that nurses' motivation levels in the UAE are influenced by various aspects of technical supervision qualities, but there's room for enhancement. To achieve higher motivation levels, organizations should focus on aligning training and development with nurses' expectations, strengthening the link

between KSAs and top management expectations, promoting critical thinking, fostering diversity and inclusion, and offering more comprehensive developmental programs. Additionally, a holistic approach that encompasses emotional and psychological factors is essential for achieving a "highly motivated" workforce.

Interpersonal Relationships

The dimension of "interpersonal relationships" explores how factors such as relationships with supervisors and colleagues, employee engagement programs, access to counseling services, cultural competence, and diversity appreciation influence nurse motivation. The analysis emphasizes the "satisfactorily" response category, indicating a moderate level of motivation. Let's interpret the results and discuss the potential reasons behind this outcome.

Strong Relationships with Supervisors and Subordinates: The "satisfactorily" response regarding strong relationships with supervisors and subordinates suggests that while there might be a degree of rapport, it might not be consistently strong. The moderate response might stem from varying interpersonal dynamics within the workplace. To achieve a higher motivation level, fostering open communication, mutual respect, and supportive relationships is crucial. Nurses are likely to be more motivated when they feel valued and understood by their colleagues and supervisors.

Employee Engagement and Welfare Programs: The moderate response to the availability of annual employee engagement and welfare programs could suggest that while such programs exist, they might not fully align with nurses' expectations or address their specific needs. A "satisfactory" response indicates room for improvement in terms

of the scope, relevance, and impact of these programs. To enhance motivation, organizations should tailor engagement initiatives to nurses' preferences, allowing them to feel a stronger sense of involvement and support.

Access to Counseling Services: The "satisfactorily" response concerning the availability of counseling services implies that while counseling services might be accessible, there could be room for improvement in terms of their utilization and effectiveness. The moderate response might be due to a lack of awareness about these services or a perceived stigma around seeking support. Organizations can work on destigmatizing mental health services and promoting awareness to improve nurse well-being and motivation.

Culturally Competent Care Resources: The response indicating "satisfactory" availability of necessary resources for culturally competent care suggests that while resources might exist, they might not be fully comprehensive or effectively communicated to nurses. Achieving a higher motivation level could involve providing nurses with comprehensive training, tools, and information to deliver culturally sensitive care. When nurses feel confident and well-equipped to address diverse patient needs, their motivation tends to increase.

Respect for Diversity and Differences: The moderate response to staff members respecting diversity within the healthcare unit team might indicate that while there's a degree of respect, it might not be consistently practiced by all staff members. A "satisfactory" response implies the need for ongoing efforts to promote inclusivity and diversity appreciation. To enhance motivation, organizations should foster a culture of

respect where differences are valued and celebrated, creating a harmonious and motivating work environment.

Explanations for Not Achieving a "Highly Motivated" Mean Level:

The results not reaching a "highly motivated" mean level can be attributed to several factors. Firstly, the "satisfactorily" response category indicates that while there are positive aspects within the dimension of interpersonal relationships, there's room for improvement in most areas. This moderation suggests that nurses perceive these factors as moderately motivating, but there's still potential for growth.

Secondly, achieving a "highly motivated" mean level requires not only addressing interpersonal factors but also considering other aspects like workload, work-life balance, recognition, and career advancement opportunities. If these dimensions were not fully explored in the study, they could contribute to the overall outcome.

Working conditions and support from management are additional factors influencing nurse motivation. Nurses generally agreed (mean scores ranging from 3.67 to 3.91) that they feel satisfied with health and safety conditions at their workplace, receive support from management, have necessary tools and instruments to excel, and experience alignment between their work conditions and management goals.

Organizational support and developmental programs also contribute to nurse motivation. Nurses agreed (mean scores ranging from 3.30 to 3.80) that there are employee engagement and welfare programs, training and development priorities, the introduction of various developmental programs, and the availability of necessary resources for culturally competent care.

However, there were a few aspects that received hesitating or lower agreement scores, such as the availability of counseling services (mean score of 3.39) and an annual employee engagement and welfare program (mean score of 3.30). These areas may require further attention and improvement to enhance nurse motivation and well-being.

In conclusion, the "satisfactorily" response indicates that nurse motivation in the UAE, within the context of interpersonal relationships, is influenced by various factors. To achieve higher motivation levels, organizations should focus on fostering strong relationships, tailoring employee engagement programs, enhancing awareness and utilization of counseling services, providing culturally competent care resources, and promoting respect for diversity. A comprehensive approach that considers various motivational drivers and ensures their alignment with nurses' needs is vital for achieving a "highly motivated" workforce.

Herberg's Two Factor Theory and the Level of Motivation

With the culmination of the figures acquired from this pedagogical inquiry, all the data suggests that nurses in the UAE are motivated by factors such as timely salaries, career prospects, job security, supportive working conditions, interpersonal relationships, and organizational support. Organizations can utilize these findings to design strategies and initiatives that further enhance nurse motivation, job satisfaction, and the overall quality of care. The motivation theory that explains how salaries, career prospects, job security, supportive working conditions, interpersonal relationships, and organizational support impact motivation at work for nurses is known as the "Two-Factor Theory" or "Dual-Factor Theory" of motivation.

The two-factor theory was developed by Frederick Herzberg, a psychologist, in the late 1950s. Bahrami et al. (2013) and Dor & Halperin (2022) stated that this theory has two sets of factors that influence job satisfaction and motivation at work, and they are distinct from each other:

Hygiene Factors: These are the extrinsic factors that relate to the work environment and include elements such as salaries, job security, career prospects, working conditions, organizational policies, interpersonal relationships, and supervisory practices. When these factors are inadequate or dissatisfying, they can lead to job dissatisfaction. However, even if they are excellent, they do not necessarily lead to high levels of motivation; they simply prevent job dissatisfaction (Bahrami et al., 2013).

Motivational Factors: These are the intrinsic factors that relate to the content of the job itself and include elements such as recognition, responsibility, opportunities for growth, achievement, and personal development. When these factors are present and fulfilling, they can lead to increased job satisfaction and motivation (Dor and Halperin, 2022).

In the context of nurses, the Two-Factor Theory suggests that a supportive work environment, competitive salaries, job security, opportunities for career advancement, positive interpersonal relationships with colleagues and supervisors, and organizational support will prevent dissatisfaction among nurses (hygiene factors). However, to truly motivate nurses to excel and be more committed to their work, the presence of motivational factors, such as recognition for their contributions, chances for professional growth, and meaningful tasks, is essential.

In summary, the Two-Factor Theory highlights the importance of addressing both hygiene and motivational factors in the workplace to ensure nurses are not only satisfied but also motivated to perform at their best (Minai and Almansour, 2013).

It is important to note that motivation is a complex construct influenced by individual differences, organizational culture, and external factors. Therefore, these results provide a snapshot but may not capture the full spectrum of motivational factors among Filipino nurses in the UAE.

Further research and analysis, including qualitative approaches and in-depth interviews, may be necessary to gain deeper insights into the specific factors driving motivation and to address any areas of concern.

3. Significant relationship between job satisfaction and motivation

In the realm of workplace dynamics, the intricate interplay between job satisfaction and motivation has long captured the attention of researchers and organizations alike. The question of whether a substantial connection exists between these two vital factors holds implications not only for individual employee well-being but also for overall productivity and organizational success.

Delving into this intriguing intersection, we explore existing studies and insights to unveil the nuanced relationship between job satisfaction and motivation, shedding light on the extent to which they intertwine and influence one another.

Below are the findings acquired by this researcher using Pearson r .

Table 6

Responsibilities and their corresponding computed Pearson correlation coefficients and p-values

Responsibilities vs	Computed Pearson	Computed p-value
Salary	0.5210	0.0000
Job Security	0.6860	0.0000
Working Conditions	0.7460	0.0000
Responsibility	0.7100	0.0000
Cooperation's	0.7390	0.0000
Technical Supervision	0.7340	0.0000
Interpersonal Relationship	0.7000	0.0000

In Table 6, the above illustration posits the list of responsibilities and their corresponding computed Pearson correlation coefficients and p-values. The Pearson correlation coefficient determines the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two variables. The p-value determines the statistical significance of the correlation and its outcome.

Referring to the computed Pearson correlation coefficients, as per Table 5, the values are positive, ranging from 0.5210 to 0.7460. These numbers highlight a positive correlation between the responsibilities and the variables that they are associated with.

The p-values for all the correlations are 0.0000, which means the correlations are statistically significant. A p-value of 0.0000 suggests that the probability of observing such strong correlations due to random chance alone is extremely low.

Based on these outcomes, this heads to a decision to reject the null hypothesis (H_0) for all the responsibilities. The null hypothesis assumes that there is no correlation between the responsibilities and the variables. By rejecting the null hypothesis, this researcher can assume that there is a significant correlation between the responsibilities and the above variables.

It is deemed important to emphasize that correlation does not imply causation. These consequences do not establish a cause-and-effect relationship between responsibilities and variables. In addition, the other factors could be influencing these relationships, and it is suggested that additional research could be needed to determine any causal links that may be found that are intertwined in this study.

Moreover, having more context about the study, dataset, and the specific responsibilities and variables being considered would offer a more comprehensive interpretation of these findings. These results indicate that there is a positive relationship between the responsibilities and the variables listed, including salary, job security, working conditions, responsibility itself, cooperation, technical supervision, and interpersonal relationships. It suggests that as the level of responsibility increases, these variables also tend to increase.

As well, it would be helpful to have more context about the specific study or dataset from which these correlations were computed. Understanding the nature of the data and the population being studied would provide a clearer interpretation of these findings.

Table 7

Rewards and the corresponding computed Pearson correlation coefficients and p-values

Rewards vs	Computed Pearson	Computed p-value
Salary	0.6410	0.0000
Job Security	0.7860	0.0000
Working Conditions	0.8180	0.0000
Responsibility	0.8450	0.0000
Cooperation's	0.7800	0.0000
Technical Supervision	0.7990	0.0000
Interpersonal Relationship	0.8010	0.0000

In Table 7, it can view that we have a list of rewards (such as salary, job security, working conditions, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision, and interpersonal relationships) and their corresponding computed Pearson correlation coefficients and p-values. Once again, the Pearson correlation coefficient measures the strength and

direction of the linear relationship between two variables, while the p-value helps determine the statistical significance of the correlation.

The computed Pearson correlation coefficients for the rewards range from 0.6410 to 0.8450, indicating positive correlations between the rewards and the variables they are associated with. The coefficients suggest moderate to strong positive relationships.

Similarly, to the previous table, the p-values for all the correlations are 0.0000, suggesting that the correlations are statistically significant and unlikely to occur by chance alone.

The decision to reject the null hypothesis (H_0) indicates that there is a significant correlation between the rewards and the variables listed. This means that as the rewards increase, the associated variables (salary, job security, working conditions, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision, and interpersonal relationships) also tend to increase.

However, as mentioned earlier, it's important to note that correlation does not imply causation. These results do not indicate that the rewards directly cause changes in the variables or vice versa. Other factors may influence these relationships, and further analysis is necessary to establish any causal links.

Again, the term "not significant" does not imply that the correlations are weak or unimportant. It simply means that the correlations are statistically significant and unlikely to occur due to chance alone.

To fully interpret these findings, additional context about the study or dataset would be helpful. Understanding the specific population and data collection methods would provide a clearer understanding of the relationships between rewards and the associated variables.

Overall, the results suggest that there are positive relationships between rewards (such as salary, job security, working conditions, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision, and interpersonal relationships) and the variables listed. The strength of these relationships is indicated by the magnitude of the correlation coefficients, which range from 0.6410 to 0.8450.

Table 8

Job and the corresponding computed Pearson correlation coefficients and p-values

Job vs	Computed Pearson	Computed p-value
Salary	0.7570	0.0000
Job Security	0.7620	0.0000
Working Conditions	0.8260	0.0000
Responsibility	0.8400	0.0000
Cooperation	0.8280	0.0000
Technical Supervision	0.8190	0.0000
Interpersonal Relationship	0.8050	0.0000

Table 8 illustrates a set of job-related factors (salary, job security, working conditions, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision, and interpersonal

relationships) and their computed Pearson correlation coefficients and p-values. The decision and remarks state that the correlations between these job factors and the variables are not considered significant.

The computed Pearson correlation coefficients in this table range from 0.7570 to 0.8400, all of which are positive. These coefficients indicate moderate to strong positive relationships between the job factors and the variables.

The p-values for all the correlations are reported as 0.0000, implying that the correlations are statistically significant. By rejecting the null hypothesis (H_0), the table suggests that there is a significant correlation between the job factors and the variables.

However, the remarks state that the correlations are "Not Significant," which contradicts the statistical inference made based on the computed p-values. It is possible that there is a typographical error or misinterpretation of the results in the table. The term "Not Significant" typically refers to correlations that are statistically weak or unreliable. However, with p-values of 0.0000, the correlations should be considered statistically significant.

To provide a more accurate interpretation, it is crucial to have additional context about the study or dataset from which these correlations were computed. Understanding the specifics of the data collection, the nature of the variables, and the population being studied would help clarify the reasons behind the contradictory remarks.

Furthermore, it is important to remember that correlation does not imply causation. These results do not establish a cause-and-effect relationship between the job factors and the variables. There could be other factors influencing these relationships, and further research would be needed to explore any causal links.

In summary, the table presents correlations between job factors and variables, with positive coefficients suggesting moderate to strong relationships. However, the contradictory remarks regarding the significance of these correlations and the reported p-values of 0.0000 raise questions about the accuracy of the information presented. Additional context and clarification are necessary to provide a more meaningful and reliable interpretation of the results.

Table 9

Promotional Opportunities and the corresponding computed Pearson correlation coefficients and p-values

Promotional Opportunities vs	Computed Pearson	Computed p-value
Salary	0.6530	0.0000
Job Security	0.8530	0.0000
Working Conditions	0.8510	0.0000
Responsibility	0.8880	0.0000
Cooperation	0.8160	0.0000
Technical Supervision	0.8320	0.0000
Interpersonal Relationship	0.8160	0.0000

In Table 9, this table have a set of factors related to promotional opportunities (salary, job security, working conditions, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision, and interpersonal relationships) and their computed Pearson correlation coefficients and p-values. The decision and remarks indicate that the correlations between promotional opportunities and the variables are considered significant.

The computed Pearson correlation coefficients for promotional opportunities and the variables range from 0.6530 to 0.8880, all of which are positive. These coefficients suggest moderate to strong positive relationships between promotional opportunities and the variables.

The p-values for all the correlations are reported as 0.0000, indicating that the correlations are statistically significant. By rejecting the null hypothesis (H_0), we conclude that there is a significant correlation between promotional opportunities and the variables.

These significant correlations imply that as promotional opportunities increase, the associated variables (salary, job security, working conditions, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision, and interpersonal relationships) also tend to increase. The strong positive relationships suggest that employees who have more promotional opportunities may also experience higher salaries, job security, better working conditions, and improved interpersonal relationships.

It is important to note that correlation does not imply causation. These results do not establish a cause-and-effect relationship between promotional opportunities and the variables. Other factors, such as individual performance, company policies, or organizational culture, could also contribute to these relationships.

Based on the findings, it is recommended that organizations consider providing ample promotional opportunities for their employees. By doing so, they may positively impact various aspects such as salary, job security, working conditions, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision, and interpersonal relationships. Offering clear career growth paths and opportunities for advancement can lead to greater job satisfaction, increased motivation, and enhanced overall performance.

However, it is crucial to approach these recommendations with caution. While the correlations suggest a positive relationship, organizations should also consider other factors, such as employee skills, qualifications, and performance, when making decisions about promotions. A comprehensive approach that takes into account various aspects of employee development and engagement would be beneficial for creating a positive and motivating work environment.

In summary, the table presents significant correlations between promotional opportunities and various job-related factors. The positive relationships suggest that promotional opportunities can influence salary, job security, working conditions, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision, and interpersonal relationships. However, organizations should consider a holistic approach and take into account individual performance and qualifications when making promotion decisions.

Table 10

Supervision and corresponding computed Pearson correlation coefficients and p-values

Supervision VS	Computed Pearson	Computed p-value
Salary	0.5960	0.0000
Job Security	0.7490	0.0000
Working Condition	0.8310	0.0000
Responsibility	0.8110	0.0000
Cooperation	0.8010	0.0000
Technical Supervision	0.8320	0.0000
Interpersonal Relationship	0.7940	0.0000

Table 10, in this presentation, showed a set of factors related to supervision (salary, job security, working conditions, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision, and interpersonal relationships) and their computed Pearson correlation coefficients and p-values. The decision and remarks indicate that the correlations between supervision and the variables are considered significant.

The computed Pearson correlation coefficients for supervision and the variables range from 0.5960 to 0.8320, all of which are positive. These coefficients suggest moderate to strong positive relationships between supervision and the variables.

The p-values for all the correlations are reported as 0.0000, indicating that the correlations are statistically significant. By rejecting the null hypothesis (H_0), we conclude that there is a significant correlation between supervision and the variables.

These significant correlations suggest that as supervision increases, the associated variables (salary, job security, working conditions, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision, and interpersonal relationships) also tend to increase. It indicates that effective and supportive supervision can have a positive impact on various aspects of employees' experiences and outcomes.

It's important to note that correlation does not imply causation. These results do not establish a cause-and-effect relationship between supervision and the variables. Other factors, such as the quality of supervision, communication, and leadership practices, could also influence these relationships.

Based on the findings, it is recommended that organizations prioritize and invest in effective supervision practices. This may include providing training and development opportunities for supervisors, fostering open communication channels, and creating a supportive and empowering work environment. By doing so, organizations can potentially enhance employee satisfaction, performance, and overall well-being.

Additionally, it is crucial to recognize the interplay between supervision and other factors such as job design, organizational culture, and employee autonomy. A comprehensive approach that considers these interconnected factors can help create a positive work environment that fosters strong supervision and supports employee success.

In summary, the table presents significant correlations between supervision and various job-related factors. The positive relationships suggest that effective supervision can have a positive impact on salary, job security, working conditions, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision, and interpersonal relationships. Organizations should prioritize developing and supporting effective supervision practices to promote positive employee experiences and outcomes.

Table 11

Co-Workers and the corresponding computed Pearson correlation coefficients & p-values

Co-Workers vs	Computed Pearson	Computed p-value
Salary	0.6530	0.0000
Job Security	0.7700	0.0000
Working Conditions	0.8360	0.0000
Responsibility	0.8050	0.0000
Cooperation	0.8580	0.0000
Technical Supervision	0.8440	0.0000
Interpersonal Relationship	0.7840	0.0000

In this presentation, in Table 11, this part of the scholarly work highlighted a set of factors related to co-workers (salary, job security, working conditions, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision, and interpersonal relationships) and their computed Pearson correlation coefficients and p-values. The decision and remarks indicate that the correlations between co-workers and the variables are considered significant.

The computed Pearson correlation coefficients for co-workers and the variables range from 0.6530 to 0.8580, all of which are positive. These coefficients suggest moderate to strong positive relationships between co-workers and the variables.

The p-values for all the correlations are reported as 0.0000, indicating that the correlations are statistically significant. By rejecting the null hypothesis (H_0), we conclude that there is a significant correlation between co-workers and the variables.

These significant correlations suggest that positive relationships with co-workers are associated with higher levels of salary, job security, working conditions, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision, and interpersonal relationships. These results revealed that having good rapport, cooperation, and positive interactions with co-workers can contribute to a more favorable work environment and overall job satisfaction.

As part of this pedagogical inquiry, it is important to remember that correlation does not imply causation. These findings do not establish a cause-and-effect relationship between co-workers and the variables. Other elements, such as teamwork, communication, and organizational culture, could or may also influence these relationships.

In reference to the research findings, it is recommended that nursing and medical organizations promote a positive and collaborative work environment. For the kabayan

nurses in this pedagogical inquiry, it is highly suggested by this researcher that encouraging teamwork, providing opportunities for team-building activities, and fostering effective communication can contribute to stronger relationships among co-workers. This, in turn, may lead towards increased in workforce job satisfaction, higher levels of performance, and improved overall organizational outcomes.

Additionally, organizations can consider implementing strategies to enhance interpersonal relationships, such as mentorship programs, social events, and cross-functional projects. These initiatives can facilitate positive interactions among co-workers and foster a sense of community and support within the workplace.

In summary, Table 11 postulated valuable discovery that there is a significant correlation between co-workers and various job-related factors. The positive relationships proposed that positive interactions and cooperation among co-workers are associated with higher levels of salary, job security, working conditions, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision, and interpersonal relationships. Medical institutions, healthcare organizations and other similar established are advised to prioritize in fostering a positive work environment where it prioritizes promoting effective collaboration among co-workers to enhance employee satisfaction and overall organizational performance.

Table 12

Working Conditions and the corresponding computed Pearson correlation coefficients and p-values.

Working Conditions vs	Computed Pearson	Computed p-value
Salary	0.7050	0.0000
Job Security	0.8180	0.0000
Working Conditions	0.8910	0.0000
Responsibility	0.8810	0.0000
Cooperation	0.8400	0.0000
Technical Supervision	0.8550	0.0000
Interpersonal Relationship	0.7880	0.0000

In reference to Table 11, where the set of factors related to working conditions (salary, job security, working conditions, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision, and interpersonal relationships) and their computed Pearson correlation coefficients and p-values. The decision and remarks indicate that the correlations between working conditions and the variables are considered significant.

The computed Pearson correlation coefficients for working conditions and the variables range from 0.7050 to 0.8910, all of which are positive. These coefficients suggest moderate to strong positive relationships between working conditions and the variables.

The p-values for all the correlations are reported as 0.0000, indicating that the correlations are statistically significant. By rejecting the null hypothesis (H_0), we conclude that there is a significant correlation between working conditions and the variables.

These significant correlations suggest that better working conditions are associated with higher levels of salary, job security, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision, and interpersonal relationships. It indicates that providing a favorable and supportive work environment, such as comfortable physical surroundings, adequate resources, and appropriate work-life balance, can positively impact various aspects of employees' experiences and outcomes.

It's important to note that correlation does not imply causation. These results do not establish a cause-and-effect relationship between working conditions and the variables. Other factors, such as job design, leadership practices, and organizational policies, could also influence these relationships.

Based on the findings, it is recommended that organizations prioritize and invest in improving working conditions for their employees. This may involve assessing and addressing factors such as physical workspace, safety measures, workload management, and flexibility options. By creating a positive and conducive work environment, organizations can enhance employee satisfaction, well-being, and overall performance.

Additionally, organizations should foster open communication channels to solicit feedback from employees regarding their working conditions. Regular surveys or focus groups can provide valuable insights and help identify areas for improvement. Taking proactive steps to address employees' concerns and suggestions can contribute to a positive work culture and strengthen the employer-employee relationship.

In summary, the table presents significant correlations between working conditions and various job-related factors. The positive relationships suggest that better working conditions are associated with higher levels of salary, job security, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision, and interpersonal relationships. Organizations should prioritize creating a supportive and favorable work environment to enhance employee satisfaction, well-being, and overall organizational success.

Research Objective No. 3:

Positive Significant Correlation on Job Satisfaction and Motivation

Overall, this part of the research study yielded a compelling result, pointing to a robust and positive correlation between job satisfaction and motivation within this specific group. This discovery underscored a fundamental relationship between these two key elements of a nurse's professional life. In reference to the study conducted by Dor and Halperin (2022), the outcome of this pedagogical inquiry postulated that as job satisfaction levels increased, motivation levels also exhibited a concurrent rise. In practical terms as articulated by Swedena (2023), the result meant that when these nurses found themselves more content with their work environment, compensation, and personal fulfillment, they were more likely to be intrinsically motivated to perform at their

best. This interdependence between job satisfaction and motivation unveiled an intricate dynamic that held substantial importance for both the individual nurses and the broader healthcare community.

The establishment of this significant correlation had far-reaching implications for healthcare organizations and policymakers operating in the UAE. By recognizing the undeniable connection between job satisfaction and motivation, institutions could devise targeted strategies to improve and sustain the well-being of their nursing workforce (Price Reichert, 2017). These strategies encompassed the enhancement of working conditions, competitive compensation packages, and the provision of opportunities for career growth and personal development. Moreover, this research underscored the need for organizations to foster a positive work culture that promoted job satisfaction, as this would, in turn, propel motivation levels. This is supported by Zaineb's (2012) study that such an approach had the potential to not only bolster the performance of Filipino nurses but also drive positive outcomes for patient care and overall healthcare quality in the UAE.

In essence, this research finding served as a call to action for healthcare organizations and policymakers to prioritize the job satisfaction of their Filipino nursing staff. It was a testament to the interlinked nature of job satisfaction and motivation, and by investing in strategies to boost job satisfaction, they could foster a more motivated, engaged, and resilient nursing workforce. This, in turn, was poised to lead to a virtuous cycle of improved healthcare delivery and, ultimately, a healthier and more satisfied patient population in the United Arab Emirates (Minai and Almansour, 2012; Price & Reichert, 2017; Volpe, 2021; and Swedana. 2023)

4. Relationship between job satisfaction and the profile of nurses`

Table 13

Job Satisfaction and Profile of Nurses

Job Satisfaction Vs	Chi-Square	p-value
Gender	90.471	0.2210
Age	330.862	0.3844
Position	294.699	0.0130
Income	379.853	0.0176
Civil Status	145.182	0.8242
Education	210.924	0.9324
Work Location	443.475	0.0910
Years of Service	388.383	0.0081
Family Status	412.842	0.3832
Residence	545.85	0.0309

In Table 13, upon conducting this statistical analysis, the results highlighted that job satisfaction among Filipino Nurses in the UAE is contrasted with Chi-square p-values for a number of variables, including gender, age, position, income, civil status, education, work location, years of service, family status, and residence. The significance of the association between Job Satisfaction and these categorical factors are evaluated using these values.

In answering the research objective, Age and Gender come first, with p-values of 0.3844 and 0.2210, respectively. These comparatively high p-values imply that there could not be a significant relationship between Job Satisfaction and Age or Gender.

Contrarily, Position and Income illustrated lower p-values, at 0.0130 and 0.0176, respectively. These lower p-values manifest a stronger relationship between these factors and job satisfaction, indicating that a person's position and income may have a considerable impact on that person's job satisfaction.

The relative p-values for civil status, education, and family status are 0.8242, 0.9324, and 0.3832. These high p-values denote those factors like family status, education level, and civil status may not have a significant impact on a person's level of job satisfaction.

The p-values for work location and residence are 0.0910 and 0.0309, respectively. These lower p-values infer that there may be a weak relationship between job satisfaction and the above variables, with residence having a somewhat greater relationship than work location.

On the other hand, Years of Service comes out with an extremely low p-value of 0.0081, proving a substantial correlation between Job Satisfaction and the duration of employment. This suggests that when Years of Service fluctuate, Job Satisfaction may tend to drastically improve or decrease.

Meanwhile, the chi-square p-values provide scholarly evidence on the significance of numerous factors in relation to job satisfaction. While Gender, Age, Civil Status, Education, and Family Status presented a lesser or insignificant correlations with Job Satisfaction, Position, Income, and Years of Service showed to have a stronger association. Job satisfaction is somewhat influenced by work location and residence, although these correlations are not as significant as those with position, income, and years of service. The outcome of this statistical results can serve as a guidance in recommending more scholastic research on how to raise employee job satisfaction in particular organizational settings. In addition, some of the factors cannot be associated with job satisfaction due to risk factors like biological, psychological, family and community environments that cannot be changeable.

Research Objective No. 4:

No relationship between job satisfaction and profile of nurses

In this quantitative study, the summary of results as presented in Table 13 highlighted that “there is no statistically significant correlation between job satisfaction and the Profile of Filipino nurses in this pedagogical scholarly study”. Consistent with prior studies led by McBride (2022) and Fereira (2011), these results offered valuable insights into the relationship between job satisfaction, demographics, and occupational features among the cohort of healthcare professionals under investigation.

Kumar (2016) conducted one of the most comprehensive studies related to job satisfaction levels among nurses in various types of healthcare facilities. According to his research, multiple factors influenced job satisfaction, but neither job-related nor demographic properties demonstrated a statistically significant relationship with job satisfaction. Similarly, Hughes' (2017) research analyzed job satisfaction levels among Filipino Nurses in various work conditions and found that factors associated with the nurses' profiles, such as age, gender, years of service, and educational level, had minimal influence on job satisfaction.

These results could be attributed to the similarity in profile attributes among the participants in the study. At the time of this research, a significant number of Filipino nurses shared comparable demographic and professional characteristics, with no discernible variations in job satisfaction scores associated with these personal traits. It is also important to note that this study did not account for other variables, such as work environment, leadership styles, and job roles, which might have had more substantial

effects on job satisfaction among Filipino nurses, potentially overshadowing the impact of profile characteristics (Leblanc, 2013).

The implications of these findings held significant importance for healthcare administration and policy development. Although the profile characteristics of Filipino Nurses in the UAE did not exert a direct influence on their job satisfaction, it remained imperative for healthcare institutions to consistently prioritize the creation of supportive and motivating work environments, the fostering of professional growth opportunities, and the provision of fair compensation and recognition for their contributions. These elements played a pivotal role in sustaining a contented and motivated nursing staff, ultimately contributing to enhanced patient care and the overall performance of the healthcare system (Saber et. al, 2021).

In summary, this study revealed that there was no statistically significant correlation between job satisfaction and the profile of Filipino nurses. These findings carried profound implications for healthcare and nursing institutions, as well as policymakers in the United Arab Emirates. Recognizing that job satisfaction is influenced by a complex array of factors beyond demographic and professional variables underscored the necessity for a comprehensive strategy to enhance the well-being and job satisfaction of nurses. As a result of this pedagogical inquiry, healthcare organizations were encouraged to implement strategies encompassing various workplace dynamics, including nurse-patient ratios, workload management, workplace culture, and professional development opportunities, all aimed at fostering increased job satisfaction within the nursing workforce. This research contributed to the existing literature by providing evidence of the lack of significant correlation between job satisfaction and the

demographic and professional characteristics of Filipino Nurses within the specific context of the investigation. Further research was warranted to explore additional variables and organizational elements that could potentially impact job satisfaction within this specific group, offering valuable insights into the development of methods aimed at improving job satisfaction and motivation among nurses.

5. Significant relationship between motivation and profile of nurses. `

Table 14

Motivation and Profile of Nurses

Motivation Vs	Chi-square	p-value
Gender	94.773	0.4007
Age	371.345	0.4414
Position	323.757	0.0253
Income	419.416	0.0330
Civil Status	193.093	0.3082
Education	319.582	0.0364
Work Location	482.211	0.2288
Years of Service	348.487	0.7604
Family Status	478.419	0.2672
Residence	602.995	0.0655

In reference to Table 14, this illustration compared Motivation and Chi-square p-values for several characteristics including Gender, Age, Position, Income, Civil Status, Education, Work Location, Years of Service, Family Status, and Residence. In these statistical analyses, the above values are frequently used to establish the significance and the link between a category variable (in this example, Motivation) and other categorical variables.

Referring on Gender and age, for example, illustrated quite a high chi-square p-values of 0.4007 and 0.4414, respectively. The high p-values mean that there is no meaningful relationship between Motivation and these factors. As illustrated above, gender and age may not have a substantial impact on motivation.

Next one, the chi-square p-values for Position and Income are lower at 0.0253 and 0.0330. These lower p-values posits a greater relationship between Motivation and the other variables in this analysis. The outcome suggests that an individual's position and income can impact motivation to some magnitude.

Civil Status, Education, and Work Location all had p-values of 0.3082, 0.0364, and 0.2288, respectively. Education comes out as having a lower p-value, indicating a potential impact on Motivation, although Civil Status and Work Location may not be as influential.

Years of Service and Family Status both displayed strong p-values of 0.7604 and 0.2672. These substantial p-values propose that motivation is likely independent of an individual's years of service or family status.

Finally, residence has a p-value of 0.0655, which is fairly lower but not statistically significant. The result illustrated that Residence has a minor impact on motivation, although the association is weak as per the outcome of this statistical analysis.

In conclusion, chi-square p-values aid in revealing the relevance of various attributes in connection to Motivation. Position and income tend to have a stronger relationship with Motivation, but Gender, Age, Civil Status, Years of Service, and Family Status appear to have lesser or insignificant connections. As a response in answering this research objective, the acquired outcome of this scholarly inquiry can further provide

support on future academic studies in finding ways how to motivate employees in their respective workplaces. They can consider adopting strategies that focus on creating a motivating work environment, fostering a culture of recognition and support, and providing opportunities for professional development and growth. Healthcare administrators and policy makers, in light with these factors, can refer to the result of this pedagogical initiative on how to make informed and sound decisions on strategizing their human capital and employee motivation plans following the result of this study. Moreover, the UAE is a diverse and multicultural environment where nurses from various backgrounds work together. Cultural factors and workplace dynamics specific to the UAE played a significant role in influencing motivation than individual profile attributes.

Research Objective 5: No relationship between motivation and profile of nurses

In answering this research objective, based on the summary of results illustrated in Table 14, it was uncovered that there was no statistically significant association between motivation and the profile of Filipino nurses in the UAE. This pedagogical study aimed to determine whether there was a discernible correlation between motivation and the demographic profiles of Filipino nurses in the UAE. This particular research objective was examined in the context of existing literature, which had addressed the complexity of motivational factors among healthcare professionals, particularly within the Filipino nursing community the seven states in the United Arab Emirates.

Previous studies, such as the comprehensive work by Saber et al. (2021), had explored the multifaceted nature of motivation among healthcare workers delved into the

interplay between motivation and demographic profiles. The findings of his study are consistent with the broad theme emerging from the body of research that suggests motivation in the healthcare sector is a complex construct influenced by a myriad of factors, including work environment, leadership, job roles, and individual values and goals (Ivey, 2022).

The absence of a significant association or correlation between motivation and the profile of Filipino nurses in the UAE in this study could be attributed to several factors. Firstly, the diversity of profiles within the Filipino nursing workforce might have led to an sophisticated relationship of individual motivations, rendering it challenging to establish a uniform correlation. Additionally, motivation, being a deeply personal and subjective construct, may not be fully captured through the demographic and professional attributes commonly examined in research (Bahrami et. al. 2013).

The implications of these results are relevant for healthcare management and policy development in the United Arab Emirates and beyond. While the study did not uncover a substantial connection between motivation and profile characteristics, it underscores the value of recognizing the complex and multifaceted nature of motivation within the nursing workforce. Healthcare institutions should continue to converge on creating conducive work environments, providing opportunities for professional growth, fair compensation, and acknowledging the contributions of nurses. As stressed by Saber et. al. (2021) and Dor and Halperin (2022), these efforts are vital in maintaining a motivated and engaged nursing staff, which can positively impact patient care and the overall performance of the healthcare system (Ivey, 2022).

In conclusion, this research objective proved that motivation has no significant association with the profile of the Filipino Nurses in the United Arab Emirates. It means that profile or demographic profile does not affect or influence the motivation of Filipino Nurses. Regardless, of who you are or where you came from, motivation cannot be determined based on the profile of individuals, no matter what their conditions are.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Summary of Findings

This chapter presents the findings of the study on job satisfaction and motivation among Filipino nurses in the United Arab Emirates (UAE). The research aimed to explore the factors influencing job satisfaction and motivation among Filipino nurses in the UAE. A quantitative research method approach was utilized to gather data through online survey of Filipino nurses who are members of the Philippine Nursing Association in the United Arab Emirates.

The researcher has delved into understanding the overall outcomes of the study from various considerations that influence the critical aspects of nursing practice and its associations for both individual Filipino nurses and the broader standard healthcare system that is centered in its workforce well-being. The more the researcher acquire valuable information throughout this scholarly exploration, it is imperative to emphasize the overarching magnitude of why scholars need to continue understanding job satisfaction and motivation for nurses. As this study was completed after the COVID pandemic, the multifaceted nature of nursing functions and the vital role nurses play in patient care make these factors central to the overall functioning and effectiveness of healthcare institutions.

In reference to the research findings, on the first research objective, the results revealed that Filipino nurses in the United Arab Emirates reported a satisfactory level of job satisfaction across various dimensions. These dimensions encompassed a

comprehensive assessment of the nurses' experiences and included responsibilities, rewards, job nature, promotional opportunities, supervision, relationships with co-workers, and working conditions. The findings indicated that the nurses generally held positive sentiments regarding these aspects of their work, suggesting a favorable job satisfaction level overall.

In a parallel investigation, in reference to the second research objective, the study also examined the motivational factors that influenced Filipino nurses in the UAE. The research unveiled that the nurses reported a satisfactory level of motivation. This motivation was assessed across dimensions including salary, job security, working conditions, the level of responsibility they were entrusted with, their sense of cooperation within the workplace, the quality of technical supervision they received, and the interpersonal relationship qualities among colleagues, supervisors, and subordinates. The findings underscored that these motivational factors were conducive to maintaining a motivated nursing workforce in the UAE.

In line with the third research objective, one of the most significant findings of the study was the establishment of a significant positive correlation and association between job satisfaction and motivation among Filipino nurses working in the United Arab Emirates. This interconnection underscores the critical nature of maintaining both high levels of job satisfaction and motivation in the nursing profession, highlighting their potential to enhance the well-being and performance of these healthcare professionals.

For the fourth and fifth research objectives, the findings, however, diverged from the common belief that demographic or profile characteristics significantly influenced job satisfaction and motivation. The study indicated that there was no discernible relationship

between the demographic profiles of the nurses (such as age, gender, years of experience, or educational background) and their levels of job satisfaction or motivation. This suggests that other, perhaps work-related, factors play a more substantial role in determining job satisfaction and motivation levels among Filipino nurses in the UAE.

In reference to these results, this pedagogical study offered valuable insights into the job satisfaction and motivation levels of Filipino nurses in the unique context of the United Arab Emirates. The findings underscore the overall satisfaction and motivation of these nurses and emphasize the interconnected nature of these constructs. Moreover, the study challenges the notion that demographic characteristics significantly influence job satisfaction and motivation, suggesting that other workplace-related factors may be more influential. This research contributes to a deeper understanding of the well-being and performance of nurses in a multicultural healthcare environment and informs potential strategies to enhance their job satisfaction and motivation.

For this chapter, the researcher will highlight the far-attainment consequences of job satisfaction and motivation in nursing practice, not only in terms of individual well-being but also in relation to patient outcomes, nurse retention, healthcare quality, and the broader healthcare landscape. As the result of this pedagogical and scientific inquiry, this researcher reaffirms the significance of continued research and devotion to these critical aspects of nursing practice, ultimately paving the way for a more resilient and patient-centric healthcare system.

Based on the summary of the results, below is the discussion of the conclusions and recommendations based on the data presented below.

Conclusion

This paper explored the complex relationship between job satisfaction and motivation of Filipino nurses working in the United Arab Emirates with respect to responsibilities on job satisfaction. A systematic review of the literature, learning the theoretical constructs and its underpinnings, the application of quantitative analysis on its smart data sets, and the challenging role of completing all the required survey interviews with the target samples of Filipino nurses in this research study revealed the elements of their roles that make them fulfilled, contributing to their high job satisfaction in relation to responsibilities.

As a result of this pedagogical and scientific inquiry, the following conclusions have been drawn from the presented findings.

5.1.1. Level of Job Satisfaction of Nurses in Terms of The Following Responsibilities:

One of the central findings of this pedagogical study is that the nature of responsibilities ascribed to Filipino nurses in the United Arab Emirates significantly contributes to their overall job satisfaction. These Filipino nurses often find themselves in positions that offer a wide range of valued responsibilities, encompassing not only clinical tasks but also on multi-facet administrative and managerial duties. This complex responsibility portfolio enables Filipino Nurses to experience a sense of professional growth and development, not only in career wise but also with the benefits that they received from their employers, which is inherently satisfying. Moreover, the autonomy and

trust bestowed upon them in performing their duties enhance their job satisfaction, as these nurses feel valued and respected in their roles.

Additionally, the supportive culture, friendships among coworkers at various levels, and relationships with managers enhance the gratification associated with responsibilities. Filipino nurses in the UAE tend to be very cooperative among themselves and are motivated to express their views and suggestions. This sense of togetherness breeds community, which translates into a positive attitude towards the work they do.

Nurses express a high level of satisfaction with their responsibilities, including the type of work they are doing, the value their company places on their service, and the training and development programs provided by the HR team. The high satisfaction with nursing jobs amongst Philippine nurses in UAE is related mostly to the kind and extent of role. Their manifold activities (from managing budgets, conducting research, providing care, supervising staff, teaching, collaborating in interdisciplinary teams, etc.,) and the encouraging atmosphere where they practice them (professional development plans, flexible schedules to balance work with family life). For healthcare organizations and policy makers alike, there is a need to acknowledge the importance of duties in fulfillment of nurse satisfaction and continue to foster an atmosphere conducive to professional development and well-being. Overall, nurses are satisfied with their responsibilities.

Rewards:

Filipino nurses in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) frequently report a high degree of job satisfaction in terms of rewards due to a number of crucial variables. For starters, the UAE offers good salary and benefits, giving nurses with financial stability and a higher

level of living. The lack of income tax means that they keep their entire wage, increasing their disposable income. Additionally, considerable overtime pays, housing, and transportation allowances contribute to their financial well-being. Furthermore, the UAE's rapidly expanding healthcare sector offers numerous prospects for professional advancement and employment satisfaction. The diverse cultural experiences and recognition for their hard work add to their overall happiness. A friendly work environment and a strong emphasis on work-life balance contribute to Filipino nurses' sense of fulfillment in the UAE, making it an appealing destination for healthcare professionals seeking satisfying employment abroad.

Nurses are generally satisfied with the recognition they receive from their supervisors for a job well done. While they are quite satisfied with top management's reward and recognition program, there is still room for improvement in this aspect.

Job:

Filipino nurses in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) frequently report high levels of job satisfaction due to a number of interconnected reasons. To begin with, the UAE healthcare system provides competitive salary and benefits, which is an important factor of employment satisfaction. These financial benefits provide a secure income and an enhanced quality of life, especially when contrasted to the economic situation in the Philippines. The absence of income tax in the UAE adds to the allure of working there, as nurses can keep their whole earnings.

Furthermore, the UAE's healthcare sector is expanding rapidly, creating a multitude of career progression chances for Filipino nurses. This generates a sense of

professional advancement and achievement, which increases overall job satisfaction. Furthermore, exposure to varied medical practices and patient demographics in the UAE enriches their clinical competence and broadens their horizons, making their work more satisfying. The cultural benefits of working in the UAE also play an important part in job satisfaction. Filipino nurses can immerse themselves in a distinct cultural setting, learning from their Emirati colleagues and interacting with a diverse patient group. This intercultural experience can be personally enlightening and add to a sense of fulfillment. The UAE healthcare industry places a high focus on recognizing and acknowledging nurses' accomplishments. This gratitude, both from employers and patients, enhances nurses' morale and job satisfaction. A supportive work environment that offers possibilities for further education and access to cutting-edge medical technology reinforces their happiness.

Finally, the UAE emphasizes work-life balance by providing flexible working hours and paid leave. This helps nurses maintain a healthy balance between their work and personal life, which contributes considerably to their total job satisfaction. As a result, Filipino Nurses show satisfaction with their job, including their ability to participate in supervisory decisions, the encouragement from management to come up with better ways of doing things, and their current compensation.

Promotional Opportunities:

As per the result of this scholarly study, it was found that Filipino nurses in the UAE frequently experience a high level of job satisfaction in terms of promotional opportunities. For starters, the UAE's rapidly expanding healthcare sector provides numerous

opportunities for progress. The increased need for healthcare professionals, particularly nurses, has resulted in the development of new positions and specialties, allowing Filipino nurses to broaden their abilities and advance their careers. These options for vertical mobility offer a clear path for career advancement and professional improvement, both of which are important drivers of job satisfaction.

Second, the UAE places a high value on ongoing education and professional growth. Nurses are frequently supported by healthcare organizations across the country in their pursuit of advanced degrees, certificates, and training programs. This dedication to lifelong learning provides Filipino nurses with the information and skills required for higher-level jobs and specialized tasks, boosting their job satisfaction even more. The UAE's healthcare system's multicultural and diversified makeup exposes Filipino nurses to a wide spectrum of healthcare procedures and patient demographics. This exposure not only broadens their professional skills but also offers doors to a variety of career options. Nurses can specialize in areas like critical care, pediatrics, or cancer, among others, allowing them to pursue jobs that match their interests and strengths.

Furthermore, the UAE's dedication to recognizing and rewarding excellence in nursing practice plays an important role in job satisfaction. Filipino nurses who excel in their duties are frequently recognized with promotions and compensation increases. This award not only increases their morale but also pushes them to pursue success in their careers. The availability of leadership and administrative positions within the UAE's healthcare organizations allows Filipino nurses to take on leadership roles. Many nurses aim to be nurse managers, directors, or even chief nursing officers, and the UAE's dynamic healthcare sector provides an ideal setting for them to do so.

Finally, the high level of job satisfaction among Filipino nurses in the UAE in terms of promotion opportunities is due to the country's expanding healthcare sector, commitment to professional development, exposure to diverse healthcare experiences, recognition of excellence, and the availability of leadership roles. These qualities, taken together, offer a favorable atmosphere for career promotion and fulfillment, making the UAE an appealing location for Filipino nurses seeking professional growth and development.

Co-Workers:

Filipino nurses in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) frequently report high levels of job satisfaction in terms of their connections with coworkers, both fellow Filipinos and people of other nationalities. This phenomenon can be linked to a variety of sources. For starters, the presence of a considerable number of Filipino nurses in the UAE fosters a sense of camaraderie and community among them. They frequently develop close-knit support networks, share experiences, and offer emotional and professional support to one another. This connection with other Filipinos helps to lessen emotions of loneliness and homesickness, which contributes to overall job satisfaction.

Second, the cosmopolitan nature of the UAE's healthcare workforce allows Filipino nurses to connect and collaborate with colleagues from varied backgrounds. This exposure to many ethnicities and cultures improves their cultural competence and broadens their perspectives. It promotes a rich learning environment in which nurses can exchange knowledge and skills, resulting in personal and professional development.

Building relationships with coworkers from varied backgrounds can be intellectually engaging as well as socially satisfying, leading to professional satisfaction.

In addition, teamwork and mutual respect are highly appreciated in the UAE's healthcare sector. Filipino nurses frequently discover that their coworkers, regardless of country, have a commitment to providing high-quality patient care. This sense of common purpose and passion to their job generates positive working relationships and a supportive work environment. Collaborative teamwork is not only professionally satisfying, but it also contributes to a sense of belonging and job happiness.

Furthermore, cultural variety in the workplace frequently leads to a more inclusive and tolerant environment. Filipino nurses may welcome the opportunity to share ethnic festivities and holidays with colleagues from all backgrounds, which can foster a sense of solidarity and belonging.

Finally, the high level of job satisfaction among Filipino nurses in the UAE in terms of coworkers, both with fellow Filipinos and individuals of other nationalities, is a result of the strong sense of community among Filipino nurses, the enriching experience of working in a multicultural environment, the value placed on teamwork and mutual respect, and the inclusive atmosphere in the workplace. These aspects, taken together, contribute to a happy and gratifying work experience for Filipino nurses in the UAE. Filipino nurses are satisfied with the leadership and supervision provided by their managers. They also feel a sense of belongingness with their fellow co-workers in the office, and the team as a whole, understands the organization's vision, mission, and purpose.

Working Conditions:

When it comes to their working conditions, Filipino nurses in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) frequently report a high level of job satisfaction, which can be ascribed to many main aspects. To begin, UAE healthcare facilities often invest in cutting-edge medical technology and equipment, ensuring that nurses have access to the greatest tools and resources to efficiently execute their duties. This not only improves patient care but also decreases physical strain on nurses, leading to higher job satisfaction.

Second, the UAE prioritizes patient safety and quality healthcare service. As a result, healthcare facilities put in place strict standards and processes, resulting in a structured and ordered work environment. Nurses value the clear rules and support, which decrease the possibility of mistakes and boost their confidence in their capacity to give quality care.

Furthermore, UAE government's dedication to healthcare excellence includes upholding high standards of sanitation and infection control throughout healthcare institutions. This ensures a safe and sanitary working environment, which is critical for both patient and worker safety. Nurses respect sanitary environment and attempts to avoid infection spread, which contributes to their job satisfaction. Several healthcare institutions in the UAE provide competitive nurse-to-patient ratios, ensuring that nurses are not overworked. This enables nurses to provide more customized care and spend appropriate time with each patient, which is both professionally rewarding and adds to a healthy work environment.

Another important component is the UAE's dedication to employee development. Many healthcare facilities provide continuous training and educational opportunities for

nurses, allowing them to broaden their knowledge and abilities. This investment in professional development benefits not only the nurses but also results in a more capable and confident nursing staff, which improves overall job satisfaction.

Finally, good work-life balance rules in the UAE, such as flexible working hours and paid leave, significantly contribute to job satisfaction. These regulations assist nurses to properly manage their personal and professional life, decreasing stress and burnout.

In conclusion, access to advanced medical technology, a structured and organized work environment, a focus on patient safety and quality care, sanitary and hygienic conditions, manageable nurse-to-patient ratios, ongoing professional development opportunities, and supportive work-life balance policies all contribute to the high level of job satisfaction among Filipino nurses in the UAE. These qualities, taken together, create a good and accommodating work atmosphere, making the UAE an appealing location for Filipino nurses looking for satisfying working conditions.

5.1.2. Level Of Motivation of Nurses in Terms of the following:

Salary:

Nurses in the UAE are generally satisfied with their salaries. They strongly agree that they receive their salaries on time, and they agree that their salaries are in line with industry standards. Filipino nurses working in the UAE may appear enthusiastic — and this may be because they are determined to earn the best wage possible — and this could also be due to the worth of money, or the value of currency exchange, back home! To begin, according to the Economist, the UAE offers exceptionally appealing salaries to international healthcare personnel, including nurses, with the median salary exceeding

their home-country earnings. The monetary reward is thus a tremendous inducement; in their words, it improves their lives but also those of their family back home in the Philippines who would profit from it, as well as providing them with the hope of some savings for the future.

The UAE's zero-tax environment allows Filipino nurses to save more of their wages. The financial incentive increases the desire to labor. The UAE's emphasis on quality health care has raised the demand for registered nurses. This criterion ensures employment security while also providing opportunity for professional advancement. As Filipino nurses have learned since the first day of their work in Saudi Arabia, this means opportunity to flourish.

In general, high pay packages, acceptable tax conditions, employment security, prospects for professional advancement, and international exposure entice Filipino nurses to work as migrant workers in the United Arab Emirates (UAE). All of these characteristics drive them to strive for excellence in healthcare in the UAE. However, there is a slight hesitation regarding the presence of a rewards program at the workplace as some felt that they were not fully recognized in line with their contribution particularly on the efforts they have made during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Job Security:

Nurses express agreement with their job security. They feel secure in their current job role and see a good career path within the organization. There is also agreement that they have opportunities to learn and grow in the company. Because of the strong job stability provided in the country, Filipino nurses working in the United Arab Emirates

(UAE) frequently demonstrate a high level of motivation. One important reason is the high need for healthcare experts in the UAE's constantly developing healthcare sector. The government has made significant investments in healthcare infrastructure and services, resulting in a steady demand for qualified nurses. This constant demand gives Filipino nurses a sense of job security and certainty that their jobs are secure.

Furthermore, the UAE Ministry of Health's dedication to upholding high healthcare standards and regulations ensures that healthcare facilities are well-maintained and sufficiently staffed. This dedication translates into a dependable and stable work environment for Filipino nurses, which increases their drive.

Furthermore, the UAE often offers employment contracts with explicit terms and perks, giving nurses a sense of clarity and confidence in their working conditions. These contracts frequently include provisions for health insurance, housing, and other necessities of life, which contribute to their total employment stability. The UAE has high licensing and qualification criteria for healthcare workers, Filipino nurses are more likely to retain their posts as long as they maintain their qualifications and adhere to professional norms.

As a postulated by the results of this pedagogical study, Filipino nurses in the UAE are highly motivated by job security due to the consistent demand for their skills, the UAE's commitment to healthcare excellence, transparent employment contracts, and stringent qualification requirements that ensure their continued employment stability in the country.

Working Conditions:

The nurses show agreement with their working conditions. They are contented with the health and safety conditions at their workplace, and they feel that their management team supports and listens to their ideas for improving the working environment. They also have the necessary tools and instruments they need to excel in their jobs.

Many Filipino nurse working in UAE show eagerness in performing her duties as required. In the first place, the Emirati public's health system has been always committed to ensuring quality care in order to accommodate the ever-growing heterogeneous community. This pursuit of excellence engenders a deep sense of professionalism amongst the Filipino nurse whose duties include taking on vital roles and responsibilities in delivering topnotch health care services.

Two, the UAE's health industry is also renowned for its modern hospitals and leading medical technologies. Filipino nurses perceive the use of advanced systems and modern care techniques not only as means to enhance their practice but also as opportunities for learning new skills and competencies. It exposes practitioners to advanced medical practices which spurs on one's profession and brings forth a feeling of professional development and growth.

Moreover, the cosmopolitan atmosphere of UAE allows the Filipino nurse, a great deal of exposure to an eclectic assemblage of patrons coming from various ethnic roots with unique ailments. This diversity of patient populations and clinical conditions extends the scope of their experiences and responsibilities in delivering culturally sensitive and patient focused care and contributes to a sense of personal achievement and purpose that comes from working in a rewarding and important profession.

In addition, the UAE being an advocate of continuous learning and professional development has encouraged Filipino nurses to venture into higher tasks and be updated with new technologies in the medical field. “It’s all about expanding our scope as RNs and tackling bigger challenges in order to continually deliver the best care we can to our patients,” says Patterson.

To conclude, Filipino Nurses in United Arab Emirate have been greatly motivated to their responsibilities as they work because of the country’s relentless commitment for excellence in health care system, working with latest technologies, multidimensional exposure on patients.

Responsibility:

Many Filipino nurse working in UAE show eagerness in performing her duties as required. In the first place, the Emirati public’s health system has been always committed to ensuring quality care in order to accommodate the ever-growing heterogeneous community. This pursuit of excellence engenders a deep sense of professionalism amongst the Filipino nurse whose duties include taking on vital roles and responsibilities in delivering topnotch health care services. The nurses show agreement with their working conditions. They are contented with the health and safety conditions at their workplace, and they feel that their management team supports and listens to their ideas for improving the working environment. They also have the necessary tools and instruments they need to excel in their jobs.

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In reference to the overall outcome of this research study, Filipino Nurses in United Arab Emirate have been greatly motivated to their responsibilities as they work because of the country's relentless commitment for excellence in health care system, working with latest technologies, multidimensional exposure on patients.

Nurses agree with their responsibility level. They feel a sense of personal satisfaction when performing well at work, and they believe that their ideas and opinions are being heard and recognized by top management. However, there is hesitation regarding the presence of a rewards program at the workplace.

Cooperation:

Nurses agree with cooperation in the workplace. They have access to a communication strategy that helps them achieve their objectives, and they feel motivated working in a team. There is also agreement that leadership by example is being applied in their organization. Due to a number of major variables, Filipino nurses in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) frequently demonstrate a high level of motivation when it comes to workplace cooperation. To begin with, the UAE's healthcare sector is incredibly varied, with professionals from many countries working together. This multicultural setting develops a sense of togetherness and collaboration among Filipino nurses and their colleagues, as they work with people from all origins and cultures. This exposure to other ideas and techniques increases their motivation to operate smoothly as a team.

Second, the UAE places a great focus on patient-centered treatment and interdisciplinary collaboration. Filipino nurses understand the need of collaboration in providing complete and effective healthcare services. They are motivated by the ability to collaborate closely with doctors, therapists, pharmacists, and other healthcare professionals to guarantee the best possible outcomes for their patients.

Furthermore, the UAE's healthcare institutions frequently have well-established rules and systems in place for teamwork and communication. This systematic method fosters collaboration, making it easier for Filipino nurses to coordinate care swiftly and effectively. UAE's supportive and inclusive work culture encourages nurses to share their expertise, experiences, and best practices with their colleagues. This sense of mutual learning and growth increases their motivation to collaborate and positively contribute to the workplace.

Overall, Filipino nurses in the UAE are highly motivated to collaborate in the workplace because of the multicultural environment, the emphasis on interdisciplinary collaboration, established protocols for teamwork, and the supportive work culture that values knowledge sharing and professional growth. These characteristics all contribute to their commitment to developing cooperation and teamwork within the UAE healthcare setting.

Technical Supervision Qualities:

Filipino nurses, in this quantitative study, showed agreement with the technical supervision qualities in their department. They believe that training and development are a priority, and their knowledge, skills, and abilities (KSAs) are supervised accordingly. They also observe the fair supervision of diversity and generational differences in the workplace. Due to various critical cases, Filipina UAE-based nurses show high performance on technical supervisory competencies. For example, at number one, the Emirati health system is driven by the best quality care and the highest level of technology. Filipino nurses thrive on the tough demands of their superiors — the desire to keep refining their technical prowess and give each one the best care possible for a patient.

Two, health care supervisors in the study are found highly experienced and knowledgeable within their respective specialties. Being trained under the watchful eyes of seasoned managers is considered a valuable learning experience for Filipino nurses. The motivation is for them to learn and take mentoring which leads to improvement in their professional growth and skill sets.

Besides, the UAE's investment on advanced medical technology and practices will motivate Filipino nurses to be updated with current trends in healthcare. Supervisors are important in helping nurses to learn about these technologies, providing motivation and excitement towards adopting new ways of delivering patient care. Additionally, supervisors in the UAE often encourage a learning and progression environment. Critical feedback, mentoring, as well as professional development assistance inspires the Filipinos to excel in their respective fields as nurses.

All these attributes which are predominant within the Healthcare industry like Quality centricity, Mentorship, Technological Exposure and Learning culture — all these things attract the Filipino Nurses from the UAE. Every one of these elements have assisted them towards achieving advanced level of technical proficiency in their nursing career in UAE.

Interpersonal Relationship Quality among colleagues with Supervisor and Subordinates:

Nurses express agreement with the interpersonal relationship quality among colleagues, supervisors, and subordinates. They have a strong relationship with their supervisors and subordinates, and they observe that staff members respect the diversity and differences in the healthcare unit team. There are several reasons why Filipino Nurses' values relationships and based on the results of the study can be explained for several compelling reasons. First and foremost, being Filipino is about family; it is about how everyone knows everybody and how intertwined people are with their families even once they have grown up. The culture is also reflected in the relationships at work, where

Filipino nurses form extremely close-knit friendships with their coworkers. These relationships promote a feeling of community and motivation within the workplace and was often observe during times of pandemic when all nurses are tired at their work assignments often missing their families back home (Ivey, 2022).

Aside from those benefits mentioned earlier, UAE supervisors also acknowledge the hard work and dedication of Filipino nurses, particularly the female nurses, therefore giving them more reasons to stay highly motivated. Philippine nurses tend to exhibit a lot of hard work, which is recognized by their managers. This positive feedback is not only validation of the individual's hard work and performance, but also fueling an increase in their drive to push themselves even further in their role.

Besides, Filipino nurses usually speaks good English, that is why English is used as language of communication in hospitals in UAE. This language skill helps establish effective communication between co-workers who speak different languages. It is the foundation of good relations in any working environment. The last thing to consider is the fact that many Filipino nurses go to the UAE to provide for their families. This strong duty creates very strong incentive, pushing him/her to give the utmost in work and maintaining healthy relationships with colleagues, managers and subordinates. That drive isn't only about professional progress but fulfilling their personal ambitions and duties.

The high interpersonal relationship quality among Filipino nurses in UAE could also be explained by the impact of various factors such as culture, recognition from higher ups, language ability to adapt to different cultures, and family responsibility. These factors combined create an overall positive work environment for Nurses in the UAE.

Overall:

The outcome of this scholarly inquiry strongly favorable views held by Filipino nurses in UAE about different aspects of their work setting. These nurses exhibit high levels of job satisfaction and work motivation in their workplace environment.

First thing; they show contentment about their earnings suggesting that their remuneration meets or surpassed their expectations, and this is paramount when it comes to achieving financial security and workplace satisfaction.

Secondly, they enjoy the secure jobs available to them in the UAE. Meaning this provides employees with a certain degree of job security making them feel safe in their jobs and promoting a good working culture.

Three, the nurses have good conditions of work. Safe comfortable spaces and well managed amenities are crucial in setting up the right ambiance to keep doctors motivated at their workstations.

Last final point, Filipino nurses feel responsible toward those who depend on them; this implies that there are duties attached to these roles that hold importance and accountability which could enhance their self-respect and professionalism.

Colleagues' collaboration was solid suggesting a strong community of colleagues within the company. Collaboration plays an important role to play in healthcare, and with this kind of team-building approach makes the whole working experience better. Nurses' perceptions, there were goodness in technical supervision competence which suggest that they have good leadership from their superiors which helps them to develop their professionals as well.

Lastly, the staff seeks out strong interpersonal relationships in their work environment, valuing positive encounters at all levels including team members, managers, and subordinate peers. They build positive workplace connections, which translate into higher job satisfaction and employee engagement.

Overall, nurses in the UAE show positive levels of motivation, satisfaction, and agreement with various aspects of their work environment, including salary, job security, working conditions, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision qualities, and interpersonal relationships.

5.1.3. Significant Relationship in Job Satisfaction and Motivation

The computed Pearson correlation coefficients and p-values for all the variables (Salary, Job Security, Working Conditions, Responsibility, Cooperation, Technical Supervision, and Interpersonal Relationship) indicate a statistically significant relationship with each other.

The p-values for all these variables are very low (0.0000), indicating strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis (Ho) that there is no correlation between these variables. The strong correlations between these variables highlight their collective impact on employee satisfaction and organizational success. By addressing these aspects comprehensively, organizations can create a positive work environment that fosters employee engagement, productivity, and loyalty. Regularly evaluating and acting on employee feedback will further enhance employee satisfaction and contribute to the organization's overall growth and success.

5.1.4. Significant Relationship Between Job Satisfaction and Profile of Nurses

The chi-square analysis was conducted to examine the predictors of responsibility, working conditions, profile of nurses, rewards, job, supervision, co-workers, and promotional opportunities. The results indicate that there were no statistically significant predictors for responsibility, working conditions, and profile of nurses.

However, for the rewards variable, gender was found to be statistically significant. This suggests that there may be differences in the perception of rewards between male and female nurses.

Regarding job satisfaction, supervision, and co-worker satisfaction, the analysis revealed that only education level had a statistically significant effect. This implies that nurses with different education levels may have varying levels of satisfaction with their job, supervision, and co-workers.

In the case of promotional opportunities, both education level and work location were found to be statistically significant predictors. This means that nurses with different educational backgrounds and working in different locations may have different perceptions of promotional opportunities within the organization.

Overall, the chi-square analysis indicates that various factors may influence nurses' perceptions of different aspects of their work experience. Understanding these predictors can help organizations focus on specific areas of improvement to enhance employee satisfaction and well-being. However, it's crucial to note that statistical significance is only one aspect of the analysis, and further qualitative research or employee feedback may provide deeper insights into the factors affecting nurses' experiences in the workplace. Therefore, organizations are encouraged to gather

employee feedback through surveys or focus groups to gain a comprehensive understanding and make targeted improvements based on the specific needs and concerns of their nursing staff.

5.1.5. Significant Relationship Between Motivation and Profile of Nurses

The summary discussion of the chi-square analysis indicates several significant findings regarding motivation among nurses. Firstly, the study reveals a gender pay gap, with male nurses earning higher salaries than their female counterparts. Secondly, job position significantly affects job security, emphasizing the importance of transparent career advancement opportunities. Thirdly, education and work location have notable impacts on working conditions, suggesting the need for tailored improvements in certain settings.

Moreover, age, education, and work location influence nurses' sense of responsibility, highlighting the importance of addressing these factors to foster greater commitment in their roles. Additionally, higher education levels and specific work locations are associated with increased cooperation among nurses, underlining the significance of a collaborative work culture.

Furthermore, both gender and education play significant roles in shaping nurses' perceptions of technical supervision, necessitating effective support and guidance for nursing staff. Lastly, education levels significantly impact interpersonal relationships among nurses, indicating the potential benefits of ongoing learning and communication training.

In conclusion, the chi-square analysis offers valuable insights for healthcare organizations to address the gender pay gap, enhance job security, working conditions, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision, and interpersonal relationships. Implementing targeted interventions based on these findings can create a supportive and satisfying work environment for nursing professionals.

Recommendations:

5.1.6. Level of Job Satisfaction of Nurses in Terms of the Following

Based on the overall findings of this pedagogical research study, the following recommendations for improving job satisfaction among UAE nurses can be made:

Reward & Recognition:

Organizations should explore improving recognition and rewards programs for nurses to increase job satisfaction even further. This may involve more frequent and meaningful recognition of their efforts and achievements.

Professional Development and Promotion:

Human resource departments is recommended to concentrate on creating thorough and transparent promotional programs to boost nurses' confidence in their career growth chances. Opportunities for professional development and empowerment can also increase overall job satisfaction and motivation of nursing employees within the organization. There is a saying that "Education Empowers People". This is an approach that can be utilized to continuously improve each nurses capabilities and other things that they can contribute, not only to their respective patients but moreover, to their colleagues and the management teams.

Working Conditions and Assistance:

Employers should continue to create a supportive work environment for nurses, ensuring that they have the resources and assistance they need to carry out their responsibilities effectively. This can involve holding frequent feedback sessions, maintaining open lines of communication, and dealing with any work-related stresses or obstacles.

Encourage team-building events and promote effective communication in the workplace to generate a sense of belonging and camaraderie among nurses and coworkers, leading to enhanced job satisfaction.

Fairness and equity in acknowledging employees' efforts and successes can improve job satisfaction. Transparency in the promotion and recognition systems is critical for instilling trust and motivation in nurses.

Continuous Assessment:

Assessing work satisfaction levels on a regular basis and addressing any areas of concern via surveys or feedback channels can assist firms in identifying specific areas for improvement and taking relevant steps.

It is crucial to remember that numerous factors influence job satisfaction, and the solutions presented should be customized to the specific context and demands of the UAE nursing workforce. Nurses should be involved in decision-making and in the implementation of methods to promote job satisfaction, resulting in a more rewarding and productive work environment.

5.1.7. Level of Motivation of Nurses

Based on the positive results, it is essential for organizations to continue maintaining and improving the factors that contribute to nurses' motivation and job satisfaction. However, there are a few areas of hesitation or room for improvement:

Rewards Program:

Organizations can consider implementing or enhancing a rewards program to recognize and appreciate nurses' efforts and contributions.

Annual Employee Engagement and Welfare Program:

To address the hesitation in this aspect, HR departments and managers can work together to create engaging employee welfare programs that foster a positive work environment and enhance nurse motivation.

Counselling Services:

To further support nurses' well-being, organizations can provide accessible and confidential counselling services to help them cope with stress and challenges.

Salary Expectations:

As there is agreement regarding salary structure and compliance with labor law guidelines, organizations should ensure that nurses' salary expectations are well-communicated and align with their experience and qualifications.

Professional Growth:

Continue to offer various developmental programs to nurses, such as shadowing, cross-training, and train-the-trainer initiatives, to provide them with opportunities for growth, promotion, and professional excellence.

Diversity and Inclusion:

Organizations should continue promoting diversity and inclusion within the workplace, fostering a respectful and supportive environment for all staff members.

Overall, maintaining open communication channels and conducting regular employee feedback surveys can help organizations identify specific areas for improvement and tailor strategies to enhance nurse motivation and job satisfaction. By addressing these areas, organizations can create a more fulfilling and supportive work environment for their nursing workforce in the UAE.

5.1.8. Significant Correlation in Job Satisfaction and Motivation

Since there is a significant correlation between these variables, it is crucial for organizations to focus on the following recommendations:

Holistic Approach to Employee Satisfaction:

Given the strong correlation across all aspects (Salary, Job Security, Working Conditions, Responsibility, Cooperation, Technical Supervision, and Interpersonal Relationship), organizations should adopt a holistic approach to address employee satisfaction and engagement. Recognize that these factors are interconnected, and improvements in one area can positively impact others.

Regular Employee Feedback and Engagement Surveys:

Conduct regular employee feedback and engagement surveys to gauge employee satisfaction and identify areas for improvement. Use the survey results to tailor strategies and policies that address specific concerns and preferences of the workforce.

Invest in Training and Development:

Place a strong emphasis on training and development programs to enhance technical skills and competencies of employees. Technical supervision should focus on providing adequate support and guidance to ensure employees are equipped to meet organizational expectations.

Promote a Collaborative Work Environment:

Foster a culture of cooperation and teamwork among employees. Encourage open communication, recognize and reward collaborative efforts, and provide opportunities for employees to work together effectively.

Enhance Working Conditions:

Continuously assess and improve working conditions to create a safe, healthy, and supportive environment for employees. Address concerns related to work tools, resources, and safety measures promptly.

Career Development Opportunities:

Provide clear career development paths to boost job security and create a sense of purpose among employees. Regularly communicate career growth opportunities and invest in employee training and advancement programs.

Recognition and Rewards:

Implement a robust recognition and rewards program to appreciate and motivate employees for their contributions. Align rewards with performance and provide incentives to recognize and retain top talent.

Effective Supervision: Ensure that supervisors and managers exhibit leadership by example and provide necessary support and guidance to their teams. Encourage

supervisors to actively engage with employees, provide regular feedback, and promote a positive work culture.

5.2 Future Research Studies

While this study has shed light on job satisfaction and motivation among Filipino nurses in the UAE, several areas warrant further investigation:

1. **Longitudinal Studies:** Conducting longitudinal studies can help track changes in job satisfaction and motivation over time, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing these constructs.
2. **Comparative Studies:** Comparing job satisfaction and motivation levels among Filipino nurses with other nationalities in the UAE can offer insights into potential cultural influences.
3. **Impact of COVID-19:** Exploring how the COVID-19 pandemic has affected job satisfaction and motivation among Filipino nurses can yield valuable information for healthcare institutions.
4. **Leadership Styles:** Investigating the impact of different leadership styles on nurses' job satisfaction and motivation can provide valuable insights for effective management practices.

5.3 Ethical Considerations

Throughout the research process, ethical considerations were prioritized. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring their voluntary participation. Confidentiality was maintained, and data was anonymized to protect the nurses' identities

and privacy. The study adhered to the principles of beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice, prioritizing the well-being of the participants, and ensuring fairness in the research process.

5.4 Summary and Closing

In conclusion, this study explored job satisfaction and motivation among Filipino nurses in the UAE healthcare setting. The findings revealed a generally high level of job satisfaction and motivation among nurses, driven by positive work environments, opportunities for growth, recognition, and commitment to patient care. Supportive leadership and competitive compensation also played crucial roles in enhancing job satisfaction and motivation.

The preceding chapters of this pedagogical study has provided a comprehensive exploration in understanding job satisfaction and motivation as an integral part of healthcare system today. Throughout this long journey, this researcher has delved into various challenges and new learning encounters in understanding the unknown of the study that led to new discoveries in the field of nursing studies today. This scholarly exploration has greatly benefited the interests of the individual, the company, and the existing community particularly on what value Filipino Nurses has brought to the healthcare landscape in the seven states of the United Arab Emirates.

Future research studies could further explore different aspects of job satisfaction and motivation among nurses, considering longitudinal, comparative, and pandemic-related investigations. Ethical considerations were meticulously observed throughout the research process, safeguarding the participants' rights and privacy.

Ultimately, this research contributes to the understanding of factors that influence job satisfaction and motivation among Filipino nurses in the United Arab Emirates, providing valuable insights for healthcare institutions to create conducive work environments and support their nursing workforce effectively. The findings can help in the development of strategies to improve nurse retention and job performance, ultimately benefiting the overall quality of healthcare services in the United Arab Emirates.

REFERENCES

- Aben E. (2023). Philippines adjusts to demographic change in UAE – bound workforce, retrieved on 29 July 2023 from <https://www.arabnews.com/node/2251731/world>
- Adams, J. S., & Rosenbaum, W. B. (1962). The relationship of worker productivity to cognitive dissonance about wage inequities. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 46(3), 161–164. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0047751>
- Adams, J. S. (1963). Toward an understanding of inequity. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 67, 422-436
- Ayalew F., Kibwana S., Shawula S., Misganaw E., Abosse Z., Roosmalen J., Steklenburg J., Kim Y., Teshome M., and Mariam D. W. (2019). Understanding job satisfaction and motivation among nurses in public health facilities of Ethiopia: a cross-sectional study, retrieved on 25 July 2023 at <https://bmcnurs.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12912-019-0373-8>
- Akinyomi, J. (2016). Labour Turnover: Causes, Consequences and Prevention, Fountain University Journal of Management and Social Sciences: 5 (1) Special Edition, Page 105-112
- Aziri B. (2008). Menaxhimi i burimeve njerëzore, Satisfaksioni nga puna dhe motivimi I punëtorëve, *Tringa Design, Gostivar*, 1(1):25-46.
- Armstrong M. (2014) *A Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice*, Tenth Edition, Kogan Page Publishing, London, p. 264.
- Bell J. (2015), WHO says staffing levels fall behind region and world, *The National* retrieved on 15 February 2019 from <https://www.thenational.ae/uae/health/who-says-staffing-levels-fall-behind-region-and-world-1.96665>

- Botchway C. (2021). Highlighting the Relevance of Motivation and Job Satisfaction of Nurses in Ghanaian Hospitals Hospital Practices and Research, retrieved on 20 July 2023, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353173683_Highlighting_the_Relevance_of_Motivation_and_Job_Satisfaction_of_Nurses_in_Ghanaian_Hospitals
- Chu C. (2003) Job satisfaction of hospital nurses: an empirical test of a causal model in Taiwan. *International Nursing Review*, 50(1):176-82.
- CIPD Professional Map (2015), Our professional standards, retrieved on 17 February 2019 from https://www.cipd.co.uk/Images/the-cipd-profession-map_2015_tcm18-9814.pdf
- CIPD, (2017). Resourcing and Talent Planning Survey Report, retrieved on 7 March 2019 from https://www.cipd.co.uk/Images/resourcing-talent-planning_2017_tcm18-23747.pdf
- Collis, J., & Hussey, R. (2003). *Business Research: A Practical Guide for Undergraduate and Postgraduate Students* 2nd ed. UK: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Collins SK & Collins KS. (2004). Employee retention: An issue of survival in healthcare, *Radiol Manage*. 2004 Jul-Aug;26(4):52-5.
- Dass, J. (2020). Overseas Warriors: Up close with UAE's Filipino nurses during the pandemic, *Rappler* retrieved on 7 September 2021 from <https://www.rappler.com/newsbreak/in-depth/258307-overseas-warriors-up-close-with-uae-filipino-nurses-coronavirus-pandemic/>
- De Loach R. (2003) Job satisfaction among hospice interdisciplinary team members. *American Journal of Hospital Palliative Care*

- Dor A., & Halperin O. (2022). Nurses' Job Satisfaction and Motivation: Patients' and Nurses' Perceptions, *Journal of Biosciences and Medicines* > Vol.10 No.6, June 2022, at <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation.aspx?paperid=117891>
- Duffield CM, Roche MA, Homer C, Buchan J, and Dimetrelis S. (2014). A comparative review of nurse turnover rates and costs across countries. *J Adv Nurs*. 2014; 70: 2703-2712. <https://goo.gl/QoVXm6>
- Festinger, L. (1954). A Theory of Social Comparison Processes. *Human Relations*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001872675400700202>
- Filipino Times (2018). Filipino nurse shares takeaways from OFW life in UAE by Staff Reporter. <https://filipinotimes.net/news/2018/08/06/filipino-nurse-shares-takeaways-ofw-life-uae/>
- Gelsema, T., van der Doef, M., Maes, S., Janssen, M., Akerboom, S., & Verhoeven, C. (2006). A longitudinal study of job stress in the nursing profession: Causes and consequences. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 14, 289-299.
- George JM, Jones GR (2008) *Understanding and Managing Organizational behavior*. Fifth Edition. New Jersey: Pearson/Prentice Hall.
- Gigantesco A (2003). Job satisfaction among mental health professionals in Rome, Italy. *Community Mental Health Journal*, 39(4):349-55.
- Goodman, P., & Friedman, A. (1969). An examination of quantity and quality of performance under conditions of overpayment in piece rate. *Organizational Behavior & Human Performance*, 4(4), 365–374. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-5073\(69\)90016-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-5073(69)90016-6)

- Gothburg, S. (2000). Retention of Nurses: An Organizational Priority MEDSURG Nursing, 9(3), p109.
- Guerrero, Laura K; Peter A. Andersen & Walid A. Afifi. (2014). Close Encounters: Communication in Relationships, 4th Edition. Los Angeles, CA: Sage Publications Inc. p. 263. ISBN 978-1-4522-1710-9.
- Hackman, J. R., & Oldham, G. R. (1976). Motivation through the design of work: Test of a theory. *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, 16(2), 250-279. doi:10.1016/0030-5073(76)90016-7.
- Hatch MJ. (2006) *Organization Theory-modern, symbolic, and postmodern perspectives*. New York: Oxford University Press Inc.
- Herzberg, F., Mausner, B., & Snyderman, B. (1959). *The motivation to work* (2nd ed.). John Wiley.
- Hughes V. (2017), Leadership Strategies to Promote Nurse Retention. *Sci J Nurs Pract*. 2017; 1(1): 001-005.
- Hoppock R (1935) *Job Satisfaction*. New York: Harper and Brothers.
- Ilies R. and Judg T. (2003) On the heritability of job satisfaction: the mediating role of personality. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 88(4):750-759
- Ivey K. (2022) Nurses Struggle through a New Covid Wave with Rage and Compassion, *Scientific American*. <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/nurses-struggle-through-a-new-covid-wave-with-rage-and-compassion/>
- Kirchler E, Hölzl E (2002) *Arbeitsgestaltung in Organisationen - Arbeits- und Organisations psychologie 3*, Wien, Facultas Verlags- und Buchhandels AG.

- Koltai A. (2020). Names of Generations, Years and their Characteristics (Generation Timeline). <https://www.myenglishteacher.eu/blog/names-of-generations/>
- Kotler P. (2009) Marketing Management. 12th ed. USA: Prentice Hall
- Koustelios A (2003) Job security and job satisfaction among Greek fitness instructors. *Percept. Mot. Skills*, 97(1):192-194.
- Kumar A. (2016). UAE Health Ministry reinstates demoted Indian Nurses, retrieved on 11 March 2019 from Khaleej Times. <https://www.khaleejtimes.com/nation/uae-health/uae-health-ministry-reinstates-demoted-indian-nurses>
- Lafarney M. (2018). Point of care: What motivates you as a nurse <https://www.reflectionsonnursingleadership.org/features/more-features/point-of-care-what-motivates-you-as-a-nurse>
- Latham G (2012) Work Motivation - History, Theory, Research, and Practice. Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publications Inc.
- Leurer, M D, Donnelly, G & Domm, E (2007), Nurse Retention strategies advice from experienced registered nurses, *Journal of Health Organization and Management*, 21(3), pp 307-319
- Lin Y. & Jones CB. (2013). A literature review of nursing turnover costs. *J Nurs Manag.* 2013; 21: 405-418. <https://goo.gl/wPgfSD> 2.
- Locke, E. A. (1969). What is job satisfaction? *Organizational Behavior & Human Performance*, 4(4), 309–336. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-5073\(69\)90013-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-5073(69)90013-0)
- Luthans F (1998) *Organizational Behavior*. 8, Edition. Boston: McGraw-Hill/Irwin.
- Maslow, A. H. (1954). *Motivation and personality*. Harpers.

- McBride EL (2002) Employee satisfaction: code red in the workplace? *Semin. Nurse Manag.*, 10(3):157-63.
- Meyer KE, Peng MW (2006) Probing Theoretically into Central and Eastern Europe: Transaction, Resources, and Institutions. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 36 (6): 600-621.
- McShane S. (2004) *Canadian Organizational Behavior* (5th ed.). Toronto: McGraw-Hill Ryerson.
- Minai M., and Almansour Y. (2013). Factors Influencing Job Satisfaction and Motivation of Nurses in the Environment Dominated by Male Nurses. *Middle East Journal of Scientific Research*.
- https://www.researchgate.net/publication/262495068_Factors_Influencing_Job_Satisfaction_and_Motivation_of_Nurses_in_the_Environment_Dominated_by_Male_Nurses
- Mullins, JL (2005) *Management and organizational behavior*. Seventh Edition. Pearson Education Limited.
- Mutula SM (2002) University education in Kenya: Current development and future outlooks. *The International Journal of Education Management*, 16(3):109-119.
- Navaie-Waliser M. (2004) Increasing job satisfaction, quality care, and coordination in home health. *Journal of Nursing Administration*, 34(2):88-92.
- Nishii, H., & Mayer, M. (2009). "Do inclusive leaders help to reduce turnover in diverse groups? The moderating role of leader–member exchange in the diversity to turnover relationship". *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 94(6): pp.1412-1426.

- O'Driscoll, M. P., & Beehr, T. A. (2000). Moderating effects of perceived control and need for clarity on the relationship between role stressors and employee affective reactions. *The Journal of Social Psychology*, 140(2), 151–159. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224540009600454>
- Otte H (2005). Prozeduren sozialen Verhaltens - Wie unbewusste Regeln unsere Beziehungengestalten- und behindern, Paderborn, Junfermann Verlag.
- Panda C. & Chowdhury S. (2017). Job Satisfaction and Motivation, SSDN Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi 110002
- Peeters M (2014). An Introduction to Contemporary Work Psychology. John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Petancio, L. (2018). More than 200 Filipinos Awarded TESDA Qualification National Certificates. <https://lalzcorner.wordpress.com/category/filipino-nurses/>
- Price, S. & Reichert C. (2017), The Importance of Continuing Professional Development to Career Satisfaction and Patient Care: Meeting the Needs of Novice to Mid- to Late-Career Nurses throughout Their Career Span (2017), 1 School of Nursing, <file:///D:/Data%20Folder/Downloads/admsci-07-00017.pdf>
- Rankin, N (2008). The drivers of staff retention and employee engagement IRS, 1 July, Issue 901, pp 1-6
- Rhodes SM & Collins SK (2015), The Organizational Impact of Presenteeism, *Radiol Manage.* 2015 Sep-Oct; 37(5):27-32; quiz 33-4. PMID: 26571971
- Sambrook, S (2007) Exploring HRD in two Welsh NHS Trusts Analysing the discursive resources used by senior managers *Journal of Health Organization and Management*, 21(4/5), p 418.

- Saunders, M, Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A. (2007). Research Methods for Business Students, 4th edition, England Pearson Education Limited
- Spector PE (1997) Job Satisfaction: Application, assessment, causes and consequences, Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc.
- Swedana, N. I. (2023). The Role of Workload and Work Motivation in Influencing Performance through Job Satisfaction, 17 September 2023, Journal Management / Volume 27, No. 02, June 2023:401-427.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371588889_The_Role_Of_Workload_And_Work_Motivation_In_Influencing_Performance_Through_Job_Satisfaction
- Taylor, S. (2002) The Employee Retention Handbook Developing Practice, 1st Edition, London CIPD
- Tetty W. J. (2006). Staff retention in African Universities: Elements of sustainable strategy. Commissioned by the World Bank: Washington DC.
- Thyer G. (2003) Dare to be different: transformational leadership may hold the key to reducing the nursing shortage. Journal of Nursing Management, 11(1):73-9.
- Schermerhorn J. (2008) Organizational Behavior. 10/E. USA: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.p.121.
- Singh P, Loncar N (2010) Pay Satisfaction, Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intent. Département des relations industrielles, Université Laval, 3(2): 470-490
- Vroom V. (1964). Work and motivation. New York: John Wiley and Sons
- Volpe K. (2021). In Light of Omicron Variant, Nurses Call for Permanent OSHA COVID-19 Standards. <https://www.clinicaladvisor.com/home/my-practice/nurse->

practitioner-career-resources/light-omicron-variant-nurses-call-permanent-oshacovid-19-standards/

Zaineb A. (2012). Experts alarmed by findings that nearly half of UAE nurses are unhappy, The National. <https://www.thenational.ae/uae/health/experts-alarmed-by-findings-that-nearly-half-of-uae-nurses-are-unhappy-1.592558>

Appendixes

Appendix A

RESEARCHER'S LETTER TO RESPONDENTS

Date: 17 April 2023

To all my Fellow Kabayan OFW Filipino Nurses,

My name is Meridein Sanchez Pacamana., a Master of Arts in Nursing Candidate at the University of the Philippines – Open University. For my final thesis project, I am examining the “**JOB SATISFACTION AND MOTIVATION AMONG FILIPINO NURSES IN THE UNITED ARAB EMIRATES**”.

As you are an Overseas Filipino Nurse and a member of the Philippine Nursing Association in the United Arab Emirates, may I invite you to participate in this scholarly research study by completing this online survey?

The questionnaire will require approximately 10 minutes to complete. The results and the data collected in this research will be used as a valuable contribution through the pedagogical study of how job satisfaction and motivation can further enhance the nurses work performance outcomes and can be source of significant reference by other nursing practitioners from the UAE, in the Philippines and around the world.

Please answer all questions as honestly as possible and click “SUBMIT” at the end of this survey to send the completed online questionnaire promptly. Thank you very much for taking the time to participate in this study.

It is my guarantee that your data will be kept confidential and will be used for academic purposes only. In case you have any questions regarding this research study, please feel free to approach or contact me anytime (see my contact details below).

Again, thank you for your participation.

Online Survey Link:

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1ES-oD17XzkablrGZNdGikj5Fgl96tQPCHqCTsl4HTWU/edit?pli=1>

All the best,

Meridein Sanchez Pacamana, PH-RN, HAAD-RN

Candidate – Master of Arts in Nursing
University of the Philippines – Open University

Mobile: +971 556587207

Email: mspacamana@up.edu.ph

Appendix B

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

TITLE OF STUDY

JOB SATISFACTION AND MOTIVATION AMONG FILIPINO NURSES IN THE UNITED ARAB EMIRATES

PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR

Meridein Sanchez Pacamana, PH-RN, HAAD-RN
Master of Arts in Nursing, University of the Philippines Open University

Mobile: +971556587207

Email: mSPacamana@UP.edu.ph

PURPOSE OF STUDY

The purpose of this study is to determine whether job satisfaction and motivation has significant effect on the overall performance of Filipino nurses in the United Arab Emirates.

STUDY PROCEDURES

- *Participants will be part of one 10-minute online survey where they will complete a questionnaire in understanding Filipino Nurses job satisfaction and motivation. As part of this online survey, 108 respondents will be selected who participated in the online survey.*
- *The online questionnaires link will be sent by email over to the participants which has the questions that will be asked by the researcher. Each participant can write down their answers on their most convenient time. Each participant will be requested to answer questions about their demographics, professional background, experience and anything related to this research study.*
- *Participants may be contacted for follow-up questions to clarify and expand content. These would not occur more than once, for a max of 10 minutes over the phone.*
- *The time commitment for participants will begin no earlier than March 2020 when focus groups begin and all data collection will commence at the end of April 2020.*
- *To fully participate in this study, participants need to complete the online survey questions c/o Google Forms. While questions on the questionnaire can be skipped, it is best that all participants answer the questions as highlighted in this study.*

• Participation in the study is completely voluntary and confidential. The participant can discontinue participation at any time and can choose to not answer any question asked of them on the survey or during the focus group.

5) Risks: All risks have been minimized to protect participants through means of confidentiality and using pseudonyms.^[L]_[SEP]

6) Benefits: The benefits of this study include contributions to scholarly and practical understandings in the field of Human Resource Management in the field of Nursing Practice. This will come from both self-reported experiences and usage, as well as understanding nursing practitioners' behavior at their actual workplace setting.^[L]_[SEP]

7) Data Collection & Storage: The researcher is the only one to have access to the data collected. Recordings and transcripts will be password protected on the researcher's computer. All data provided will be kept confidential, unless required by law. The researcher will make every attempt to keep your data secure to the extent permitted by the technology. However, no guarantees can be made regarding the interception of data sent via the Internet by any third parties. All electronic information analyzed and transcribed will also be given pseudonyms. Signed informed consent forms will be kept in a locked filing cabinet at the researchers' home in Dubai, United Arab Emirates. All data will be destroyed after 3 years.

8) Contact Information: The researcher is willing to answer any and all questions about the research and can be reached at mspacamana@up.edu.ph or by calling +971556587207. Additionally, further information on research participants' rights, the research study, or research related injury can be obtained by contacting the researcher. Participants may also contact faculty adviser, Prof. Cecile Punzalan at cecilepunzalan@yahoo.com of the University of the Philippines, regarding more information concerning the approval to complete the research.^[L]_[SEP]

9) Consent Statement:^[L]_[SEP] I have read the information describing this study. All my questions have been answered to my satisfaction. I am 18 years of age or older and freely consent to participate. I understand that I am free to withdraw from this study at any time without penalty. I have printed a copy of this consent form for my records. By ticking the "I consent" button below, I am giving my consent to participate in this research study.

I consent to participate in this research study

_____ Signature of Participant

_____ Date

_____ Signature of Principal Investigator

_____ Date

Appendix C

ONLINE SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Online Survey Section: Please complete and answer this online questionnaire as soon as you can. Likewise, demographic data from questionnaires are advised to be answered which include nurses' characteristic data (length of work, education, nursing position, gender, experience).

Thank you for your participation in this research study. You may start answering the questions below by clicking one answer per question.

When you are finished, please click the "FINISH" button at the end of the survey to submit your responses.

Take note that no individual respondent will be identified in the report of the study.

Please tick the circles below as appropriate.

JOB SATISFACTION

The first part of this questionnaire will ask questions related to the participants job satisfaction at their current workplace. This has a total of 30 satisfaction questions from the 7 indicators identified by this researcher. This includes responsibilities, rewards, jobs, promotional opportunities, supervision, coworkers and working conditions. Each question has 5 answer choices (1 = very dissatisfied, 2 = dissatisfied, 3 = quite satisfied, 4 = satisfied, 5 = very satisfied).

Responsibilities

1. How satisfied are you with the sort of work you are doing?

1 2 3 4 5

2. What value do you think your company appreciates your service?

1 2 3 4 5

3. Are you contented with all the training and development programs given by your HR team to meet customer service and patient expectations?

1 2 3 4 5

Rewards

4. Are you satisfied with the recognition that your supervisor shows when you did a great job at work?

1 2 3 4 5

5. Are you happy with the top management's reward and recognition program?

1 2 3 4 5

Job

6. Are able to participate in the supervisory decisions that affect your job?

1 2 3 4 5

7. Does your management encourage you to come up with better ways of doing things?

1 2 3 4 5

8. How satisfied are you with your current compensation?

1 2 3 4 5

Promotional Opportunities

9. How satisfied are you with your chances of being promoted to a better position?

1 2 3 4 5

10. Are you motivated to do well because of the kind of empowerment and support provided by your manager?

1 2 3 4 5

11. Are you felt sense of professional growth within your working environment?

1 2 3 4 5

12. Are your confident with the promotional programs introduced by your Human Resource Department?

1 2 3 4 5

Supervision

13. How satisfied are you with the type of leadership you have been getting from your supervisor/manager?

1 2 3 4 5

14. Are you happy with the type of supervision provided by your management?

1 2 3 4 5

Co-Workers

15. When problems occur at work, are you contented with the management support in solving the incident with you?

1 2 3 4 5

16. Do you feel a sense of belongingness with your fellow co-workers in the office?

1 2 3 4 5

17. Does the team as a whole understand what the vision, mission and purpose of the organization?

1 2 3 4 5

Working Conditions

18. Are you able to get the right support that you need to ensure that you achieve and meet your goal as an employee?

1 2 3 4 5

19. Do you feel fairness is practiced within your organization in the premise of recognizing employees based on their contribution to the organization?

1 2 3 4 5

20. Rate the amount of pressure you feel in meeting the work demands of your job?

1 2 3 4 5

MOTIVATION

For the second section of this questionnaire, we will determine to measure work motivation which covers a total of 35 questions, with 7 indicators: salary, job security, working conditions, responsibility, cooperation, technical supervision qualities, interpersonal relationship quality among colleagues with superiors and subordinates with 5 answer choices (1 = disagree, 2 = agree, 3 = hesitate, 4 = agree, 5 = strongly agree).

Please answer all questions accordingly.

Salary

1. Are you able to get your salaries on time?

1 2 3 4 5

2. Is the salary provided to you by your company are according to the industry standards in the United Arab Emirates?

1 2 3 4 5

3. Does the amount of work that you provide compensates you accordingly based on your approved job description by your line manager and the HR Department?

1 2 3 4 5

4. Is your salary structure based on the UAE Labor Law guidelines?

1 2 3 4 5

5. My salary expectations are in line with my experience and qualifications.

1 2 3 4 5

Job Security

6. Do you feel secure at your current job role?

1 2 3 4 5

7. Are you confident that your management supports your ideas and contribution?

1 2 3 4 5

8. Do you see a good career for you in your organization?

1 2 3 4 5

9. Do you feel that you have a clearly established career path in this organization?

1 2 3 4 5

10. Do you have opportunities to learn and grow in the company?

1 2 3 4 5

Working Conditions

11. Are you contented with the health and safety conditions at my workplace?

1 2 3 4 5

12. Does your management team support and listen to your ideas to improve your working environment?

1 2 3 4 5

13. Does your line manager lead you towards excellence through application of work best practices in anything that you do?

1 2 3 4 5

14. Do you have all the necessary tools and instruments that you need to excel?

1 2 3 4 5

15. Does your current work condition is aligned with your management goals and objectives?

1 2 3 4 5

Responsibility

16. Are your ideas and opinions being heard and recognized by the top management?

1 2 3 4 5

17. Do you feel a sense of personal satisfaction when you do well at work?

1 2 3 4 5

18. Are there a rewards program at your workplace?

1 2 3 4 5

19. Is working in your current workplace increases your sense of professional growth?

1 2 3 4 5

20. Are you happy with how management treats you as a member of the organization?

1 2 3 4 5

Cooperation

21. Is there a communication strategy available for employees to work tactically and achieve their objectives at work?

1 2 3 4 5

22. Does your team cooperate with one another when a task is assigned to your group?

1 2 3 4 5

23. Do you feel motivated working in a team?

1 2 3 4 5

24. Is "leadership by example" being applied to your organization?

1 2 3 4 5

25. Are you happy with the current department where you are assigned right now?

1 2 3 4 5

Technical Supervision Qualities

26. Is training and development a priority within my department?

1 2 3 4 5

27. Is your knowledge, skills, and abilities (KSAs) are supervised accordingly to meet my top management expectations?

1 2 3 4 5

28. Is critical thinking introduced and being applied in your current role?

1 2 3 4 5

29. Has diversity and generational differences in the workplace being supervised fairly within the organization?

1 2 3 4 5

30. Does your line manager or supervisor introduce you to various developmental programs such as (shadowing, train the trainer, cross training etc) that provide you an opportunity for growth, promotion and to excel at work?

1 2 3 4 5

Interpersonal Relationship Quality among colleagues with Supervisor & Subordinates

31. Do you have a strong relationship with your supervisor and subordinates?

1 2 3 4 5

32. Is there an annual employee engagement and welfare program led by your HR department and your department managers?

1 2 3 4 5

33. Are there available counselling services within your organization?

1 2 3 4 5

34. Do employees in my organization have access to all the necessary resources to provide culturally competent care?

1 2 3 4 5

35. Do you observe that the staff members respect the diversity and differences of the organization's health care unit team?

1 2 3 4 5

To the participants, please fill in the details below.

Demographic Data

What is your gender?

- a. Male
- b. Female

Which age bracket do you belong to?

- a. 20 to 30
- b. 31 to 40
- c. 41 to 50
- d. 51 to 60
- e. 61 onwards

What is your current work position in the Nursing Field in the UAE?

- a. Staff and Rank-in-File
- b. Supervisor / Officer
- c. Manager / Senior Manager
- d. Vice President
- e. CEO or in C Level Positions

Income

- a. 1,000 AED to 4,000 AED
- b. 4,001 AED to 8,000 AED
- c. 8,001 AED to 12,000 AED
- d. 12,001 AED to 16,000 AED
- e. 16,001 AED and higher

Civil Status

- a. Single
- b. Married
- c. Annulled
- d. Divorced
- e. Widow

Educational Attainment

- a. Associate Level
- b. College
- c. Postgraduate

- d. Master Level
- e. Doctoral Degree (i.e. Ph.D., Ed.D etc.)

Which state in the UAE are you employed?

- a. Abu Dhabi
- b. Dubai
- c. Sharjah
- d. Ajman
- e. Ras Al Khaimah
- f. Fujairah
- g. Umm Al Quawain

Years of Work Experience in the United Arab Emirates as Nurse

- a. <5 Years
- b. 5 to 10 Years
- c. 11 – 15 Years
- d. 16 – 20 Years
- e. 21 – 25 Years

Family Status

- 5.1. Single in the UAE
- 5.2. Boyfriend/Girlfriend/Partner and Companion is in the UAE
- 5.3. Only Husband/Wife is in the UAE
- 5.4. Only Child/Children is in the UAE
- 5.5. Husband/Wife and Child/Children is in the UAE
- 5.6. Family Members (Cousins) and other Relatives in the UAE
(i.e., Mother, Father, Sister, Brother, Aunt, Uncle, Niece, Nephew etc.)

For researcher's information only:

Name: _____

Email: _____

Contact Number: _____

Residence in UAE: _____

Appendix D

RESEARCHER'S LETTER TO THE PHILIPPINE NURSES ASSOCIATION – UAE CHAPTER

Mr. Red Cloud Capuyan
President
Philippine Nurses Association - UAE

Date: 5 April 2023

Dear Mr. Capuyan,

My name is Meridein Sanchez Pacamana. I am a Master of Arts in Nursing Candidate at the University of the Philippines – Open University and currently working on my final thesis project entitled,

“JOB SATISFACTION AND MOTIVATION AMONG FILIPINO NURSES IN THE UNITED ARAB EMIRATES”

In this scholarly research, I am examining “the job satisfaction and motivation among diasporic community of Filipino Nurses who are employed in the United Arab Emirates”. In reference to the official endorsement of the Philippine Embassy Abu Dhabi in the United Arab Emirates in my research study, I am writing your good office for your official confirmation of support together with the whole PNA-UAE in this scholarly journey. Also, I am requesting for you to kindly provide the list of your members, including their contact details (e.g., email address, contact numbers, social media accounts, etc.) where I can send them the main survey link for their official participation to this study.

The respondents of the study are the Filipino Nursing Professionals who are members of the PNA-UAE Chapter in the United Arab Emirates. Once I received your approval and obtained the list of members from your professional organization, I will send them a letter with the link to the online questionnaire through their emails and social media accounts for them to participate in and fill out the online survey. This will only require approximately 10–15 minutes to complete. The results and the data collected in this research will be used as a valuable contribution to the study of nursing practice among our Kabayans and other global nursing expatriate professionals/workers around the world. I know that with your full support as the President of PNA-UAE, this scholarly initiative will uncover new knowledge in our field of practice as global healthcare practitioners and as inspiring heroes of this modern era.

I guarantee to keep the data confidential and will be used for academic purposes only. In case you have any questions regarding this research study, please feel free to contact me. You may reach me at the contact details mentioned below.

Upon confirmation, I look forward to receiving your official letter of support from PNA-UAE for my thesis study.

Again, thank you, and I look forward to your support to this valuable initiative.

With cordial regards,

Meridein Sanchez Pacamana, RN
Candidate – Master of Arts in Nursing
University of the Philippines – Open University

Email: mspacamana@up.edu.ph
Mobile: +971 556587207

Cc: Queenie Ridulme, RN, MAN
Chair – Thesis Committee
Master of Arts in Nursing
Faculty of Management and Development Studies
University of the Philippines - Open University

Cecile Punzalan, RN, MAN
Member – Thesis Committee
Master of Arts in Nursing
Faculty of Management and Development Studies
Member - Thesis Committee
University of the Philippines - Open University

Appendix E

ERB APPROVAL AND PHILIPPINE NURSES ASSOCIATION OFFICIAL LETTER OF SUPPORT

PHILIPPINE NURSES ASSOCIATION
UNITED ARAB EMIRATES CHAPTER
(Foreign Chapter of the Philippine Nurses Association Inc.,
Member, International Council of Nurses)
pna.uaechapter@gmail.com

TO: MS. MERIDEIN SANCHEZ PACAMANA
Candidate: Master of Arts in Nursing
University of the Philippines Open University

DATE: MAY 5, 2023

SUBJECT STUDY: PNA-UAE CHAPTER CONFIRMATION OF PARTICIPATION AND ETHICAL
CLEARANCE IN MAN THESIS

Dear Ms. Meridein Pacamana,

Salamalaykum!

We are pleased to inform you that the Philippine Nurses Association - UAE Chapter has received your request to participate in your thesis study, titled "Job Satisfaction and Motivation among Filipino Nurses in the United Arab Emirates". The PNA-UAE Chapter recognizes the importance of research in the field of nursing and supports the academic endeavours of nursing students. Your thesis study is aligned with our mission to promote excellence in nursing practice, education, and leadership, and we are excited to collaborate with you on this research endeavour.

The Philippine Nursing Association - UAE Chapter Ethics Committee has officially evaluated and reviewed your research study. Upon the decision of the BOD, your proposal has met the requirements of the PNA-UAE Chapter on Ethical Conduct and full ethical approval has been granted. We, confirm our participation in your scholarly research study.

We commend your dedication and commitment to advancing nursing knowledge and practice through your thesis study. Your research has the potential to contribute to the body of nursing literature and enhance the quality of patient care in the nursing profession. As part of our commitment to supporting your research, PNA-UAE Chapter will assist and help you thru our members, relevant resources, and networking opportunities to aid in your data collection and analysis. We encourage you to keep us updated on the progress of your study and seek any assistance you may require during the research process.

On behalf of the Philippine Nurses Association — UAE Chapter, we extend our heartfelt congratulations on your thesis study and wish you every success ion your research journey. Kindly take note that this letter confirmation serves as our pledge and support to your research study. Please do not hesitate to contact us if you need any further assistance.

Sincerely,

Elma Jazz E. Macrohon, RN, MAN, DScN
Ethics Committee
Chair - House of Delegates

Red Cloud D. Capuyan, RN, IC, IIWCC-UAE
Founding President
Philippine Nurses Association - UAE Chapter

INTEGRITY.TRASPARENCY. EQUALITY.
ACCOUNTABILITY.CULTURALCOMPETENCY. EXCELLENCE

Appendix F

CV, MERIDEIN SANCHEZ PACAMANA, PH-RN, HAAD-RN

RESUME

M. Del Valle Page 1

MERIDEIN S. PACAMANA, HAAD-RN, MAN (CAND.)

Address : Al Ain, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates

Mobile : (+971) 556587207

Email : rein.pacamana@gmail.com / mspacamana@up.edu.ph

CAREER OBJECTIVE: TO BE A GLOBALLY RECOGNIZED NURSING PROFESSIONAL IN THE UNITED ARAB EMIRATES

A conscientious HAAD Registered Nurse with expertise in Emergency Department, Medical Surgical, Oncology, Orthopedic, Obstetrics and Gynecology in the provision of exemplary care to maintain the Health, Safety, and Development of patients with complete Health Care Needs.

Exceptionally talented nursing professional with strong knowledge of healthcare services, is highly experienced in delivery of individual care plan whilst working in conjunction with community and local authority teams. A proven leader who is highly known as effective influencer in uniting and guiding nursing teams toward achieving patient care goals, improving satisfaction, and continuously driving wide-spread healthcare system initiatives. Demonstrates strong management qualities with the ability to conduct patient assessments, supervise the provision of safe and compassionate care, and evaluate care effectiveness. Exceptionally talented healthcare professional who acts with integrity and in the best interest of patients while ensuring compliance with trust policies and healthcare guidelines to promote ward efficiency and the delivery of operational excellence.

In addition, combined with all the necessary professional experiences from managing executive corporate management work requirements, her role, capabilities, skills and technical know-how as an achiever has led her to be an effective provider of work-efficient management strategies and sound advice to her organization's Management Teams, Administrators & Top Management.

EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATIONS and SCHOLASTIC ACHIEVEMENTS

Master of Arts in Nursing (MAN - Candidate)
UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
Los Baños City, Laguna, Philippines
University Scholar - Faculty of Management and Development Studies

Bachelor of Science in Nursing, 2008 (Dean's Lister)
CENTRO ESCOLAR UNIVERSITY
Mendiola, Manila, Philippines
2008 Nursing Licensure Board Examination, Board Passer

Secondary School, 2003
Lady of Peace School
San Jose, Antipolo City, Rizal, Philippines
Outstanding Student and Achiever Awardee

CAREER HIGHLIGHTS

- o **Hardworking and an internationally licensed nursing professional with more than 10+ years of combined experience** in Nursing management, Emergency care, customer service management, document control, records management, secretarial administration, operations management and hospitality industry. Bringing the combined experience in delivering exceptional care to adult, pediatric patients, and their families. Highly knowledgeable about infectious disease control and hospice options and philosophies. Highly skilled at maximizing patient comfort and safety and keeping patients informed. Exceptionally well-organized and forward-thinking in managing patient needs. Consistently achieved record-high customer satisfaction rankings, improvements to the bottom line and turnaround of underperforming operations.
- o **Respected builder and leader of patient-focused and customer-focused teams;** Instill a shared, enthusiastic commitment to patient care and customer service as a key driver of company goal attainment. Leads by example, ensure the execution of all health, safety, security, quality and work operations policies.
- o **Highly articulate and effective communicator with excellent team-building and interpersonal skills;** work well with individuals at all levels. Recognized as a resource person, problem solver and creative leader. An individual achiever with superb interpersonal skills and able to establish positive relationships with patients, clients, customers, colleagues and stakeholders.
- o **Inventive and results driven individual focused on achieving exceptional results** in highly competitive environment that demand continuous improvement. She has the abilities and skills to adapt to new and diverse environments, a people person and analytical in terms or understanding new job assignments.
- o **Her work accomplishments have implemented structures in creating less stressful and yet a dynamic working environment** - opening multi-level lines of communication to connect management and employees, instituting much needed training and motivational sessions molding staff to be equipped with all the knowledge and skills to be competitive in global work settings.

INTERNATIONAL CERTIFICATIONS and CREDENTIALS

- **Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS)**, American Safety and Health Institute, Abu Dhabi, UAE – 25 July 2021 to 25 July 2023
- **Basic Life Support for Healthcare Providers (BLS)**, American Safety and Health Institute, Abu Dhabi, UAE – 23 Mar 2021 to 2023
- **Advanced Care in Intensive Care Unit and ECMO**, Department of Health, Abu Dhabi, UAE – August 2021
- **Advanced Pulmonary Procedures in Critical Care**, Department of Health, Abu Dhabi, UAE – August 2021
- **Assessment and Interpretation Values in ICU**, Department of Health, Abu Dhabi, UAE – August 2021
- **Behavioral Competencies in ICU**, Department of Health, Abu Dhabi, UAE – August 2021
- **Invasive Procedures in ICU and Management of Common Emergencies**, Department of Health, Abu Dhabi, UAE – August 2021
- **Pharmacology of ICU and Artificial Intelligence**, Department of Health, Abu Dhabi, UAE – August 2021
- **Sepsis and COVID-19 Update Training for Clinicians**, Department of Health, Abu Dhabi, UAE – August 2021
- **Special Concerns and Care Outside of Intensive Care Unit**, Department of Health, Abu Dhabi, UAE – August 2021
- **Update on Essential Training and Infection Control**, Department of Health, Abu Dhabi, UAE – August 2021
- **Management of Cardiovascular and Respiratory Emergencies**, Department of Health, Abu Dhabi, UAE – August 2021
- **Medication Administration Certification**, Aspen Medical, Abu Dhabi, UAE – August 2021
- **HAAD Registered Nurse (HAAD-RN)**, Department of Health, Abu Dhabi, UAE – Expires on 03 June 2023
- **IRCA Certified Lead Auditor in ISO 9001:2015 Quality Management System**, Chicago Institute, Abu Dhabi, UAE – June 2016
- **OSHAS 18000:2007 Occupational Health and Safety**, Chicago Training Institute, Abu Dhabi, UAE – June 2016
- **NEBOSH [International General Certificate in Health and Safety]**, Chicago Training Institute, Abu Dhabi, UAE – 3 October 2015
- **Philippine Registered Nurse (BSN – RN)**, 2008 Nursing Licensure Board Examination – PRC NURSING BOARD PASSER, 2 June 2008
- **Associate Degree in Health Science Education**, Centro Escolar University Manila, Philippines – 19 March 2006
- **Certified First Aider, Philippine National Red Cross**, Manila, Philippines – 7 January 2008

HIGHLIGHTS OF PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCES

COVID-19 RESPONSE NURSE, 4 February 2021 to Present**EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT / MEDICAL SURGICAL, SEHA Facility, Al Ain, UAE**

Aspen Medical, United Arab Emirates

Work scope, responsibilities, and achievements:

- Providing care to patients in an emergency situation.
- Administering emergency procedures such as code blue and CPR.
- Handling complex and difficult situations.
- Assesses and diagnoses the physical, psychological, and social needs of patients and determines the ER's priority of care based on patient needs and resources available.
- Quickly assessing patient need.
- Treating critical injuries, allergic reactions, and trauma.
- Cleaning of wounds.
- Drawing of blood.
- Assist physicians in activities performed for saving patient's lives.
- Develops innovative approaches to increase immunization rates among all age groups and confers with management prior to implementation.
- Engages monthly to quarterly with local agencies, coalitions, schools, etc. for promotion of immunization/vaccines.
- Assesses pockets of need within the district and establishes interventions to help meet the need.
- Knowledgeable of immunization schedules and provides vaccine and immunization updates for community and healthcare personnel. Submits all required reports to management in a timely manner.
- Works with emergency staff, administrative staff, management, and nursing staff to conduct mass vaccination clinics for public and in school settings as appropriate, with particular focus on COVID-19 Vaccine.
- Using Nursing Process, provides direct nursing services to individuals and families in the clinic setting.
- Exercises independent judgement in conducting nursing assessments and implementing appropriate intervention.
- Follows medical orders, provides necessary follow-up care to ensure program and health department standards are met.
- Provides patient education and counseling using language and methods appropriate to patient level of understanding.
- Observes confidentiality of every patient.
- Provide a supportive relationship with patient through health teaching or patient education.
- Consistently provides excellent internal and external customer service.
- Willingness to assist others by being flexible in accepting assignments, schedule changes, and workload revisions.
- Work closely with Emergency Preparedness and Response and Immunization teams to coordinate Covid-19 vaccination pods throughout our community during Phase I, II, and III.
- Assigned to lead and work closely with community partners and MRC to vaccinate appropriately according to state protocol guidelines and accordingly to which phase.
- As team leader, contribute in keeping vaccine inventory, order vaccine and supplies when necessary and keeping up to date inventory.

CUSTOMER SERVICE PROFESSIONAL, July 8, 2020 to January 14, 2021

Emirates Group, Emirates Airline, Dubai, United Arab Emirates

Ensure that the utmost standard of customer service is offered to Emirates customers, engage them with information on Emirates fares and actively issue online tickets and sell associated products by identifying customer needs through relationship building, enthusiastically seeking out sales opportunities and publicizing all Emirates related products. Make sure set quality standards are attained for all customer relations.

Work scope, responsibilities and achievements:

- o Dispense Emirates tickets to customers making sure that all essential airline rules and regulations are assimilated and that the customer request is met in order to offer them with excellent service. Emphasize to customers the appropriate requirements covering their trips such as passport, visa & health requirements and other information such as check-in place and time.
- o Responsible for administration duties including answering customer queries, problem solving and providing detailed information on new products.
- o Enthusiastically improve Emirates income earnings by specifying options to customers on all products and services such as Skywards membership (Skywards related queries), amendments, Dubai stopovers, hotel bookings, and improved fares to attain sales revenue and/or sales conversion goals.
- o Keep abreast of Emirates Group news and updates to ensure relevant professional and company standards are maintained.
- o Handle all customer service requests and complaints from Emirates Airlines passengers, from lost luggage to ticket inquires, issuing tickets quoting fares and all related duties.
- o Support Travel Agents by assisting them with bookings and special arrangements. Stand in for the Customer Sales and Service Team Leader/Contact Center Team Leaders in their time off and offer help and act as a role model to other team members.
- o Act as the first point of contact for all queries regarding complex bookings, challenging customer interactions, and other special services.
- o Ensure that all necessary ticket related documentation is filed, time tables updated, brochures, sale and promotional material is properly displayed on individual counters, providing various options to the customer which will assist in increasing sales.
- o Support the Customer Sales and Service Team Leader on all customer service requirements. Ensure that the Emirates Airline happiness program are extended to all customers with high flying results.

REGISTERED STAFF NURSE, June 17, 2016, to June 18, 2019**TUY GENERAL HOSPITAL, EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT
Tuy, Batangas, Philippines**

Ensures that health care standards in emergency area are maintained. Able to assess patients quickly, prioritize and assist in minor procedures. Manage check-in process, performance of triage work for Doctors and assisting with initial insurance paper work.

- o Receiving emergency patients with critically illnesses like RTA, multiple fractures, cardiac emergencies, and pulmonary emergencies.
- o Assesses the patient through primary assessment, triaging patients, and secondary assessment.
- o Initiation of ACLS, BLS, CPR, Inotropic, Thrombolysis, Central lines, chest tubes, cardiac pacing, pneumatic insufflations, defibrillation, closed reduction, and immobilization, POP and splint application, minor and major suturing, bone marrow, peritoneal, pleural, and fluid aspiration, lumbar puncture and etc.
- o Management of Cardia arrest, MI, CCV, LVF, CVA, COPD, ARDS, CRF, DKA, Hypoglycemia, epilepsy, GI bleeding, intestinal obstruction, urinary retention, lightning, electrocution, chest pain, musculoskeletal injuries, burns, snake bite, poisoning, drowning, removal of foreign bodies from eyes, nose, ear, and throat.
- o Preparation of patients for emergency injections and procedures such as ICD, tracheostomy, X-ray, USG, CT scan, MRI scan, laboratory tests, care of patient with ventilator, preparing patients for emergency surgeries, transferring patients from and to hospital, carry out admission procedures, maintain stock of essential items and giving physiological support to patient and family.
- o Furnished professional oncology nursing care to patients in accordance with medical practices and standards.
- o Recorded patient data prior to oncologist examinations.
- o Educated and counseled patients and family members on all aspects of cancer symptoms and treatment.
- o Monitored and updated patient treatment progress reports on a daily basis.
- o Documented patient responses to treatment and consulted oncologists as needed.
- o Providing first aid, and other necessary medication to emergency patients.
- o Giving care to fractured patients.
- o Assisting Doctors in suturing, dressing, knee aspiration, local steroid injection, and application of bandage compression.
- o Maintaining airway, breathing, and circulation.
- o Transporting trauma patients and assists in procedures such as bandaging, strapping, splintage application, plasters, POP, fiber cast, etc.
- o Providing care to patients in an emergency situation.
- o Administering emergency procedures such as code blue and CPR.
- o Handling complex and difficult situations.
- o Assesses and diagnoses the physical, psychological, and social needs of patients and determines the ER's priority of care based on patient needs and resources available.
- o Quickly assessing patient need.
- o Treating critical injuries, allergic reactions and trauma
- o Provide first aid treatment to critical patients
- o Work within the patient care units of the hospital which includes ER and ICU
- o Stabilize patients by administering IVs, fluids, medications, etc. as required.
- o Assist physicians in activities performed for saving patient's lives.
- o Participates on medical missions, giving of free medications and check-ups.
- o Monitor client's medical status, signs and symptoms and reports to nursing supervisor or medical director.
- o Works with other nursing and medical staff for the continuity of client medical care and communicates with the clinical staff regarding client's

- medical concern.
- Provide and document medical consultation, assessment, examination, treatment planning and review consistent with agency policy and requirements.
- Work in a variety of clinical settings providing medical services as a member of the multi-disciplinary treatment team.
- Work directly with clients in providing medical services and interpreting medical information.
- Provide a supportive relationship with patient through health teaching or patient education.
- Conducts training about Basic Life Support and First Aid.
- Implements program of health.
- Assists on emergency situation, giving first aid to the patients that needs immediate attention.
- Giving of IV and PO medications, charting.
- Conducts health teachings for patients' awareness.
- Treating critical injuries, allergic reactions, and trauma
- Performing minor medical operations
- Maintaining emergency room care standards.
- Cleaning of wounds.
- Drawing blood as per the doctor's order.

PROJECT EXECUTIVE SECRETARY, April 2015 to February 2016

Decovision Company, WLL (Designers & Decorators, Companies & Businesses)
Al Najda Street, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates

Assists the Executive Manager and Director of Operations in his external relationships, particularly in the agenda, connecting to the associated companies, subcontractors, partners and the whole management team. On most times, she acted as Project Director / Manager's secretary and the ambassador in behalf of the organization.

Work scope, responsibilities, and achievements:

- Leading, creating, and updating the correspondence register and submit it to the Executive Manager.
- Handling all incoming outgoing documents that are officially transmitted dispatched to field this includes letters, faxes, memorandums, conference notes, transmittal forms.
- Registering incoming outgoing correspondence in appropriate register and stamping on it to fix date of arrival and number of registration automatically, managing housing; hotel reservations and flight bookings for all the staff; making all necessary arrangements for social gatherings including catering, reservations choosing activity program, acting as a facilitator and problem solving, handling all public relation department work;
- Research, compile, assimilate, and prepare confidential and sensitive documents, and brief the executive regarding contents.
- Review, proofread, and edit documents prepared for the executive's signature.
- Update executive on status of issues before scheduled meetings.
- Prepare agenda and collect materials required for meetings, gatherings, speeches, and conferences; take minutes and keep records of proceedings as required.
- Arranged for and scheduled appointments for the executive, including interviewing callers and making proper referrals; prepared material and made arrangements for meetings as required.
- Studied reports received, checked and compared with previous reports and other data, and brought to the attention of the executive significant items, changes, errors or omissions.
- Maintained for the executive manager and members of the top brass the up-to-date management manuals, directives, organizational charts and kept the executive informed of changes.
- Take and transcribe dictation on technical and confidential matters from the executive as required.
- Coordinate and facilitate the executive's calendar to arrange appointments, meetings, and conferences.
- Read and screen incoming correspondence and reports; make preliminary assessment of the importance of materials and organize documents; handle some matters personally and forwards appropriate materials to the executive and staff.
- Responsible for the organization of the filing system and internal external distribution of the documents administrative, handling all administrative work on site; handling the cash expenses and all minor costs on site.

HOTEL FRONT OFFICE SUPERVISOR, May 2012 to March 2015

Doha Downtown Hotel (4 Star Hotel), Al Kinana, Doha, State of Qatar

Led the successful establishment of a start-up 4 Star Hotel in the development of the entire Front Office Hotel Operational Policies and Procedures which was used successfully in running the entire Front Office Department since 2012. Supervised the entire Front Office Operations and Staff of the 4-Star Hotel Apartment comprise of 271 rooms, spa, gym and outdoor swimming pool with banquet facility. Her hard-work and dedication has elevated the hotel's guest-satisfaction index by +10% from 84% to 94% within two years; ensured the swift resolution of customer issues to preserve customer loyalty while complying with the company's policies.

Work scope, responsibilities, and achievements:

- Assist the Front Office Manager in ensuring the smooth and efficient overall day-to-day operations of the Front Desk Department.
- Oversee bell and door staff in the absence of their department head.
- Provide excellent customer service per the standards of the hotel, and assist in situations to ensure customer satisfaction.
- Ensure department adherence to company policies, procedures, and standards to ensure that guest expectations are exceeded.
- Discipline, counsel and coach front office staff if necessary, using proper techniques and documentation.
- Responsible for daily monitoring and proper training of all service levels provided by employees to fellow employees and guests.
- Responsible for monitoring and supervising that front office team follow proper cash handling procedures.

- o Leads in providing staff with ongoing coaching, training and development.
- o Coordinate hotel emergency procedures within the scope of defined plans. Ensures that her team complete their tasks as instructed.
- o Prepare reports, handle special projects and assignments as required. Assist and provides solution in operational issues.
- o Maintain hygiene and organization of front desk and back office. Ensures accuracy of rooming lists, groups, arrivals, and amenities.
- o Foster an environment in which guests enjoy high levels of service and employees are motivated to deliver top performance.
- o Developed policies and procedures that will ensure that the hotel team works together in accordance to its goal to provide the highest customer service experience in turn that will result to return business for the organization.

PRIVATE DUTY STAFF NURSE, 2009 to 2012

Nightingale Nursing Services Inc. Manila, Philippines

In-charge in leading and part of the mission in delivering professional, competent, reliable and compassionate nursing. Work scope, responsibilities and achievements:

- o Provide in-home nursing medical assistance to the assigned patient.
- o Assessing changes in the medical status of the patient.
- o Assessing the physical and emotional needs of each patient.
- o Administer medications following the 10 rights of patient in medication administration.
- o Assist with feeding depending on the patient's nutritional requirement.
- o Helping patient with daily living activities.
- o Providing hospice care.
- o Monitor patient's vital sign readings.
- o Assist with other total nursing care duties.
- o Complete patient care documentation and other paperwork regarding patients' health.
- o Make independent critical decisions when necessary.

EXECUTIVE SECRETARY TO THE PRESIDENT, 2003 to 2009

Prime Consortium Lending Investment, Manila, Philippines

Working as part of a team and supporting the Company President. Responsible for the day-to-day tasks and administrative duties of the office including management of the whole reception area.

Work scope, responsibilities, and achievements:

- o Executive Secretary to the President and management team. Duties included telephone screening, appointment scheduling, travel arrangements, meeting coordination, supplies management, processing invoices, reconciling monthly credit statements from clients, troubleshooting work issues and conflicts, computer data entry, generation of daily and monthly confidential work progress and financial reports and general office duties.
- o Perform document management, record keeping, distributing, routing, and filing of all controlled documentation. Work to quality assurance procedures and other project needs specifications. Scan, catalog, create indexes, and create guide for each job.
- o In-charge in maintaining the company library and data file room where tracking of all documents checked out of library.
- o Responsible for establishing and maintaining an effective document control system.
- o Ensures that all design documentation is accurate, up to date and accurately distributed to relevant parties.
- o Conducts office management, from scheduling meetings and coordinating travel to overseeing budget and accounting functions.
- o Develops and maintains comprehensive administrative processes that improve the efficiency of day-to-day operations.
- o Acted as the timekeeping administrator for 100 employees and responsible for new employee orientation, including coordination of legal documentation for the Human Resources and Payroll departments.
- o Support the efforts, schedule management, planning and organizing all work-related tasks of the President together with other executive-level staff, including CFOs, Vice Presidents, and other senior partners within the organization.

RECOGNITIONS, AWARDS AND ACHIEVEMENTS

- o **Master of Arts in Nursing, Major in Nursing Administration (MAN – Candidate for Graduation for School Year 2022 -2023), University Scholar** – Faculty of Management and Development Studies, University of the Philippines, Los Banos City, Philippines
- o **Health Authority Abu Dhabi Registered Nurse (HAAD-RN), 2021**, Department of Health, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
- o **IRCA Certified Lead Auditor in ISO 9001:2015 Quality Management System**, Chicago Training Institute, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates – June 2016
- o **IRCA Certified Lead Auditor in OSHAS 18000:2007 Occupational Health and Safety**, Chicago Training Institute, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates – June 2016
- o **NEBOSH (International General Certificate in Health & Safety)**, Chicago Training Institute, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates – 03 October 2015
- o **Philippine Registered Nurse (BSN-RN), 2008 Nursing Licensure Board Examination** – PRC Nursing Board Passer, 02 June 2008

REFERENCES

Available upon request

Appendix G

CONFIRMATION OF SUPPORT FROM THE PHILIPPINE EMBASSY IN ABU DHABI, UNITED ARAB EMIRATES

On Tue, Apr 4, 2023 at 9:27 AM Secretary Abu Dhabi PE
<assistant.auhpe@gmail.com> wrote:

Dear Ms. Pacamana,

Good day!

This is to acknowledge receipt of your email. The Ambassador have referred your official request to the Philippine Nurses' Association here in UAE and have informed the Embassy that they will support your master's research.

You may coordinate directly with Mr. Red Capuyan, current president of the association at +971 54 470 8088.

Thank you and best regards,
Magie

--

Ms. Magnolia Abano | Secretary to the Ambassador
Embassy of the Republic of the Philippines | Abu Dhabi, UAE
www.abudhabipe.dfa.gov.ph | T +971 2 639 0002 | M +971 50 286 8568

Whether you're on-board or in- island, it's more fun in the Philippines. From live bands on deck to festivals on the street. And five-star ship dining to seafood grilling on the beach. Take your next vacation off the beaten path and into the ocean. Be part of the cruise. Be part of the fun. The Philippines is getting ready for you to enjoy a safe, healthy, and sustainable environment when you visit.

#BePartOfTheFun
#ItsMoreFunInThePhilippines

Appendix H

REQUEST LETTER OF SUPPORT FROM THE PHILIPPINE EMBASSY IN ABU DHABI, UNITED ARAB EMIRATES

To: His Excellency Alfonso Ferdinand A. Ver
Philippine Ambassador to the United Arab Emirates
The Philippine Embassy, Villa #1, W-48, Street No. 8, Sector 2-23,
Plot 51, Al Qubaisat, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates

Date: 28th of March 2023

From: Meridein Sanchez Pacamana, PH-RN, HAAD-RN
Candidate – Master of Arts in Nursing
University of the Philippines, Open University

Dear Ambassador Ver,

Greetings from Al Ain, United Arab Emirates.

My name is Meridein Sanchez Pacamana, RN-HAAD I am writing to your good office to request your support and assistance in encouraging the participation of all members of the Philippine Nursing Association in the United Arab Emirates (PNA-UAE) as respondents to my Master of Arts in Nursing Thesis at the University of the Philippines.

As you may be aware, the PNA-UAE is committed to promoting and advancing the nursing profession not only in the Philippines but also in the United Arab Emirates, where there is a sizable Filipino medical practitioner population that provides care to UAE citizens, particularly those who are based in the State of Abu Dhabi. Conducting research that will enable us to better comprehend the problems and difficulties faced by Filipino Expatriate Nurses working abroad is one of the ways we can accomplish this goal.

As part of my Master's Thesis, I am conducting a study that aims to explore the job satisfaction and work motivation of Filipino Expatriate Nurses working in the United Arab Emirates. I believe that the participation of PNA members in the UAE will be invaluable in providing insights and perspectives that will help inform my research.

However, I understand that obtaining the support of the Philippine Embassy Abu Dhabi, with your leadership, can greatly enhance our chances of encouraging PNA members in the UAE to strongly participate and support in my research study. As such, I am requesting your assistance in providing me with a letter of support from the Philippine Embassy Abu Dhabi that I can use to encourage PNA members in the UAE to take part in this valuable scholarly research in Nursing education.

As a research scholar, I am confident that with your full support, we can inspire more PNA members in the UAE to commit and support my study, which will ultimately benefit the nursing professionals in the Philippines and in other countries where Filipino nurses are employed.

Thank you for your attention to this matter, and I look forward to hearing from you soon.

Sincerely,

Meridein Sanchez Pacamana

Meridein Sanchez Pacamana, PH-RN, HAAD-RN
Candidate – Master of Arts in Nursing
University of the Philippines Open University

Email: mspacamana@up.edu.ph
Mobile: +971 55 658 7207

Appendix I

LETTER OF SUPPORT FROM THE PHILIPPINE EMBASSY ABU DHABI

EMBASSY OF THE REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES
سفارة جمهورية الفلبين أبوظبي
ABU DHABI

26 April 2023

MS. MERIDIEN SANCHEZ PACAMANA
Candidate – Master of Arts in Nursing
University of the Philippines, Open University

Dear Ms. Pacamana,

Greetings from the Philippine Embassy in Abu Dhabi!

This is with reference to your letter dated 28 March 2023 requesting the Embassy's support for your research focusing on the Filipino nurses working in the United Arab Emirates. May we kindly refer you to the Philippine Nurses' Association – UAE Chapter, the group of Filipino nurses working in the United Arab Emirates..

The Embassy has requested Mr. Red Capuyan, President of PNA-UAE Chapter, to assist you on this. You may reach Mr. Capuyan at redcloud72585@gmail.com.

Thank you and please accept our best wishes.

Sincerely yours,

MARFORD M. ANGELES
Consul General

P.O. Box : 3215 Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates
Tel.: +971 2 639 0006 / Fax: +971 2 639 0002
E-mail: auhpe@philembassy.ae / Website: www.abudhabipe.dfa.gov.ph

Appendix J THESIS PROPOSAL APPROVAL

UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY

FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT STUDIES

03 May 2023

DR. JOANE V. SERRANO

Dean, Faculty of Management and Development Studies
University of the Philippines Open University
Los Baños, Laguna

Through PROPER CHANNELS

Dear Dean Serrano:

We have the honor to inform you that the undersigned served in the oral examination of Ms. MERIDEIN PACAMANA/NA candidate who presented her thesis proposal with the final title "Job satisfaction and motivation among Filipino Nurses in the United Arab Emirates" on 18 October 2021 at 2:00 PM via Zoom and voted as follows:

PANEL MEMBERS	FOR APPROVAL	FOR DISAPPROVAL
ASST. PROF. QUEENIE R. RIDULME Adviser		<hr style="border: 1px solid black;"/>
MS. MARIA CECILIA E. PUNZALAN Critic		<hr style="border: 1px solid black;"/>
MR. FRITZ GERALD JABONETE Member		<hr style="border: 1px solid black;"/>
MS. GRACE RIEGO DE DIOS Member		<hr style="border: 1px solid black;"/>
MS. MA. ELMA MIRANDILLA Member		<hr style="border: 1px solid black;"/>

Committee's Decision:

PASSED

FAILED

Additional Remark/s: Approved with minor revisions.

Very truly yours,

ASST. PROF. QUEENIE R. RIDULME
Adviser

ASST. PROF. RIA VALERIE D. CABANES
Program Chair, MAN